

SINTERING BEHAVIOUR,
MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL
PROPERTIES OF VANADIUM
ENRICHED HIGH SPEED STEELS
PROCESSED IN VACUUM AND
NITROGEN RICH ATMOSPHERES

João Mascarenhas

An investigation of the effects of sintering atmosphere and alloy composition on the sintering behaviour, microstructures and mechanical properties of T42 type high speed steels containing 6 to 12 % vanadium.

**Submitted for the degree
Of Doctor of Philosophy**

Department of Mechanical and
Manufacturing Engineering
Engineering Materials Group

University of Bradford
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ABSTRACT:

Water atomised high vanadium containing T42-type HSS powders, compositions containing 0.5-2.7 wt% C and 6-12 wt% V, and whose mean particle sizes ranged 58-140 μm , were sintered in vacuum and $\text{N}_2+7\%\text{H}_2$ atmosphere by supersolidus liquid phase sintering (SLPS) mechanisms. SLPS densification was carried out within the $\gamma+L+\text{carbides}$ phase region. Sintering temperatures in vacuum were higher than in $\text{N}_2+7\%\text{H}_2$ atmosphere. In fact, P68 (8V-2.4C), P77 (7V-2.7C) and P81 (6V-2.6C) vacuum sintering temperatures were 1260°, 1200° and 1200°C, respectively, and when these compositions were sintered in $\text{N}_2+7\%\text{H}_2$ atmosphere the respective sintering temperatures were 1200°, 1150° and 1150°C. Sintering windows increased from about 10°C in vacuum to about 30°C in $\text{N}_2+7\%\text{H}_2$ atmosphere. Vacuum sintered microstructures at optimum sintering temperature, in the case of P68 alloy were comprised of vanadium rich MC carbides embedded in a bainitic/martensitic matrix. P77 and P81 were found to be unsinterable in vacuum as microstructures though having MC carbides also showed deleterious grain boundary M_2C eutectic carbides even in undersintered specimens. Bend strength of vacuum sintered P68 alloy was in the 2-2.4 GPa over a hardness range of 855-900 HV.

$\text{N}_2+7\%\text{H}_2$ atmosphere sintered specimens showed decreasing sinterability with decreasing carbon and increasing vanadium contents, due to the constriction of the $\gamma+L+\text{carbide}/\text{carbonitride}$ phase region. Microstructures of $\text{N}_2+7\%\text{H}_2$ atmosphere sintered specimens comprised grain boundary MX carbonitrides along with grain boundary M_6C and M_3C carbides, and a pearlitic matrix. The MX carbonitride phase was the only one, which contained nitrogen. Compositions with carbon contents in excess of 3 wt% were found to be unsinterable, they distorted before attaining full density when sintered at 1110°C, due to the formation of extensive amounts of M_3C carbide. This was due to sintering involving heating and cooling through an invariant $\gamma+L+\text{M}_6\text{C}+\text{MX}+\text{M}_3\text{C}$ phase region. The presence of this region represented a compositional barrier limiting the range of alloys which could be sintered satisfactorily to full density. A comprehensive sintering mechanism was developed for the $\text{N}_2+7\%\text{H}_2$ atmosphere sintering of the vanadium containing HSS: below solidus, nitrogen replaces carbon in the MC carbides which become *in situ* formed MX carbonitrides, the released carbon forming M_3C carbides and decreasing solidus, then the sintering temperature; with increasing temperature, but still below solidus, *in situ* MX dissolve and grain boundary MX are formed, these later ones having higher vanadium content; on crossing the solidus M_3C carbides liquate forming a Cr-rich liquid which is responsible for densification.

Hardness of heat treated specimens sintered in $\text{N}_2+7\%\text{H}_2$ atmosphere were higher, 885-997 HV, when compared to vacuum sintered material, 855-900 HV. Bend strength values obtained in the present research were in the range 2-2.4 GPa for P68 vacuum sintered composition. Nitrogen sintered P68, P77 and P81 compositions showed bend strength in the range 1.8-2.1 GPa.

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FELIX QUI POTUIT RERUM COGNOSCERE CAUSAS
(happy the ones who could know the origin of the things)

To my wife Cris

To my parents

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1- INTRODUCTION

1.1-GENERAL REMARKS

High Speed Steels (HSS), developed from Mushet's air hardening steels have the ability to maintain high levels of hardness at temperatures up to $\approx 500^{\circ}\text{C}$ [1,2]. This property enabled them to be used to cut metals at much higher speeds than the previously employed carbon tool steels; hence their name [1,2]. They are high alloy steels containing 20 to 30 wt% alloying additions of the carbide forming elements tungsten, molybdenum, chromium and vanadium. High speed steels are designated in British Standard [3] as either molybdenum (M series) or tungsten (T series) based. Not all compositions fall within this classification. The non-carbide forming element cobalt is added to some alloys. Nominal compositions of some HSS are given in Table 1.1.

High Speed Steels are utilised in the quenched and tempered condition. In this condition their microstructures comprise 20-30 volume % of primary carbides, formed during solidification of the melt, dispersed in a matrix of tempered martensite. These primary carbides are typically 1-20 μm across. However the actual primary carbide phases present, their particle size distribution and volume fractions depend on both alloy composition and method of manufacture [1]. The martensite is precipitation hardened by dispersions of much finer, 10-20 nm across, secondary carbides resulting from solid state precipitation during tempering [4,5]. HSS are characterised by high hardness, 800-1000 HV (66-70 HRC) [1,6]; high fracture strength, 1-5 GPa [1,2,6,7,8,9,10] and moderate fracture toughness (K_{IC}) 10-18 $\text{MPa m}^{1/2}$ [2,9,11] combined with good wear resistance. Hardness is maintained at elevated temperatures, a property of HSS's referred to as red hardness [1,12]. These values can be varied by heat treatment, enabling properties to be tailored to particular applications [12,13].

Originally, all HSSs were produced by cast and wrought (CW) processes. The complex solidification of these alloys through peritectic and eutectic reactions, results in segregated “as-cast” structures containing extensive networks of eutectic carbides [14]. “As-cast” HSS’s are too brittle for practical purposes and the eutectic structures are broken down by extensive hot working. However, this operation produces anisotropic microstructures with carbide bands and clusters aligned in the hot worked direction, leading to anisotropic properties [1].

Nowadays, significant amounts of HSS are produced by Powder Metallurgy (PM) processing. The majority of PM HSS is produced by hot isostatic pressing (HIPping) of spherical gas atomised powders [15,16,17,18]. Alternatively, cheaper irregular water atomised powders can be processed by cold compaction in rigid dies or cold isostatic pressing followed by batch vacuum sintering to nominally 100% theoretical density [19,20]. Variations to this route comprise either sinter + HIP [21,22,23] or sinter + hot work [24] in order to remove residual porosity. PM routes produce uniform microstructures with the carbide sizes being dependent on the processing route. Vacuum sintering produces carbides similar in size, but not in distribution, as cast and wrought steels whereas carbides in HIPped materials are much finer, maximum diameter no more than 5 μm across [19,25]

A recent PM development is the sintering of vanadium containing HSS in nitrogen-rich atmospheres [26-37]. This results in lowering of the sintering temperatures and ultimately may facilitate processing using cheaper continuous sintering instead of high temperature batch production [28]. Details of the sintering mechanisms have yet to be established. It is the study of this latter process that is the main objective of this investigation.

Although high speed steel have been superseded by cemented carbides for the majority of turning operations they remain the most widely used material for drilling

operations. According to Edwards [38] 80% of all drilling operations are performed using HSS drills. Other popular applications for HSS are for milling [2] and gear hobbing operations [38]. High purity cast and wrought M50 and to a lesser extent T1 alloys produced by VIM/VAR and EFR techniques are the approved materials for mainline aero-gas turbine engine bearings [39]. In addition to metal cutting applications PM processed HSS are used or under development for automotive applications, in particular for valve train components; rocker arms, valve guides and particularly valve seat inserts [40,41,42].

1.2-CONSTITUTION OF HIGH SPEED STEELS

1.2.1-ROLE OF ALLOYING ELEMENTS IN HSS

The generic name *High Speed Steel* covers a wide range of compositions. The composition range is wide, Figure 1.1, but some authors considered them initially within a framework of a ternary Fe-W-C alloy [1], but this is not quite accurate as there is also the addition of chromium, vanadium, molybdenum and sometimes cobalt. They also can be considered within the quaternary alloy system Fe-Cr-W(Mo)-C, the vanadium effect requiring special consideration [43]. Hence, it is better to consider high speed steels as a system of five components. Molybdenum sometimes replaces part of the tungsten, 1 wt% molybdenum having the same effect as 2 wt% tungsten [1]. When in the molten state, high speed steels may be considered as a reasonably homogeneous solution, but once solidification has been initiated, the solid material never again assumes a single-phase condition. In the solid state, high speed steels are composed of carbides embedded in a ferritic matrix in the annealed condition or tempered martensite in the heat treated state [1,13,44]. The characteristics of each high speed steel grade are due to the alloying

elements which enter its composition, each one contributing in a different manner to the final steel properties through their effects on the type of carbides produced, their volume fraction and the influence elements have on the heat treatment response [1,13,44]. Matrix composition does not alter greatly, the differences between alloys being due to different carbide types and volume fractions formed in the microstructure [1]. So, the effect of each alloying element should be considered.

Carbon is the most important constituent element concerning to the hardening operation [1,12,44]. In the as-annealed condition, most of the carbon is present as carbides whilst during the austenitizing process some of the carbides are dissolved: the carbon which enters the matrix at this stage is responsible for the martensitic hardening and the carbide precipitation on tempering which causes the secondary hardening typical of high speed steels [1,44]. Carbon is at its most effective when it is present in such amounts that it will satisfy the stoichiometric requirements of formation of the alloy carbides present in the hardened and tempered samples [1]. Therefore, the carbon required (wt%) for each percent of alloy constituent and taking into account the type of carbide that each one forms, is reported [1] as being 0.033% C for each 1% of W (M_6C), 0.063 % C for 1% Mo (M_2C), 0.176% C for 1% V (V_4C_3) and 0.060% C for 1% Cr ($M_{23}C_7$). In the case of M2 HSS the standard carbon level range is 0.8-0.9 wt%, from the stoichiometric point of view only the needs for W, Mo and V are satisfied [1]. If allowance for Cr is made, the C content should be about 1.1 wt% for optimum results [1]. Carbon content can have a significant effect on the solidus, increasing carbon content decreases solidus [45,46,47,48]. Special attention must be paid for increased carbon steels as the higher the carbon content, the closer the solidus temperature will approach the upper limit of heat treatment range, so the greater the risk of incipient melting in hardening [1].

Chromium is present in almost all the high speed steels (3-5 wt%), its role being to provide hardenability, by slowing down austenite transformation reactions, provide the carbon necessary for hardening as its carbides readily dissolve in the austenite during heat treatment, Figure 1.2, retard precipitation of carbides during tempering, improve cutting properties and retard scaling [1,2]. It forms $M_{23}C_6$ -, M_3C - and M_7C_3 -type carbides. In current standard grades of HSS's these are normally not primary carbides, i.e. carbides formed during solidification processes, instead they are precipitated during annealing processes which are used to soften materials prior to machining [1,12,13]. The main disadvantage in the use of chromium as an alloying element is that its carbides dissolve at 1000°C and does not prevent grain growth [12]. Care must then be taken to avoid overheating or holding too long at the austenitizing temperature [12,13,49,50].

Tungsten and molybdenum perform similar purposes and are more or less interchangeable on an atomic basis [1,2]. Usual compositional ranges are 1.5-20 wt% for tungsten and 3.5-9.5 wt% for molybdenum. Both elements promote resistance to tempering, and cutting efficiency is increased as the tungsten content, or its molybdenum equivalent is increased. Combined with carbon these elements form the complex stable carbides that are typical of the high speed steels – M_6C (f.c.c.) type carbide – whose composition varies between Fe_3W_3C and Fe_4W_2C , or more generally $(Fe,Mo,W)_6C$, W and Mo being freely interchangeable on an atomic basis [1,44]. The composition of several carbides present in HSS are shown in Table 1.2. In as-cast high speed steels the M_6C carbide appears in the eutectic form [1,14]. In W-grade steels, and less frequently in Mo-grade steels (those where vanadium content is low, i.e. 1-2 wt%) the eutectic takes the form of a M_6C herring bone structure. Molybdenum, on the other hand, forms a M_2C -type feathery eutectic or rod shaped carbide in as-cast steels [1,14,51,52,53]. This carbide is,

however, unstable and reacts with iron to form M_6C and MC carbides when heated at 1100-1200°C according to $M_2C + \gamma\text{-Fe} \rightarrow M_6C + MC$ [1,14,51,54], or during the hot working operation [14]. The M_2C eutectic volume fraction has been found to be dependent on the solidification rate: slow solidification favours M_6C as the eutectic carbide, whilst rapid solidification favours M_2C [55]. The formation of M_2C eutectic type instead of the M_6C eutectic is known to be favoured by high levels of carbon, vanadium [14,51], and a high Mo/W ratio [14]. On the other hand, though M_2C , as a component of the as-cast microstructures of some high speed steels, e.g. M2, has been considered as an undesirable feature because it is associated with embrittlement [56]. However, according to Fishmeister et al [14] it has properties which perhaps have not been yet fully appreciated, so that as it forms a finer eutectic structure, it is easier to break down during hot working. These two elements greatly contribute to the red hardness, for which the high speed steels are prominent, due to the formation of the reported M_2C (W_2C , Mo_2C) carbides in the tempered martensite of heat treated HSS's [1].

The Vanadium is always present in cast and wrought high speed steels, within the range 1-5 wt%, or in higher concentrations in powder metallurgy alloys, such as ASP60 [15,19]. The main role of vanadium is to give rise to the very hard (MC -3000 HV [1,2], M_2C -2000HV [1], M_6C -1500HV [1]) non-stoichiometric MC -type carbide (VC - V_4C_3), its actual composition being closer to V_4C_3 [43,44]. These, MC hard particles are important in the enforcement of abrasion resistance [57]. MC is a stable carbide only sparingly soluble in the matrix during industrial heat treatment practice, Figure 1.2. As such it pins austenite grain boundaries, minimising grain growth during heat treatment [1,12,58]. Vanadium behaviour is similar to tungsten or molybdenum, though since it has a much stronger carbide forming tendency, 1 wt% vanadium can replace 4 wt% tungsten [44]. Another

effect of the stability of the vanadium carbide is that vanadium additions tend to displace the alloys phase diagrams to the right, so that for a given carbon content a high vanadium content will give the same effect as reducing carbon [1]: it is an α -phase stabiliser [1,44].

Despite the referred to above regarding to low solubility of the vanadium carbide in the matrix, there is enough solubility to have an important effect on heat treatment. MC solubility is enhanced when primary carbide size is rather small [52]. On quenching, vanadium carbide precipitates at grain boundaries allowing austenite grains to be delineated, and on tempering, vanadium delays overtempering of the martensitic structures, being the most effective element under this concern, because it promotes secondary hardening due to the precipitation of V_4C_3 [1,4,44]. Due to its high hardness and resistance to dissolution vanadium carbides can cause difficulty in grinding particularly if they are coarse [1,7,59].

It was found [51] that during the solidification process of M2-type HSS, a low carbon content as well as a low vanadium content favoured the precipitation of M_6C -eutectic carbides. On the other hand, a high carbon content as well as a high vanadium content favoured the precipitation of MC and M_2C carbides. For the same steel it was also reported that vanadium has influence on the volume fraction of MC carbides: above 1.9 wt% vanadium the amount of MC is almost proportional to the vanadium content [51].

Cobalt is another alloying element present in the composition of many high speed steels. It does not form any carbide but it enters into the matrix, raising the solidus temperature, providing an opportunity to raise the hardening temperature, what results in an increased carbide solution [1] and in higher secondary carbide precipitation. For a given hardening temperature, increasing the cobalt content reduces the degree of austenite retention [1]. The thermal conductivity is also increased, particularly at high temperatures,

with increasing cobalt content. Reduced toughness (especially in interrupted cutting) and wear resistance are the negative results of cobalt addition. The current high speed steels cobalt additions are up to 8 wt%, because the additions above this value have insignificant effect, as reported by various authors [60,61,62]. On the microstructure, cobalt seems to have minor effects, for a correctly heat treated sample.

Nitrogen forms a solid solution in ferrite with a solubility of 0.001% at room temperature, increasing a little bit more to 0.02% at 425°C [44]. It favours brittleness and ageing processes, steel nitrogen content depends on the steelmaking process, as shown in Table 1.3 [13]. In HSS's nitrogen has similar effects as those of both carbon and silicon [1]. It lowers the as-quenched hardness and raises the tempered hardness: it stabilises austenite, like carbon, increasing its retention on quenching, and concerning to this its effect is more or less additive to that of carbon, this effect being maximised in the absence of strong nitride formers such as aluminium and titanium [1]. Its effect on suppressing M_2C formation is similar to, and additive to, that of silicon [1]. Sudo et al [63] working with cast M2-type alloys, 0.87C-5Mo-6W-4Cr, observed that the morphology of MC primary carbides was found to change from globular to dendritic type when nitrogen content was decreased from 0.028 wt% to 0.003 wt%. Rasheva et al [64] working on melting and casting under gas pressure of a P6A2M5 tool steel, 6W- 5Mo- 2V- 0.0-0.5N, found that for nitrogen contents of 0.5 wt%, ingots exhibited an homogeneous dispersion of M_6C eutectic carbides and M(CN) carbonitrides and, low segregation of nitrogen and carbon. In their work [64], M(CN) carbonitrides composition was reported as being 0.5W-0.5Mo-5.88Cr-85.2V-1.34Fe-0.01Mn (wt%).

Figure 1.3 shows the volume fraction of carbides in T1, M2 and T15 HSS's. It can be seen that the highest volume fraction belongs to M_6C carbide, also known as the HSS carbide [1].

1.3-PROCESSING OF HIGH SPEED STEELS

1.3.1 - CAST AND WROUGHT HIGH SPEED STEELS

High speed steels can be considered homogeneous when they are in the liquid state, but as soon as solidification starts, these materials never again assume a single-phase condition. Phase diagrams of the T1 and M2 HSS are shown in Figure 1.4 [65,66,67]. When in the solid state, HSS are constituted by the matrix and the carbides these last responsible for the wear-resistant properties of these type of steels. To produce a steel ingot of a particular desired composition, the respective melt is cast in a mould. The “as-cast” structure of HSS is quite different from the one accepted as normal for the production of tools [1,14], because of the vast eutectic carbide areas present in the structure, which weaken the steel, Figure 1.5, and are a consequence of the peritectic and eutectic reactions. These deleterious carbides are formed during the steel solidification, and their morphology is dependent on both composition and cooling rate [1]. Solidification has been described by a number of authors [1,14,53]. The expected reactions to occur during solidification of T1 HSS (0.7-0.78 wt%C) would be in the general following order:

where L = liquid, A = austenite, F = ferrite and C = carbide(s) [1,44]. This sequence depends on the steels composition, particularly carbon content, since the higher carbon containing steels, e.g. T15 (1.3-1.5 wt%C), commence solidification with the precipitation of austenite rather than δ -ferrite [1]. The “as-cast” structure can be predicted from the phase diagrams for each alloy, and is a function of the alloy composition, and phase diagram regions that the alloy crosses during solidification.

Depending on the type of steel, e.g. if type T (tungsten-rich) or type M (molybdenum-rich), the predominant eutectic carbide changes. Hence, in type T (and less frequently in molybdenum steels), where the most usual carbide is M_6C , the most usual eutectic carbide is $M_6C +$ austenite (γ), this carbide occurring with the herringbone-type morphology. Another eutectic that occurs in most of the molybdenum and tungsten-molybdenum HSS is the feathery or rod shaped eutectic, $\gamma - M_2C$. Though this carbide transforms to M_6C (and MC) carbide when the steel is heated at 1200°C [1], if it remains in the steel structure it will be more easily broken up in subsequent working operations (hot rolling or forging), or even in heat treatment, than in the case of the herringbone type. When the “as-cast” structure is eliminated by working, the carbides (that consequently became individual particles) align in bands oriented parallel to the working direction. This banded structure, which cannot be modified by subsequent mechanical or heat treatments, results in a steel with anisotropic properties [1]. These can lead not only to different thermal expansion coefficients and distortion during subsequent heat treatments, or even to component breaking, but also to localised melting during austenitization due to chemical heterogeneities [1].

As a consequence of the working operations, the material remain with high internal stress and it must be annealed before final machining and heat treatment [12,13,49]. When

“as-cast” material is used in the fabrication of components, the machining operations can waste about 50 to 80% of the initial material, besides expensive labour costs and energy consumption [40,68].

1.4 - POWDER METALLURGY OF HIGH SPEED STEELS

Powder metallurgy processing routes for the manufacture of high speed steels were developed in the 1960's and 1970's in an attempt to overcome the problems of cast and wrought high speed steels described above. Two generic routes have been developed - hot isostatic pressing of gas atomised prealloyed powders [69,70] and cold compaction and vacuum sintering of water atomised powders [69,70]. Both these processes result in more homogeneous microstructures than is possible with conventional cast and wrought processing. HIPped materials possess finer microstructures compared to those produced by vacuum sintering [42]. A particular advantage of the vacuum sintering route is its near-net-shape capability, which maximises material utilization [69,71]. A particular advantage of PM processing is the ability to produce higher alloy containing steels than is possible by cast and wrought processing, Figure 1.1. For example it is well known [1,72] that vanadium contents greater than 5 wt% degrades the forgeability of cast ingots. This restriction does not apply to PM processing and high vanadium grades such as ASP60, Table 1.1, are processable by both HIPping [15,17] and vacuum sintering routes [19,25,73].

1.4.1 - ATOMISATION

The first step in manufacture of HSS's is powder production. Powders are prepared by disintegration of a prealloyed melt by either atomisation using high pressure gas or water jets [40,69,70,74,75]. In a general way, the melted metal is poured into the atomiser

tundish, which controls the metal flow providing a constant melt stream. This control is made by a nozzle placed at the tundish base. The nozzle dimensions constrict both liquid metal flow shape and dimension. Hence, decreasing the nozzle length/diameter ratio, the liquid metal flow changes from turbulent to laminar [76]. Therefore, during conventional gas or water atomisation, five different stages can be distinguished [77]. These are shown schematically in Figure 1.6:

- Stage I - Wave formation due to little perturbations on the liquid metal surface.
- Stage II - Wave fragment and ligament formation due to shearing forces on the perturbations observed at Stage I.
- Stage III - Ligament pulverisation into droplets (primary atomisation); at this stage, regular shaped particles occur if it exists a high superficial tension and a low cooling rate; if the superficial tension is low and the cooling rate high, irregular particles are then obtained.
- Stage IV - Additional deformation and fragmentation (thinning) of the droplets and wave fragments, which origins smaller particles (secondary atomisation).
- Stage V - Collision and particle coalescence.

As gas atomisation is of minor interest for the present research, it will only be described briefly. Full descriptions are given by Yule et al [74], German [69,70] and Klar et al [77]. Gas atomisation consists of pulverisation of a liquid metal stream by means of a high pressure gas, normally in the range 2-5 MPa [69]. After the liquid metal pulverisation by the gas (which can be nitrogen, helium or argon [69]), the resulting droplets contract due to surface tension, spheroidising and solidifying before contact the atomiser walls. The gas atomisers can be either vertical or horizontal, depending on the alloy melting point, the

vertical ones (which can have 25 or more m high [78]) used for metals and alloys, which possess a high melting point.

The parameters which can influence the gas atomisation results are various, such as: gas type, residual atmosphere, melt viscosity and temperature, type of alloy, liquid metal flow, gas pressure, speed and flow, nozzles geometry and gas temperature [69], the resulting atomised particles being spherical. A consequence of this spherical shape, is that these powders need encapsulation for further processing since they can not be held together by mechanical interlocking of individual particles [15,16,19,79].

1.4.1.1 - WATER ATOMISATION

Water atomisation is the most common metal powder production technique, either for alloys or elemental powders. The process is similar to gas atomisation, except in the cooling rate of the atomised particles which is higher [69,70,74] and the atomising fluid properties. High pressure water jets are sprayed towards the liquid metal stream, forcing its disintegration and rapid cooling. The resultant powder is more irregular than gas atomised powders, surfaces are rougher and oxidised. As a consequence of the rapid cooling, water atomised powders have very little chemical segregation within each powder particle, which results in a higher chemical homogeneity of the powder [69,74,77].

The high pressure water jet (maximum pressure values can attain 65 MPa [80] or even 150 MPa [74]) can be guided by discrete nozzles, multiple discrete nozzles or annular (or “cone-jets”) ones [74,77]. The nozzle systems used in the high pressure units are specially adapted from the ones used at low pressures, several factors need to be borne in mind by designers or operators of these systems. A special care is needed for the water

nozzles as the velocity of water, U_w^2 , leaving a water-nozzle rises with pressure, ΔP_w , as shown by [74]:

$$\rho_w U_w^2 = 2 \Delta P_w \quad (1.1)$$

where $\rho_w=1000 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, meaning that the water velocity approaches 300 m s^{-1} at a pressure of 45 MPa. So, using higher pressures the water jets become supersonic. Another concern that is necessary to beware of is the rise in water temperature due to the pumping energy [74]:

$$\Delta T = \Delta P_w / (C_{pw} \rho_w) \quad (1.2)$$

where C_{pw} is the specific heat of water (4.1 kJ kg K^{-1}), giving 2.4 K per 10 MPa (100 bar). Hence, operating at a pressure of 100 MPa the water is heated up by 24 K, which is as much as the mean temperature rise due to the metal heat content when atomising steel with a water/metal ratio of 13:1. This is the reason why secondary cooling water jets injecting into the atomising chamber are often used so as to cool the atomised stream of powder, thereby preventing boiling [74].

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE POWDER PARTICLES SIZE AND SHAPE

The water atomisation of metallic powders is not a simple and linear process. The technical development in this field has been carried out basically in an empirically way, and has been limited, as the water atomising systems are very complex and not amenable to rigorous theoretical treatments or modelling techniques and because large scale technical development work is uneconomical and even unsafe [81].

Therefore, the powder producer has to handle molten materials, whose pouring temperature is high, where changes in its viscosity and surface tension can arise due to small compositional changes. Hence, the objective of a powder producer is to obtain, first a

powder which is consistent from batch to batch, and secondly to produce powders of different alloys with consistent physical properties especially the apparent density, flowability and particle size and shape, these must be controlled since they affect die fill and compressibility. Variations in these result in variation in green density, which may result in variations in sintered sample size and properties [40,69,70,74]. To be successful in these two objectives it is necessary to have a high level of technical *know-how* and control over the several variables present in atomisation [74,80].

Some variables that are present in the water atomisation process and their effects on the size and shape of the powder particles are described below.

SUPERHEAT

When the melt temperature is increased, its both surface tension and viscosity are decreased. Higher the superheat longer the liquid metal cooling time and consequently the time during which the metal can be pulverised [80]. The effects due to surface tension are fairly modest, with a 100°C rise in superheat typically reducing particle size by only about 5-10 % in water atomisation of metals melting above 500°C (Cu-Sn, Zn) [80].

WATER PRESSURE

The water pressure has an enormous effect on the size of the powder particles, higher pressures producing finer powder particles [69,74,75]. Water pressures can be used from 30 KPa to 65 MPa [80]. In water atomisation, the water pressure is directly related with its velocity. So, it is expected that as the energy of the atomising fluid is increased the median particle size would be decreased. On the other hand, the apparent density of the powder does not seem to be affected significantly by the atomising fluid pressure. There is

an expression that correlates the water pressure with the median particle size of the atomised powders, as follows [80,81]:

$$D = K P^{-n} \quad (1.3)$$

where D is the median particle size, K is a constant dependent on atomiser parameters and melt properties, P is the water pressure and n is an index normally taking values between 0.7 and 1.2.

FLOWRATE OF ATOMISING FLUID

It might be expected that this parameter would have a similar effect to that of the pressure of the atomising fluid, as increasing the flowrate, the atomising jets energy is increased. However, in this case it seems not to have any significant effect on the median particle size, though the powder apparent density is decreased. When the pressure is constant, the velocity of the atomising fluid remains constant as well. Hence, it can be concluded that the factor that influence the mean particle size is the velocity, whilst the fluid flowrate influences the apparent density of the atomised powder, i.e. the powder particles become more irregular [81].

FLOWRATE OF LIQUID METAL

In this case one could think that increasing the liquid metal flowrate, it would have an opposite effect increasing the flowrate of the atomising fluid, as the relative energy of the atomising fluid, in relation to the amount of material to be atomised, is reduced. Nevertheless, the apparent density is not significantly affected by the liquid metal flowrate, whilst the median particle size increases concomitantly with it. This can be explained in terms of the active mechanisms operating at the atomising zone, since when the liquid

metal flowrate is increased, in general a increase of the cross section of the metal stream is observed [74,81].

WATER / METAL RATIO

When the atomising fluid pressure is maintained constant, an increasing of the water/metal flow ratio seems to produce an important decrease of the median particle size [81]. Nevertheless, in certain conditions, this effect is more evident if only the main water jets flow is considered in the water/metal ratio and not the total water flow [82]. This can show that, in this case, the atomisation is completed after the contact of the metal stream with the water jets of the main nozzles. Commercial water atomisation systems operate normally with water/metal ratios in the range 5:1 to 10:1 [75].

SURFACE TENSION OF THE LIQUID METAL

During atomisation, the surface tension forces tend to spheroidize each irregular liquid metal droplet, as the forces of the atomising medium decrease with the distance to the optimal atomising zone. Hence, as a droplet leaves the high turbulence atomising zone, the surface tension becomes more important, if the droplet is not cooled too much and its viscosity becomes higher, or it is already solidified. In this point, the melt temperature, the cooling rate, the droplet size and the chemical reactions with the atomising fluid which all affect the surface tension and viscosity are critical [77].

As the liquid metal surface tension increases, the median particle size and the powder apparent density increase as well. The last one increases because the surface tension forces tend to minimise the individual particle surface area, making them more

spherical. This tendency to minimise the powder particles surface area promotes an increasing in the median particle size [81].

It is known that small alloying element additions can promote big differences in the type of powder produced, as well as different alloys have a different behaviour, in terms of atomisation, and that these effects cause changes in the liquid metal surface tension [75,83].

The powder particle morphology becomes more irregular, if little alloying element additions, which tend to decrease the surface tension of the liquid metal, are carried out prior to atomisation.

OTHER FACTORS

There are other factors that influence the size and shape of the water atomised powder particles, such as the water nozzle design, the liquid metal stream turbulence, the collision effect in the final stages of atomisation (this effect, under conditions of high surface tension and low cooling rate, determines that the particle size is determined by the number of collisions among the spherical primary particles. These collisions can promote clustering of several thousands of these particles, producing a final coarse particle of about 125 μm , while the particle shape is determined by the coalescence rate after collisions [40,77]. This shape is also affected by other factors such as the primary particle size, temperature, composition and atomising fluid velocity, alloying content, oxidation rate and solubility of the formed oxides.

Normally, powder chemistry can be defined in two ways: major constituents and impurities [74]. The impurities can be of three different classes: (a) exogenous impurities, (b) dissolved impurities and (c) surface contamination. The first class includes impurities, which were floating in the melt before atomisation and the ones, which contaminate the powder upon atomisation [74]. Refractory or ceramic inclusions from the crucible or tundish nozzle can also occur [74]. Exogenous impurities are detrimental especially if the powder is to be compacted or to become a structural member or tool as is the case of HSS's [41,71,84], as those give rise to major inclusions in the final product with drastic results in crack initiation under service [19,25,73]. In order to reduce the non-metallic inclusion content of the powders, Wright et al [85] developed a special melt filtration technique. Ceramic foam filters were cemented into ceramic inserts and placed inside the tundish. The foam filters with the commercial name STELEX made of zirconia toughened alumina capable of withstanding molten metal at temperatures up to 1680°C.

Dissolved impurities in the metal can be considered of considerable importance to the atomisation process and product quality, but are often present in such small amounts that they are difficult to measure [74]. In this class of impurities, noble gases resulting from atomisation runs can be considered as such small amounts as 1 p.p.m. of argon can result in very brittle and weak parts due to a very pronounced porosity giving rise to "Swiss cheese" appearance of HSS's heat treated parts [74]. Surface oxides are the most common surface contamination, and they will be referred in the next section.

Water atomised HSS's powders can have a typical dendritic solidification microstructure composed of MC and M₆C carbides imbedded in a martensitic matrix [19,73,75]. However powders can show a fine-scale cellular substructure matrix, which is consistent with the high cooling rates of droplets intrinsic to water atomisation [75].

OXIDATION OF THE WATER ATOMISED POWDERS

One disadvantage of the water atomisation process, is that oxidation can occur either in the melt, prior to atomisation, or inside the atomising chamber. This oxidation, if it is not eliminated, can prevent efficient physical contact during compaction, among the powder particles. Additionally it may make sintering more difficult [40]. Oxygen content for water atomised powders range 1000-3000 ppm [69,74] while for gas atomised powders the oxygen content is <150 ppm [69,74]. Hence, during water atomisation, the majority of metallic elements react either with the water or with the steam to form oxides, by the following chemical reaction:

In general, oxidation increases with increasing melt superheat, and depends on the powder particle size [69,77,86]. For coarser powder particles the cooling time and the exposition to oxidation increase and the oxide layer become thicker. Contrarily, when the powder particle size decreases, the powder specific surface area increases. So, although finer particles cool more rapidly and having thinner surface oxides, as their surface area (per weight unit) is higher, the final oxygen content increases [77].

If the melt is protected by an inert gas atmosphere, the oxidation is produced mainly during the pouring from the induction furnace to the atomiser tundish, and still when in contact with the steam and water inside the atomising chamber. About 80 to 90% of the oxygen content of the water atomised powders, which are incorporated during atomisation, are at the powder particles surfaces. The remaining is within the particles either in solution or as microscopic oxides. These are the reasons why water atomisation is not used for the production of highly reactive metals powders, such as titanium and the superalloys. Surface oxidation of the as-atomised powders can be sometimes of minor importance, if the surface oxides are amenable to reducing atmospheres and the as-atomised oxygen content is

considered not too high, i.e. not >1000 p.p.m. [19,73,74]. On the other hand, dissolved oxygen in the melt is much more difficult to remove as it has to diffuse to the powder surface, and normally oxygen diffusion in solid metals is very slow [74,87,88]. Water atomisation has been successfully used for the production of stainless steels and high speed steels, because the oxide films can be reduced through annealing or even during sintering [89]. Annealing will reduce hardness (e.g. from 520 HV0.05 to 350 HV0.05) [73] and powders' oxygen content to range 800-1200 ppm [19,20,73]. Typical temperatures used are 800°-950°C in conjunction with cooling rates of 1-2°C min⁻¹, under atmosphere, normally hydrogen [69], or vacuum [19,20,69,73,83].

1.4.2 - PROCESSING ROUTES

Different routes are available to achieve full density of the powders produced by different powder fabrication techniques, e.g. near-net-shape, hot isostatic pressing (HIP), powder forging, powder extrusion, powder rolling and plasma spraying, [40,69,86]. Among them, some that are of most interest to high speed steels will be described.

1.4.2.1 - H.I.P. OF GAS ATOMISED POWDERS

As gas atomised powders are spherical shaped, they are not compactable by cold compaction. So, encapsulation in shaped containers and HIPping of these powders is required. HIP is the process whereby an encapsulated powder is heated somewhat to a temperature below the alloy solidus along with high pressure (up to 300 MPa though 100 MPa being the average pressure [40,84]). This process, in which densification occurs by solid state sintering, produces very fine and isotropic microstructures. It is the case of the ASP steels [15,16,17,79] where the harmful effect of large carbides, obtained in conventional ingot wrought steels, has been eliminated. But the obtained billets, some weighing over 1 ton, need further hot working, to eliminate residual porosity. These later

processes can give the material a certain anisotropy. In fact, though isotropic microstructures are claimed [79,15,16,17], a certain anisotropy was found by Mascarenhas [73] and Oliveira et al [19] when ASP60 was 3-point bend tested on both longitudinal and transverse sections, transverse rupture strength was 4.3 and 3.4 GPa, respectively.

1.4.2.2 - SINTERING OF NEAR NET SHAPES

One of the PM successes is its capability of holding close dimensional tolerances, what requires little secondary processing to finish a PM part [90]. Across the last years, with rising labour and materials costs, parts production became expensive, what interested manufacturers of production-line, in turning out parts as close as possible to finished, or net shape [71].

COLD COMPACTING AND VACUUM SINTERING

Cold compaction is used when irregular powders are to be shaped by means of an external source of pressure [91] in order to deform the powder particles into a high density compact, (at in the case of HSS about 70 % theoretical density [40]), while providing shape and dimensional control to the powder [13]. Conventional powder compaction is carried out in uniaxial hard tooling consisting of a die, with the desired shape for the compact, which is filled with the powder, and two punches that provide compression. Pressures used are typically in the range 600-800 MPa [19,40,69,73]. When complex shapes are required, the number of punches is increased, in order to give uniformity in the compact green density since density gradients translate into differential shrinkage during sintering [40,69,91]. On the other hand, for complex shapes involving undercuts or large length to

diameter ratios, cold isostatic pressing (CIP) can be used. In this case, a flexible mould is filled with the powder and pressurised isostatically using a fluid such as oil or water [69].

The parts obtained by cold compaction have the basic shape, but the properties of a green compact are unattractive. So, to increase the compact properties sintering is necessary. Sintering provides thermal energy to induce interparticle welds and improve some properties. In the case of high speed steels, vacuum sintering is often used in the densification of T1 [92,93], M2 [46,48,94], M3/2 [48], T42 [95], T15 [96], ASP60 [19], HITACHI [20]. The range of vacuum sintering temperatures of high speed steels is 1240°-1340°C, Figure 1.7. The main handicap of vacuum sintering is that vacuum can not be used in the conveyor furnaces conventionally used by the PM industry. Vacuum furnaces are batch-type furnaces. Vacuum sintering process has been the most widely used technique to process water atomised HSS powders [40,69], which require cold compaction prior sintering [40,69]. As shown in Figure 1.7 vacuum sintering of HSS needs high temperature processing normally in excess of 1240°C [19,69]. When too high temperatures are attained specimens distort as a consequence of partially melting, indicated by the presence of eutectic structures in the steels microstructures [73,83]. Commercial considerations in order to decrease sintering temperatures as either to reduce power consumption or to allow processing in continuous belt furnaces which are upper limited to 1150°C, are an industrial concern and have been addressed [32,97]. In order to respond these problems some alternatives have been made. One is Cu_3P additions to HSS powders [98,99,100], which results in the presence of a low melting point phase which promotes densification. Another approach to lower sintering temperatures is the sintering of vanadium-rich HSS's in nitrogen-rich atmospheres [27,31,32].

The HIP technique is also used on water atomised powders [21,22,101-103]. After being sintered to a closed porosity level, i.e. about 95% theoretical density, the specimens

are containerless HIPped to close remaining porosity. Improvements in the strength levels of the T1 HSS were achieved when this procedure was used. Hence, [101,102,103] strength levels of less than 2 GPa were increased up to 3.7 GPa, by controlling microstructure, particularly grain and carbide sizes during sintering, followed by HIPping. On the other hand, HIP showed to have no influence on fracture toughness of T6 and T15 type HSS, when atmosphere sintered specimens having densities in the range 92-98 % theoretical were HIPped [104].

ATMOSPHERE SINTERING

As it will be reported later, sintering of HSS's occurs at a high temperature above the alloy's solidus [48,92,105]. Because high speed steels materials are generally highly reactive at these temperatures, and because of the high surface area exposed by the powder to the atmosphere, the choice of atmosphere is critical in order to obtain the desired final product. One of the atmospheres used to sinter some high speed steels is a nitrogen based atmosphere consisting of 90%N₂-9%H₂-1%CH₄ [26-36,106]. These atmospheres are used as well in most of the industrial plants, as a protective one, because nitrogen is molecular rather than atomic, what makes it inert to steel. On the other hand, nitrogen has a density close to that of air, what prevents air from entering the sintering furnaces, thus protecting porous PM parts from harmful contact with air during the sintering process. But, depending on the composition of the steel, as temperature is increased during the sintering process, nitrogen can interact with the steel giving rise to certain hard phases as nitrides or carbonitrides [69]. As hydrogen is the most effective reducing atmosphere available [40,69], it is often added to nitrogen in small, controlled additions to produce PM parts,

being the most desirable ingredient for reduction of particle surface oxides, which thus improves bonding, then sintering. The reduction takes place when:

with M representing any common metal. The water that is formed from the reduction is a vapour that is easily removed by the gas phase. A first consequence of sintering vanadium high speed steels grades in a nitrogen-rich atmosphere, is the drop of the optimum sintering temperature (OST) as illustrated in Figure 1.8 [26,27,32].

1.4.3 - SINTERING MECHANISMS

Sintering is the thermal activated process with or without external pressure application, whereby the powder particles bond together changing physical and mechanical properties, developing toward a state of maximum density, i.e. null porosity, by occurrence of atomic transport [40,69,107]. The mass transport can be carried out by different transport mechanisms. These mechanisms depend on the type of sintering.

1.4.3.1 - SOLID STATE SINTERING

In solid state sintering, two kinds of transport mechanisms can be considered: surface transport and bulk transport. Surface transport involves the growth of the neck bond between the powder particles without changing the particle spacing, which means that no densification takes place. Surface diffusion and evaporation-condensation are the most important contributors for the surface transport sintering [69,70]. The bulk transport mechanisms involve the mass originated from the particle interior, which is deposited at the neck region, and include volume diffusion, grain boundary diffusion and plastic flow. Only bulk transport mechanisms give shrinkage, then densification [69,86,108,109]. The solid

state sintering process involves mass transport and consists of three stages: the initial stage, the intermediate stage and the final stage [69,86,108,109].

The initial stage is considered when the interparticle contact area (which can also be defined as neck size ratio- X/R) increases from zero to 0.2. In this stage the pore structure is open and thoroughly interconnected, and the pores sharp shaped. This stage is sometimes referred to only as neck growth, and it is accompanied by interparticle shrinkage of several percent, and a typical powder compact would increase from 0.5 to 0.6 in relative density [108]. As neck growth takes place due to bulk transport processes, interparticle spacing changes resulting in compact shrinkage. Otherwise, if either surface diffusion or evaporation-condensation are the dominant sintering mechanism, no shrinkage will take place [69]. During this stage of sintering, single-crystal particles in contact cannot undergo grain growth because the solid-vapour surface diverges at an acute angle from the particle-particle contact area. If migration of the grain boundary was possible away from the minimum area location, it requires an increase in area and energy [108]. Consequently, the boundary is initially limited to the neck area. As the neck growth takes place, the inhibition to boundary motion decreases, until grain growth becomes feasible. Hence, when grain growth first occurs this is considered the end of the initial stage of sintering [69,70].

The intermediate stage is characterised by densification coupled to grain growth and the density is less than about 92% of theoretical [69]. In this stage, the porosity becomes smooth but remains a continuous channel until final stage. During this stage of sintering, the cylindrical pores simply shrink, neck growth continues, but the neck shape is lost as the pores become smooth. The individual initial particles can no longer be distinguished. The sintering rate is controlled by the geometry of the grain boundary and the pores. Initially the pores are located at the three-grain edges throughout the matrix, and as sintering proceeds, the interaction between pores and grain boundaries can assume two

configurations: –the pores can be dragged by the moving grain boundaries during grain growth, or –the grain boundaries can breakaway from the pores leaving them isolated in the interior of the grains [69]. Breakaway of the grain boundaries from the pores are due to the slower moving of the last ones. When volume or surface diffusion or even evaporation-condensation across the pore occurs, pore motion under the tension of a moving grain boundary is then possible. Separation of the pores from the grain boundaries limits the final density that can be achieved by sintering, because pores located on grain boundaries disappear more rapidly than the isolated ones [69]. As the grain boundaries movement is thermally activated (as the temperature is increased, the rate of grain boundary motion increases), an accurate temperature control is needed to minimise breakaway. Another ways to minimise breakaway is to incorporate a second phase inclusion such as oxide particles into the microstructure to pin up the grain boundaries, or use a narrow initial particle size distributions [69,110].

If one can assume that the grain shape geometry is a tetrakaidecahedron, with cylindrical pores occupying the grain edges, the pore radius r , grain size G and porosity ε are interrelated as [69]:

$$\varepsilon = 4\pi(r/G)^2 \quad (1.4)$$

This relation shows that grain size will increase as either the pores coalesce (increasing r) or as porosity is eliminated (decreasing ε). So, pore elimination in this intermediate stage is attached with grain growth and a decrease in the pore size, and an attachment of the pores to the grain boundaries is necessary to maintain densification.

The final stage of sintering begins when pores spheroidize into a closed structure, densities are higher than 92% of theoretical, and grain growth tends to be evident. The pores shrink by a bulk diffusion mechanism [69,108]. It is assumed that pores are vacancy

sources and that grain boundaries are vacancy sinks [108]. In this stage of sintering, if the pores become isolated due to boundary breakdown, its shrinkage rate is dependent on vacancy diffusion to distant grain boundaries, which is a slow process [69,86]. Coarsening of the pores is also observed, occurring by mass transfer between isolated pores during grain growth [69,86]. Hence, the final density attained upon sintering is highly dependent on the pore characteristics in the final stage of sintering. Trapped gas can also have influence on the final density: if the gas is totally insoluble in the material, then the final density is lower than the theoretical ($\approx 99\%$), but if it is soluble in the matrix, the rate of densification is controlled by the rate of gas diffusion out of the pore. The changes in microstructure observed in the final stage influence some properties like wear resistance, strength, fracture toughness, magnetic behaviour and ductility [111]. The densification in this stage is slower than in the early ones, due to the rigid solid skeleton that is formed which also inhibits the final pore removal.

1.4.3.2 - SUPERSOLIDUS LIQUID PHASE SINTERING

In liquid phase sintering two methods are employed to create the liquid phase, Figure 1.9. The first approach is to use mixtures of powders in which one component has a lower melting point than the other components. The liquid formed during the sintering cycle may be transient or persistent [69]. The second approach is to use prealloyed powders, which are then heated to a temperature intermediate between the *solidus* and *liquidus*, Figure 1.10. This method is known as supersolidus liquid phase sintering (SLPS) and has been applied to a number of systems [69,112,113] including high speed steels [19,20,48,105,114]. From a commercial view point SLPS is of interest since the process

uses relatively coarse powders, median particle sizes of 50 μm [69] and at optimum sintering temperatures nominally 100% (i.e. full) density can be achieved after holding at temperature for 15-30 min. [93]

The SLPS process is illustrated in Figure 1.11. At temperatures below the solidus a small amount of solid state sintering produces inter particle bonding creating a skeletal structure. On crossing the solidus, liquid forms at interparticle necks, grain boundaries and, in powders with dendritic structures, within the inter dendritic spaces [115]. German [115] considers this latter site undesirable since the liquid forms isolated pools and does not contribute to densification. Densification requires continuous films of liquid of the type generated at interparticle necks and grain boundaries. German [115] states that powders with cellular structures are preferred. Increasing temperature increases the volume fraction of liquid giving increased penetration along grain boundaries and increasing the grain boundary area covered by liquid. The compacts densify by a process of viscous flow arising from the capillary force the interparticle liquid exerts in the compact aided by the lubricating effect of the grain boundary liquid [112,113,115]. A critical amount of liquid is needed to promote full densification [113]. However, too much liquid leads to compact distortion. Optimal volume fraction of liquid is system specific [113] and maybe as little as 2% for T1 HSS [105], in excess of 5% for M2 HSS [116] or in excess of 20% for a Fe-0.9%C alloy [117]. German [112,113,115,118,119] taking the ideas of Kingery et al [120,121] that in the presence of liquid phase sintering corresponds to a viscous flow process, has developed a mathematical model of SLPS based on mono sized, spherical powders and tetrakaidecahedron grains, which relates microstructural parameters, particle size, grain size, liquid volume fraction and liquid viscosity to the rate of densification. On the basis of this model German and co-workers [112,113] predict that the initiation of viscous flow requires liquid to cover 89% of the grain boundary area within the powder.

Since grain boundary area is proportional to grain size, i.e. it increases with decreasing grain size, the model, which assumes a constant film thickness, predicts a variation in critical volume fraction liquid with grain size, with this decreasing with increasing grain size, due to the associated reduction in grain boundary area. Once grain boundary area coverage reaches 100% compacts lose all rigidity and distort. In qualitative terms this consistent with experience since in SLPS systems close temperature control is needed to control the amount of liquid formed [105]. In the case of high speed steels such as M2, temperatures may have to be controlled to $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ about the optimum [48]. Some authors [8,10] refer to SLPS processes as liquid phase sintering.

Figure 1.12(a) shows schematically the sintering window -the temperature band over which acceptable microstructures (i.e. absence of coarse grain and carbide structures and continuous grain boundary carbide films) and properties can be obtained. Several authors [9,46,48,92,93,95,105,122] studies on T1- and M2-type HSS's, observed variations in sintering characteristics, such as optimum sintering windows and optimum sintering temperature, when standard compositions were changed, for example by varying carbon content. This can be explained by the supersolidus liquid phase sintering (SLPS) theory [118,119], where a critical amount of liquid is necessary to promote densification, therefore it is necessary to sinter somewhere above the solidus. Wright [92] has demonstrated that to promote supersolidus sintering of HSS, sintering must be carried out within the austenite (γ)+liquid (L) +carbide(s) (C) region of the phase diagram. This is illustrated in Figure 1.12(b) and (c). Therefore, the size and shape of this region influences the sintering characteristics of the alloys, i.e. the temperature gap separating the phase boundaries of the γ + Liquid+ carbides region, and not the separation between solidus and liquidus [48]. Hence, to enhance the sinterability of HSS's, i.e. lower the sintering temperatures, widen sintering windows, it is necessary to establish the compositional factors that alter the size

and shape of the γ +liquid+carbides region [114]. So, from identifying which of these factors can influence sinterability, this knowledge can be used in order to design new sinterable compositions [114].

The M-type alloys vacuum sintered by Wright et al [123] showed a sintering window of less than $<5^{\circ}\text{C}$ for M2- and 10°C M3/2-type HSS's, i.e. M3/2 possessed superior sinterability to the M2 material. Optimum sintering temperatures were judged to be 1255°C and 1250°C for the M2 and M3/2 alloys, respectively, similar trends being found by Maulik et al [46] for a M2-type HSS. In fact, regarding the M2 HSS phase diagram, the γ +L+C region is very narrow, Figure 1.4, the maximum width being about 20°C , corresponding to a sintering window less than 5°C [48]. The microstructure of the sintered M2 alloy [46,48] can also be correlated with the phase diagram. Hence, the formation of grain boundaries carbide films for the specimens sintered at 1240°C , the temperature at which rapid densification was initiated, was suggested by Wright and Ogel [48] to be due to crossing the solidus with the carbide films being a trace of the liquid. Increasing of the sintering temperature resulted in both to grain growth, coarsening of the carbides and above 1270°C eutectic carbides are observed, indicating the presence of a large volume fraction of liquid, and that the sintering is already taking place over the temperature of liquation of the carbides, or outside the γ +liquid+carbides region.

The superior sinterability of M3/2 when compared to the M2 material, was explained by Wright et al [48] using the phase transformation data for M2 type alloys of Barkalow et al [53] being due to the difference in composition, in particular the higher carbon and vanadium contents of the M3/2 alloy. In fact, a higher carbon content drops the sintering temperature by lowering the solidus line [53]. On the other hand, the addition of vanadium to a M2 base HSS [53] led to a slight lowering of the solidus and to an increase in the temperature for liquation of MC carbides, both effects resulting in a slightly broadening

of the γ +liquid+carbides region, for the M3/2 HSS, compared to M2, Figure 1.13. So, the composition difference can explain the superior sinterability of M3/2. Other elements such as W and Mo appeared not to produce any relevant effect on the gap between the solidus and the boundary denoting the liquation of the MC carbides, within the normal composition limits for these types of steels [48].

So, taking into account practical experience, Wright et al [48] considered M2 HSS as an inappropriate alloy to be processed by the vacuum sintering route, as the gap between the solidus and the line of liquation of the carbides is very narrow, unlikely to be significantly affected by compositional modifications.

Concerning T1 HSS similar correlations have been established between microstructure, sintering characteristics and the phase diagram, Figure 1.4. As can be seen, the shape of the γ +liquid+carbides region of this alloy, is quite different from that for M2. In T1 the region is wider and the gradient of the phase boundaries steeper. For standard T1 (0.8%C) HSS, the temperature interval is about 40°C, giving sintering windows of about 10°C [48], an improvement over M2. As it can be seen in the T1 phase diagram, as carbon content is increased, the temperature gap is wider and wider. This leads to an increasing in sintering window and the reduction of the solidus gives a concomitant reduction in optimum sintering temperature [42]. In fact, Wright et al [42] have shown that when a 1.4 wt% carbon containing T1 HSS was sintered in vacuum, the sintering window increased to 40°C, and the optimum sintering temperature decreased to 1250°C.

During a BRITE-EURAM project [83] computer calculated ternary, quaternary and quinary phase diagrams have been done in order to find out the effect of several alloying elements on the referred to above γ +liquid+carbides phase field. Some of these calculated diagrams had γ +liquid+carbide phase fields, which exhibited the features that could

promote good sinterability. Using these a Fe-14Mo-4Cr-1.3C-8Co alloy was identified which sintered to full density at 1170°C and possessed a sintering window of 30°C [114].

The time has also influence on the final microstructure of the sintered material. For certain systems [45,93,111] full density was attained after a few minutes at sintering temperature. On the other hand, porosity will increase with prolonged heating (over 1 hour) after reaching a minimum value, being observed as well as referred to above, grain and pore growth [111].

1.4.3.3 - EFFECTS OF ELEMENTS ON SINTERABILITY OF HSS

Sintering Curves of Figure 1.7 and corresponding microstructural developments observed in SLPS processing can be represented schematically in Figure 1.12(b). Several authors have investigated the role of alloying elements on sinterability of high speed steels powders [7,45,46,51,92,93,95,124,125]. Among them, carbon is the element whose effects have been most fully investigated in a wide range of high speed steels. Its effect is to reduce the sintering temperature by decreasing the solidus, when added within certain limits which are dependent on the steel composition, above which it can develop undesirable microstructural features such as pores and/or eutectic carbides [40,73,105]. Carbon dissolves rapidly and has high diffusivity (direct volume diffusion) [126], nevertheless, the amount of carbon to be added to promote sintering varies with the steel composition, but it is reported [40] that for a balanced alloy no more than 0.15-0.2 wt% should be added, or it may cause detrimental effects, such as nonuniform distribution of carbon, oversintering, coarse microstructure and pores [40,73]. In fact, Mascarenhas [73] observed that 0.5 wt% carbon addition to ASP60 HSS (Fe-2.3C-4Cr-7Mo-10.5Co-6.5V-6.5W) produced M₂C eutectic carbides associated to porosity, microstructure typical of oversintered samples, whilst Wright et al [105] found that additions in excess of 1.0 wt% carbon to a T1-type

composition (Fe-0.34C-4Cr-18W-0.5Mo-1V) produced large pores or resulted in eutectic formation. On the other hand, carbon effect on the sintering window is dependent on the particular grade of high speed steels being sintered, i.e. on the shape of the $\gamma+L+C$ region of the respective phase diagram [114]. Hence, if a high speed steel shows almost parallel solidus and upper limit of the $\gamma+L+C$ region lines, like in M2 HSS, Figures 1.4(b) and 1.13, though an increase in carbon content can decrease the sintering temperature by decreasing the solidus, it does not widen the sintering window [48,53]. Conversely, if the high speed steel, e.g. T1, shows steep and well separated lines defining the $\gamma+L+C$ region, and their separation increases with the increasing carbon content, then the carbon addition not only decreases the sintering temperature, but also widens the sintering window [105]. In fact Wright et al [105] working with T1 HSS reported that when carbon content was increased from 0.8 wt% to 1.4 wt% the optimum sintering temperature was lowered from 1320°C to 1240°C and the sintering window expanded from about 10° to about 40°C. On the other hand, if sufficient carbon is not available, full density is not attained, as observed by Wright et al [105] for a T1-type alloy (Fe-0.6C-4Cr-18W-0.5Mo-1V) specimens distorted before reaching full density. Some authors [7,45,124,127,128] have reported several relations to optimise carbon content in high speed steels taking into account their grade and composition. Therefore, Angers et al [7] reported that for T15 HSS carbon content should be:

$$C = 0.43 + 0.194 V + 0.026 Mo + 0.009 W - 0.02 Cr + 0.001 Co \quad (1.5)$$

where the quantities of all elements are in weight percent. Kulkarni et al [124] stated that for M2 HSS optimum carbon content should be:

$$C = 0.95 + 0.0326 (W'-6) + 0.0625 (Mo'-5) + 0.2353 (V'-2) + 7.5 \times 10^{-5} (O'-50) \quad (1.6)$$

These same authors reported [124] that for a T15 HSS carbon content should be:

$$C = 1.5 + 0.0326 (W' - 12.5) + 0.0625 (Mo' - 0.5) + 0.2353 (V' - 5) + 7.5 \times 10^{-5} (O' - 50) \quad (1.7)$$

where prime (') denotes the content of the element concerned in the specific lot of the powder. The oxygen content is in ppm and the other elements are in weight percent. G. Greetham [128] developed the following expression to determine the optimal carbon content for HSS powders. This expression takes into account the tungsten equivalent (CWE) for the calculated carbon content (CCC), all in weight percentage, as follows:

$$CWE = \%W + 2 \times \%Mo + 6 \times \%V \quad (1.8)$$

$$CCC = (CWE/20) - 0.4 \quad (1.9)$$

Wright [92] found out that a minimum molybdenum content of 0.5 wt% is necessary to sinter T1 type HSS containing 0.8 wt% C. Below this value no satisfactory density or microstructure were attained. Though the reasons why molybdenum promotes sintering in T1 were not clear, it was suggested that molybdenum can segregate to particle surfaces and grain boundaries producing localised, non-equilibrium melting [93]. Increasing molybdenum content was believed to shift the solidus to the left, resulting in lower sintering temperatures and a widening of the $\gamma + L + C$ phase field. In fact, in the BRITE-EURAM project [83] it was found that for the C-Fe-Mo and C-Cr-Fe-Mo systems when Mo was increased from 6 up to 12 wt%, the $\gamma + \text{liquid} + \text{carbide}$ (M_6C) region was expanded, resulting in lower sintering temperatures and wide sintering windows for the higher molybdenum contents.

Ternary and quaternary tungsten based systems studies [83] revealed that though they possessed extensive $\gamma + \text{carbide} + \text{liquid}$ phase regions, calculated solidus

temperatures were somewhat higher than in the molybdenum based systems. This would suggest that although no systematic studies have been performed, sintering temperature would be higher than for molybdenum based system.

Urrutibeaskoa et al [32] reported that in the nitrogen-rich atmosphere sintering of T15 (1.64% C, 4.7% V), T42 (1.43% C, 2.94% V) and a M2-type (1.33% C, 3.32% V) HSS, the optimum sintering temperature tended to be lower, the higher the level of vanadium in the steel. Observed optimum sintering temperatures were 1260°C and 1230°C when M2-type HSS was sintered in vacuum and $90\text{N}_2+9\text{H}_2+1\text{CH}_4$ atmosphere, respectively, whilst the observed temperatures in the same sintering conditions were 1270° and 1225°C for T15, and 1235° and 1215°C for T42 HSS, respectively.

Though several authors have been working on nitrogen based atmosphere sintering of high speed steels [26-36,106], only a description of the sintering mechanisms have been reported. The relevant approach made so far is by Urrutibeaskoa et al [32] working on vanadium-rich HSS, reported that some carbon in MC carbides is replaced by nitrogen, giving MX carbonitrides. The fact that the observed carbonitrides are smaller than the MC carbides is reported by these authors, that it could be due to a process of dissolution of MC carbides and reprecipitation of MX carbonitrides occurring during the nitrogen sintering cycle, though no information is given about temperatures at which this process starts. The rejected carbon as a result of the process, dissolves into the matrix – lowering the solidus – and has the opportunity to form more M_6C , or to dissolve into the matrix. The presence of these very stable fine carbonitrides inhibits grain growth, as observed in vacuum sintering. Albornoz [36] also reported a similar trend, i.e., that the carbonitrides formation occurs by the incorporation of nitrogen into the austenite and further precipitation. The same author [36], working on a high vanadium T42 type HSS (8%V), observed MX clusters on grain boundaries, explaining that this clustering effect can be attributed to local chemical

heterogeneity, such as a carbon deficiency, what should allow a higher nitrogen diffusion into that zone and further carbonitride precipitation.

Cobalt additions up to 8 wt % have no significant effect on sintering temperature as found out by Maulik et al [46] for M2 HSS. On the other hand, its effect seems to be very distinct depending to the alloy type in which it is added [83]. Hence, cobalt addition to M42 type HSS [83,114] would appear to be determinant in the sinterability of this alloy, since cobalt containing materials sintered to full density at lower temperatures than cobalt free M42 variants, Figure 1.14. Tests performed on standard T15 and a cobalt free variant, showed that at the normal carbon content of 1.5 wt%, both powders showed comparable sintering characteristics [129].

Silicon aids sintering by suppressing the melting point of the alloys [40,51]. The eutectic reaction in a M2 HSS starts at a slightly higher temperature, the fraction of the M_2C -eutectic decreases, while the fraction of M_6C eutectic carbides increases with increasing silicon content.

1.4.4 - HEAT TREATMENTS

Heat treatments of steels normally comprises annealing, quenching and tempering. In the case of HSS's heat treatments are rather complex than the ones for other types of steels. This is due to the extended range of temperatures and the need for multiple tempering [1,12,13,130].

1.4.4.1 - ANNEALING

The general purposes of an annealing treatment are both to reduce the steel's hardness and/or stresses induced by prior machining [1]. As HSS's are air hardening alloys, either produced by cast and wrought route or PM processes and normally left in the hardened condition, annealing becomes essential to enable further processing of the steels, as it produces a structure that facilitates the progress of subsequent manufacturing operations [1,13]. As parts are normally machined to final dimensions prior to hardening and tempering, annealing becomes of major importance in order to improve machinability [44]. The annealed structure is composed of carbides dispersed into a ferritic matrix, the carbides being M_6C , MC and $M_{23}C_6$ [1,19,44], the total carbide fraction being normally about 25 to 30% [1]. Annealing is as well of main importance in the reduction of surface oxides of water atomised HSS's powders [19,83].

Annealing is composed of heating to a temperature below or above A_{ci} (temperature of initiation of transformation into austenite on heating) maintenance at that temperature and slow cooling, normally furnace cooling. Basically there are two different types of annealing: subcritical annealing and transformation annealing [1,12,13]. Subcritical annealing is carried out by heating to a temperature below A_{ci} , normally around 750°-800°C for about 15 hours, followed by furnace cooling to room temperature [1]. Stress relief

annealing is carried out prior to hardening operations what helps in minimising distortion on hardening. This type of annealing is normally carried out at 650°-700°C followed by air cooling [1,44], and is done because of the stresses induced in to the cold-worked surfaces due to machining or plastic deformation.

Transformation annealing is carried out by first heating above the A_{ci} temperature, holding at this temperature to ensure that the material is fully austenitised, and furnace cooling at an adequate rate to ensure transformation of austenite in the pearlitic range [1,44]. Transformation temperature ranges for some HSS's are shown in Table 1.1.

The annealing temperature in HSS's is of major importance, grain size resulting from the hardening being dependent on the temperature of the preceding annealing process [13]. Therefore, a low annealing temperature gives rise to a fine-grained structure and consequently a greater hardness, as shown in Figure 1.15 for M2 HSS.

1.4.4.2 - HARDENING

Hardening consists of austenitise the steel at high temperature, usually 30° to 40°C below the solidus, promoting the dissolution of carbides followed by quenching [1,12,13]. Heating up to the austenitizing temperature must be carefully done in order to prevent thermal shock which causes development of internal stresses and parts may crack or warp, since sections having different dimensions heat up at different speeds [1,12,13]. This effect may be diminished by preheating the parts to a temperature normally lying past below A_{ci} of the steel, around 800° to 850°C [1,13] to allow temperature homogenisation. When salt baths are used to austenitise the parts, a preheat to about 100°C is always advisable in order to remove any moisture adhering to the steel [13].

Austenitization media for high speed steels are normally molten salt baths, which offer good protection against variations in the superficial carbon content [13]. Though

manufacturers of heat treatment salts do not specify the composition of the salts, giving instead detailed information on their properties and uses, some typical compositions and working temperatures for neutral salt baths are as follows [13]:

45% NaCl + 55% KCl	675°-900°C
20% NaCl + 80% BaCl ₂	675°-1060°C
100% BaCl ₂	1025°-1325°C

Austenitizing times are normally in the range 2-5 minutes [1,19] but are dependent of parts sections thickness, the thicker the section the longer the immersion time [13]. An increasing use of vacuum heat treatments are been using nowadays, due to health and safety problems associated with the use of molten salts [49].

Carbides have very unlike behaviour during austenitization depending on their composition [1,12,13], as shown in Figure 1.2. Hence, the less stable is the chromium carbide $M_{23}C_6$ which starts to dissolve in the range 850°-900°C and completely disappears around 1100°C, being the primary source of carbon in solution in the austenite [1,12]. The MC vanadium-rich carbide dissolves into the austenite only to limited extent, and normally at higher temperatures in excess of 1200°C [13], however when narrow sized ($\approx 1-2 \mu\text{m}$) their solubility can be increased [52]. This last carbide due to its stability has a very efficient role in avoiding grain growth grain boundaries being efficiently pinned [1]. The tungsten-molybdenum rich M_6C carbide which starts to dissolve around 1050°C still remains partially undissolved at the austenitizing temperature [1,131].

Quenching follows the austenitization of steels and is carried out at a rate sufficient to ensure transformation to martensite, the quenching medium being normally brine, oil or salt bath [1,12]. The high speed steels' structure after quenching is composed of martensite, M_6C and MC carbides occupying about 15-20% of the total volume, and about 15 to 30% of retained austenite [12]. Concerning to vacuum austenitization inert gas quenching is

normally used, ensuring a sufficiently fast rate of cool with minimum distortion, high purity gases being required with impurity limits on oxygen to 3 p.p.m. by volume maximum, the dewpoint not higher than -73°C (equivalent to 1 p.p.m. by volume of water vapour) [12]. Nitrogen is the most common gas used, helium, argon and forming gas (97.5% N_2 plus 2.5% H_2) can also be used [12].

The solubility of alloying elements in the austenite decreases concomitantly with decreasing temperature during quenching, resulting in the precipitation of some carbides [4]. At room temperature the austenite-martensite transformation is far from being complete, as M_f (martensite finishing transformation) is lower than room temperature [12], M_f being as low as higher is the carbon content of the austenite, i.e. carbon stabilises austenite so at room temperature retained austenite can be observed [1,12,44]. The as-quenched microstructure consists of a matrix of highly alloyed tetragonal martensite, 15 to 30% of retained austenite and 15-20 volume % of undissolved M_6C and MC carbides [1,12,13,44]. This structure is highly stressed and susceptible of cracking, tempering must be performed immediately after quenching [12].

1.4.4.3 - TEMPERING

Consequently, as the steel is left in an unusable condition after quenching, the structure being highly stressed and brittle, in order to transform retained austenite and reinforce the secondary hardening effect a final treatment is then required. Normally this treatment is tempering which due to the high alloy content of high speed steels produces the precipitation of a very fine dispersion of alloy carbides increasing the overall hardness, this effect known as secondary hardening [1,12,13]. The tempering cycle usually consists of heating to a temperature in the range 400°C - 600°C and holding for a period usually around 1-2 hours and cooling to room temperature [12,49,132,133]. It is normal practise to carry

out two or three tempers. Tempering progressively transforms retained austenite on cooling from the tempering temperature into martensite, so the first temper transforms the retained austenite and some carbides are precipitated as well [12]. The second temper tempers the martensite formed in the first cycle and more carbides are precipitated, and a third temper is sometimes required to transform any martensite formed on cooling after the second temper. To be remarked is that prolonged tempering in a single treatment is therefore not nearly so effective as multitempering, as martensite only forms during the cooling cycle [12]. Retained austenite elimination and secondary hardening can also be attained through a sub-zero stabilisation treatment at temperatures of around -75°C in a refrigerator or in liquid nitrogen at -196°C . This treatment allows the steel to achieve the M_f temperature the remaining austenite being then transformed [12].

Typical tempering curves for some high speed steels are shown in Figure 1.16. In this figure it can be remarked three different ranges on these curves:

✦ A first one up to about 450°C where a slight decrease of hardness is observed [134,135]. Martensite loses its tetragonal form and decomposes to b.c.c. and ϵ -carbide the later precipitating as a transition phase $\text{Fe}_{2.4}\text{C}$ which disappears and is replaced by cementite as temperature exceeds 300°C [12].

✦ A second range at about 450° - 600°C where second hardening is then observed. This is due to a very fine dispersion of carbides which precipitate in the matrix and the hardness increases, the second hardening peak being usually found in the range 500° - 600°C [1,12,13,44,134,135]. Taking into account the work reported by several authors, the responsible carbides for secondary hardening are dependent on the type of steel, i.e. on the steel's composition. M_2C carbides were identified by Kuo [134] in 6W-5Mo-4Cr-2V (M2), 1W-9Mo-4Cr-2V (M7) and 18W-4Cr-1V (T1) steels as being the secondary hardening carbides, whilst for 18W-4Cr-1V (T1) steel Honeycombe [135] found the secondary

carbide to be $M_{23}C_6$. A MC carbide was reported by Wright in both wrought and sintered T42-type HSS [4,136]. For ASP60 high speed steel the secondary carbides were found to be MC, M_3C or possibly M_2C [137]. However, according to Stiller [138] and Rong [72] secondary hardening in ASP60, ASP23 and M2 HSS's is due to the precipitation of M_2C and MC carbides. The precipitation of these carbides from the austenite raises the M_s temperature of the retained austenite (as its carbon content is lowered) and this decomposes on cooling to room temperature [12].

✦ A last stage is then observed at temperatures in excess of $\approx 600^\circ\text{C}$, the hardness dropping off rapidly. This is due to re-solution of the secondary carbides and precipitation of more complex carbides such as $M_{23}C_6$ and/or M_6C [25], these carbides being more inclined to coarsening than MC or M_2C . Also at these temperatures the martensite structure is replaced by equiaxial ferrite [136].

Therefore, after a single temper within the temperature range ($500^\circ\text{-}600^\circ\text{C}$) the structure consists of tempered martensite, untempered martensite, some retained austenite and M_6C and MC carbides. Hence, a considerable amount of retained austenite and untempered martensite are then present, the steel being in an unstable condition. Subsequent tempers convert some additional austenite and temper the previous untempered martensite [1,12,13,44,133].

1.4.5 - MICROSTRUCTURES

The microstructures of the sintered high speed steels are dependent on the alloy composition, sintering atmosphere and cooling rate. Generally, the microstructure of the PM HSS is not very divergent from the conventional wrought high speed steels, the main differences being the carbide size and its dispersion in the matrix (no banding), depending on the processing routes.

M_6C , a face-centred cubic phase, is the designated high speed steel major carbide where M represents Fe, W or Mo with some traces of other elements [1]. In the case of molybdenum high speed steels, M_6C corresponds to the complex carbide Fe_4Mo_2C or Fe_3Mo_3C , and Fe_4W_2C or Fe_3W_3C in tungsten high speed steels [122]. The M_6C carbide is often referred to simply as high speed steels carbide or eta-carbide. Another carbide present in some high speed steels is M_2C , where M designates Mo or W. Vanadium usually occurs in the MC type carbide, though because of lack of stoichiometry it is more quoted as V_4C_3 . Chromium generally occurs as $Cr_{23}C_6$ or Cr_7C_3 . These last carbides are not considered as primary carbides, as they dissolve at high temperatures and precipitate during heat treatment [1,4,139]. The referred to above carbides can occur either as isolated particles or in the eutectic form. This later morphology is not a desirable microstructure feature of cast steels, and it is usually removed during the hot-working process [1]. Though it is a common feature of the cast material, it also can occur in PM parts, when specimens are oversintered [19,46,48,73,94,95,105]. Its composition is dependent on both alloy composition and cooling rate. In tungsten steels and less frequently in molybdenum steels (those where vanadium content is low), the eutectic takes the form of herringbone type structure. In the case of the molybdenum and tungsten-molybdenum steels, the eutectic occurs in a feather or rod form [1]. The feathery eutectic may contain M_2C carbide if a sufficiently rapid cooling of the part is carried. It is known [1] that M_2C carbide decomposes to M_6C one when heated to temperatures of $1200^\circ C$. Hence, feathery type carbides are easily broken up in subsequent working or even in heat treatment, than the herringbone type eutectics. Vanadium, even when occurring as eutectic carbide, forms individual particles [1].

Steven et al [122] investigating primary carbides in the austenite and ferrite of molybdenum and tungsten-molybdenum high speed steels, identified M_2C type carbide as part of the structure of essentially nitrogen-free steels, being its proportion to other primary

phases dependent upon carbon content: very low nitrogen and high carbon favoured its presence.

Fredriksson et al [51] reported that for a M2 HSS a low carbon content as well as a low vanadium content favoured the precipitation of M_6C -eutectic carbides, and an increase in the vanadium content as well as a high carbon content favoured a precipitation of MC and M_2C carbides. Above 1.9 wt% V, the amount of MC was found to be almost proportional to the V content. On the other hand, Haberling et al [125] stated that for a 5 Mo, 2V, 6W HSS where generally only M_6C and M_2C type primary carbides were found, with a raised carbon content further carbides could be found. Hence, for a steel carbon content of more than 1.2 wt%, a columnar M_2C carbide was detected. The quantitative proportions of the steel carbides were found to change with composition. So, MC only formed in marked quantities above 0.5 wt% C. The carbide M_6C decreases quantitatively with rising carbon content and replaced by the M_2C carbide, which reaches a maximum at about 1.7 wt% C. If carbon content was greater than 2 wt% the carbide M_2C was replaced by the $M_{23}C_6$ and M_3C carbides.

For a high-vanadium high-carbon steel (1-5.5 wt% V, 0.7-1.6 wt% C) Sato et al [127] reported that found carbides were MC, M_6C and $M_{23}C_6$, and its individual amount varies depending on the steel composition. They also found that the main factor affecting the microstructure was the carbon-vanadium ratio. So, if this ratio is too low, the steel contains no $M_{23}C_6$, contrarily, if the ratio is too high, the steel contains excessive amounts of $M_{23}C_6$.

Microstructure was found to be affected by milling, used in the production of finer powders of the M2 HSS, by Shephard et al [140]. In fact, powders milled dry under argon produced a sintered structure consisting of a continuous network of carbides at the grain

boundaries, that weakens the material. Milling in liquid produced an even distribution of fine carbides.

When nitrogen is incorporated in the steels either via atmosphere sintering or in the melt prior to atomisation, the microstructure of the sintered high speed steels shows rather different features. In fact, Hirano et al [141] reported that when nitrogen was introduced into a 0.6-1.4 %C, 4 % Cr, 6 % Mo, 6 % W, and 3.5 % V HSS (via gas nitriding), the steel showed a finer and more homogeneous carbide and carbonitride structure composed by MC, MX and M_6C type carbides, than nitrogen free steels. It was also found by these authors that the amount of vanadium-rich MC (MX) type carbide (carbonitride) increased as the N/C ratio increased; M_6C carbide volume fraction increased up to 0.6% N but subsequently, decreases. As reported above [122], nitrogen seems not to favour the precipitation of M_2C carbides in M-type HSS. In the same steels mixed primary phases were found consisting of globular M_6C , MX and rod-shaped M_2C . The last two carbides delineated the grain boundaries of the modified M7 HSS, and in the high nitrogen steels (0.08-0.1 %N), MX grain boundary precipitate appeared to inhibit thermally activated grain growth. MX carbonitrides vanadium content is much higher than the correspondent MC, being this last about 2/3 of the MX. Sudo et al [63] reported that for a Mo-type HSS, the morphology of MC-type primary carbide precipitated during solidification changed from the globular to the dendritic type with decreasing nitrogen contents.

Extensive works have been done in C.E.I.T. (Spain) in nitrogen-rich atmosphere sintering [26-37]. The reported microstructures when T1, T15 or T42 [29,32] were sintered, consisted in fine MX carbonitrides ($\approx 1\mu\text{m}$) in place of coarse MC carbides ($\approx 10\mu\text{m}$) in vacuum, and M_6C primary carbides. A refining of the austenitic grain size takes place. Small amounts of eutectic carbides (M_6C , and Type I-W, Mo, Cr-rich) were observed in the

specimens sintered in the optimum sintering temperature, though these carbides were dissolved by further heat treatments. MC and needle type-W, Mo-rich eutectic carbides were observed only in vacuum sintered samples.

Although [29] the composition of M_6C carbides are very similar when sintered either in vacuum or atmosphere, there is however a significant difference concerning to vanadium concentration, being lower in the case of atmosphere sintered specimens. This is a consequence of the high vanadium concentration, ≈ 70 wt%, found in the MX carbonitrides, compared to about 40 wt% in MC carbides found in vacuum sintered alloys [26,27,32,36].

1.5 - MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HIGH SPEED STEELS

1.5.1-HARDNESS

Hardness is the property that is most used either in research or in the industry, for testing and checking, as it is a fair indication of the material condition. This is due to its simplicity of execution and minimum specimen preparation required. In high speed steels, the hardness depends on both steel composition and heat treatment [1,142]. High speed steels are usually tempered to around peak hardness, i.e. about 800-900 HV [131]. When the same tempering temperature is used, hardness increases with the austenitizing temperature, due to the higher amount of carbides dissolved, leading to more carbon and alloy elements dissolved into the matrix, producing a more pronounced precipitation of secondary hardening carbides. This is the reason why T-grade steels, that have a higher content in alloy elements, yield higher hardness than M-grades. Reported T grade steels maximum hardness is normally in excess of 1000 HV [136,143], whilst M grades is

generally around 900 HV [9,143]. The hardness of several microstructure components can be evaluated by microhardness where low loads are used for testing (typical microhardness values shown in Figure 1.17), but as sometimes this tests are difficult to perform, macrohardness is often used [1].

1.5.2 - BEND STRENGTH

Regarding to toughness, the bend test is widely accepted as to be the most reliable and to give maximum information. Due to the relatively hardness and high carbide content of high speed steels, machining of tensile specimens in the hardened condition is rather difficult, while hardening of a tensile specimen might cause its cracking or distortion. On the other hand, as it is unusual to test brittle specimens in simple tension, strength of high speed steels is commonly evaluated by bending tests. Bending tests can be under 3- or 4-point loading [144,145,146]. The bending moment is different in the two test geometries, as shown in Figure 1.18. So, for the 4- point mode there is a central span between the two inner supports, in which the calculated stresses are constant, unlike to the peak concentration at the central support of the 3-point method [1,144,145]. The transverse rupture strength (TRS) for a rectangular cross section specimen is evaluated by an expression, ASTM Standard B 528-76 / ISO 3325 [144], where linear elastic deformation is assumed:

$$\text{TRS} = 3/2 \frac{F.l}{b.h^2} \quad (1.10)$$

where F is the maximum load applied to the specimen, l is the span of the testing geometry, b and h are the cross section dimensions of the specimen

It is deduced from the expression that gives the stress in a bending specimen [147]:

$$\sigma = \frac{M \cdot y}{J_x} \quad (1.11)$$

where M is the bending momentum, y is the specimen height and J_x is the inertia momentum of the main central axis which is perpendicular to the bending momentum plan. The maximum stress, in the bending case, is attained at the points located in the specimen border, i.e. the farrest ones from the neutral line [147]:

$$\sigma_{\max} = \frac{M \cdot y_{\max}}{J_x} \quad (1.12)$$

as $\frac{J_x}{y_{\max}} = W_x$ (cm^3) is called the resistance momentum, it comes [147]:

$$\sigma_{\max} = \frac{M_{\text{bend}}}{W_x} \quad (1.13)$$

being this the basic expression for the bending resistance calculation of a bar. If the bar has a rectangular cross section ($b \times h$), then: $J_x = \frac{bh^3}{12}$, $y_{\max} = \frac{h}{2}$ and $W_x = \frac{bh^2}{6}$.

Wronski et al [97] have shown using Weibull statistics how to convert results obtained with different test rigs to the ANSE/ASTM B528-76 American standard. The obtained bend strength values, σ_R , are then converted into σ_R^S , using the following equations:

$$\sigma_R^S = \sigma_R \left[\frac{ltw}{2556} \right]^{1/m} \quad \text{for three-point bending} \quad (1.14)$$

$$\sigma_R^S = \sigma_R \left\{ \frac{tw[(m+l)L+l]}{2556} \right\}^{1/m} \quad \text{for four-point bending} \quad (1.15)$$

where t and w are the specimen thickness and width, m being the Weibull modulus, L the inner span in four-point bending tests, and l the half span in three-point bending tests or half

the difference between inner and outer spans in four-point bending tests, the measurements being taken in mm.

Typical ambient temperature strength of vacuum sintered high speed steels normally lies below 2 GPa [9,19], which is comparable to those of wrought materials tested in the direction transverse to hot working. The failure initiating sites in PM materials are generally isolated porosity and localised poorly bonded powders or grains, in contrast to carbide clusters or large individual carbides in the wrought materials [9,23,148]. In order to produce finer grains and carbides, PM powders are normally undersintered and HIPped or forged to close porosity. This procedure was found to increase the strength of the T15 HSS up to 2.6 GPa, when compared with the same steel with no HIP [23], up to 3.7 GPa in T1 grade HSS [9], and up to 4 GPa in the ASP series [19]. The determined 4-point bending test values are normally lower than the 3-point ones, because in the first ones more material is submitted to the maximum bending moment, which increases the probability of finding a defect that may be responsible for the material failure.

1.5.3 - TOUGHNESS

Fracture toughness is generally defined as a measure of the material resistance to crack propagation [149]. Several methods have been used to evaluate high speed steels toughness, based on torsion or impact tests. Nowadays, the plain strain fracture toughness, K_{IC} , test, derived from linear elastic fracture mechanics, is the most widely used [25]. This test (BS 5447 standard) needs a pre-cracking of the specimen, which is then tensile or bend tested to failure. These tests have showed its dependency on the hardness: a general approximately linear decrease of K_{IC} with hardness has been remarked, being independent of the steel composition, amount, size and morphology of the primary carbides, manufacturing route (wrought or PM), and dependent on the matrix properties [25,32,37].

1.5.4 - EFFECTS OF NITROGEN IN STEELS ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The solubility of nitrogen in iron at different temperatures is shown in Figure 1.19. As it can be seen, the nitrogen solubility increases with temperature in the ferritic state and in the melt, which is the normal behaviour for a gas, but decreases in the austenitic structure. This can be explained as there are different packing modes for nitrogen in the γ -lattice and there exists a temperature dependant equilibrium between a higher density packing mode at low temperatures and a lower density packing mode at higher temperatures [123].

$$D_{\alpha} = 6.6 \times 10^{-3} \exp\left(-\frac{18600}{RT}\right) \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (1.16)$$

From the expression 1.16, which gives the diffusion coefficient of nitrogen in α -iron, and for temperatures below 400°C, the rate of diffusion of nitrogen is somewhat higher than that of carbon [13]. In the γ -iron, the nitrogen diffusion coefficient is given as $6.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

A set of equations which gives N solubility as function of temperature between 910° and 1060°C for different C contents, was reported by a several number of researchers [150]:

$$\text{For 1.2 wt \% C:} \quad \log (\text{wt\% N}) / \sqrt{\rho_{N_2}} = (817 \pm 110) / T - 2.352 \pm 0.09 \quad (1.17)$$

$$\text{For 1.0 wt \% C:} \quad \log (\text{wt\% N}) / \sqrt{\rho_{N_2}} = (769 \pm 60) / T - 2.272 \pm 0.05 \quad (1.18)$$

where T is in K.

On the other hand, the solubility of N in f.c.c. γ Fe at 1 atm N_2 pressure, between 911°C (1184 K) and 1392°C (1665 K), is given by [150]:

$$\log (\text{wt\% N}) = -2.14 + 723 / T \quad (1.19)$$

where T is in K. Concerning to b.c.c. α Fe at 1 atm N_2 pressure, the N solubility in this phase is, between 450°C (723 K) and 911°C (1184 K), given by [150]:

$$\log (\text{wt\% N}) = -0.97 - 1640/T \quad (1.20)$$

Solubility of N in Liquid Fe-C Alloys

The solubility of nitrogen in Fe-C melts has been thoroughly studied by a large number of researchers [150]. In the studies made so far, it was found that carbon increases the activity of nitrogen in the liquid alloys and reduces the amount of nitrogen that dissolves for a given N₂ pressure.

Nitrogen content as a function of carbon and temperature was reported [151] as follows:

$$\log (\text{wt\% N}) = -[285/T + 1.21 + (\text{wt\% C})/4.575\{1646/T - 0.409\} + (\text{wt\% C})^2/4.575\{504/T - 0.233\}] \quad (1.21)$$

where T is in K.

The intentional introduction of nitrogen in steel can be carried out by different methods: surface [13,123,152-157] and bulk nitriding methods, being this last divided into liquid state [158-169] and solid state [123,155,158,170,171] nitriding. The description of all these methods would not be done in the present work. The opportunity for nitrogen to be absorbed by the steel is dependent on the higher or lower contact of the molten or solid steel with the atmosphere [13]. In Table 1.3, typical values of nitrogen in steels, produced by different processes, are presented, but some authors [172] reported methods to increase nitrogen content beyond the nitrogen solubility limit at atmospheric pressures.

Balliger et al [173] working on low-alloy steels, demonstrated that vanadium carbide particles coarsen about fifty times more rapidly than vanadium carbonitride particles, which coarsen at about the same rate as vanadium nitride particles, i.e., listing in ascending order the relative coarsening rates are:

$$VN \approx V(CN) \ll VC$$

So, steel containing nitrogen-rich phases, be they either VN or V(CN), should have enhanced properties, especially those dependent on grain size, like strength, because the fine hard phases anchor the boundaries, impeding the grain growth [173].

1.5.4.1- INFLUENCE OF NITROGEN ON PROPERTIES OF ALLOY STEELS

For many years [123] nitrogen in steel was rather disliked by the researchers and industrialists. This was due to the fact that some steels showed embrittlement, specially at low temperatures, due to the steel making processes that introduced large quantities of nitrogen into the melt. Nitrogen has both beneficial and harmful effects on the properties of steels [1,44,64,174]. In regard to austenitic steels, nitrogen effects are widely reported [155,156,158,169,175-179], being these steels the ones on which most work have been developed on many properties such as increased strength and toughness, improved corrosion resistance and austenite stabilisation. Another example of a beneficial effect are the properties obtained upon nitriding: nitrogen combines with the iron and certain alloying elements to form hard and wear resistant nitrides. The surface hardness of nitrided steels is attributable rather to the state of fine dispersion of the nitride particles than to the inherent hardness of the nitrides themselves [13]. One of the harmful effects of nitrogen is the so-called strain-ageing effect, caused by an accumulation of nitrogen atoms at the dislocations. During the course of one deformation the dislocations move away from the nitrogen atoms, but on subjecting the steel to ageing these atoms find their way again to the lattice defects and when they are in their new positions they contribute to impeding the dislocations movements on renewed deformation [13]. Strain-ageing makes the steel brittle at room temperature. Nitrogen is believed to contribute to catastrophic failures occurring in steel made ships and bridges. The simplest way to reduce the dangerous influence of

nitrogen is to kill the steel with aluminium, which combines with nitrogen to form nitrides, and at the same time the steel becomes less susceptible to grain growth [13].

A nitrogen solubility decreasing with increasing carbon content in austenitic steels was found by some authors [180-183].

1.5.4.2 - INFLUENCE OF NITROGEN ON PROPERTIES OF HSS

Adding nitrogen to High Speed Steels was found to improve cutting performances. In fact, Hirano et al [141] reported that these steels have many excellent properties, exceeding the conventional high speed steels and nitrogen-free steels. They found improved toughness in nitrogen-containing high speed steels, due to very fine carbonitride structure, that is, substituting a part of the carbon by nitrogen. Hardness attains a maximum for 0.2% N and subsequently it decreases with increasing nitrogen. Martinez et al [37] nitrogen sintering T15 and T42 HSS, found out that peak hardness are reached for these steels at higher temperatures (about 60°C above) than previously reported vacuum sintered materials with similar compositions. The reason for the need of higher tempering temperatures to reach peak hardness in these steels is attributed [37] to the high amount of nitrogen picked-up during the sintering process producing higher levels of retained austenite necessitating higher temperatures to decompose it. Similar effects are reported by Urrutibeaskoa et al [32]. Nitrogen-containing high speed steels were found, by Hirano et al [141], to be excellent base material of coated tools: coating nitrogen-containing PM high speed steels, using the PVD (physical vapour deposition), has prolonged tool life, with good abrasive wear and heat resistance provided by TiN coating, and good toughness and adhesive wear resistance provided by adding nitrogen. A 0.6C-0.6N-4Cr-3.5W-3Mo HSS composition (KHA 3VN) was subdivided into the following three groups in order to get as close as possible the desired properties [141]: a) to improve toughness, tungsten

equivalency ($W + 2Mo$) was decreased; b) to improve wear resistance, vanadium content was increased at 18% W; c) to improve wear resistance with low decrease of toughness, vanadium content was increased and W equivalency was decreased. So, nitrogen-containing PM high speed steels may reduce the cutting and forming costs when compared with conventional materials.

Regarding to fracture toughness, gas sintered high speed steels (T15, T42 and M2-type) have similar levels to those achieved by vacuum sintering at the same level of hardness, these values tending to be higher than those reported for wrought steels [32].

1.6 - AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The most commonly sintering route of HSS is vacuum sintering. Nevertheless, there exist several problems with this process, one being the high sintering temperatures that are necessary to promote the densification of the powders by supersolidus liquid phase sintering, which lie in the range 1240-1330°C [42], impeding that continuous belt furnaces could be used (maximum sintering temperature in these furnaces being 1150°C). Another problem which arises from the chemical composition of the standard HSS [83] is that the sintering window is very narrow being normally $< 10^{\circ}\text{C}$. This cause that, as industrial sintering furnaces have temperature control no better than $\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ and gradient, different parts within a batch can have different characteristics upon sintering at the same nominal sintering temperature [184].

Developments aiming to avoid these high sintering temperatures and widening the sintering window were the addition of Cu-P to the HSS, the densification process being carried out by liquid phase sintering (LPS) [184,185]. Here, the densification is attained at temperatures in the range 1120-1150°C, but as this process origins Cu-Cu₃P eutectics, these microstructural features weaken the mechanical properties of the steels [98,99,100].

A different approach made to lower the sintering temperature is sintering of vanadium-rich steels in nitrogen-rich atmospheres [32-36]. In this case the lowering of the sintering temperature is carried out by the decreasing of the solidus temperature due to the release of carbon into the matrix as a consequence of the replacement of carbon by nitrogen in the vanadium-rich MC carbides, being then converted into MX carbonitrides [32]. The resulting microstructure in this case is much finer when compared with the ones of the vacuum sintered materials. Instead of the coarse MC and M₆C carbides (maximum size $\approx 10\ \mu\text{m}$) the nitrogen sintered materials show very fine MX carbonitrides (1-3 μm) and M₆C carbides. The finer MX avoid the austenitic grain growth on both sintering and heat

treatments. Hence, sintering high vanadium HSS in nitrogen-rich atmospheres has major advantages on both sintering temperatures and mechanical properties.

The sintering of high speed steels in nitrogen-rich atmospheres have been studied by other authors [32-36] in the last years. Even so, no comprehensive models have been reported trying to explain the whole sintering mechanisms involved in this sintering process. The present research tries to bring some more details to the field through a study of the effects of V:N:C ratio on sintering characteristics and microstructural evolution.

Table 1.1 - Nominal Composition (wt%) and Transformation Temperatures (°C) of Several High Speed Steels

Specification	C	W	Mo	Cr	V	Co	A _{ci}	A _{cf}
T1	0.75	18	-	4	1	-	825	865
T15	1.5	12.5	-	4.5	5	5	-	-
T42	1.3	9	3	4	3	9	805	845
M2	0.85	6	5	4	2	-	810	850
M3/2	1.2	6	5	4	3	-	-	-
ASP60	2.3	6.5	7	4	6.5	10.5	-	-
HITACHI	2	12	10	4	4.5	12	-	-

Table 1.2(a) -Composition of Primary Carbides Present in Some HSS (wt%)

Carbide	HSS	C	W	Mo	V	Cr	Fe	Reference
M ₆ C	M2	2	35	20	3	5	35	63
	T15	-	44.4	4.2	6.6	5.4	35.2	218
	T42	-	34.7	13.6	3.8	5.7	35.4	218
MC	M50	-	-	37	41	6	2	39
	M2	15	20	12	45	4	4	63
	T15	-	26.8	2.7	52.3	12.1	4.8	218
	T42	-	30.6	1.9	54.2	9.7	3.5	218
M ₂ C	M50	-	-	62	14	11	6	39
	M2	6	40	26	12	8	8	63

(-) Not reported on original paper

Table 1.2(b) -Composition of Primary Carbides Present in Some HSS (at%)

Carbide	HSS	C	W	Mo	V	Cr	Fe	Reference
M ₆ C	T1	-	39.4	1.5	4.4	5.6	49.1	5
	M2	-	18.5	20.6	4.8	5.4	50.7	5
	M3/2	-	16.5	21.6	6.9	4.7	50.3	48
MC	M2	-	7.3	14.8	53.7	6	18.2	48
	M3/2	-	9	16.3	66.3	4.4	4	48
M ₂ C	M2	-	22	28.4	24.4	13.5	11.7	14

Table 1.3 - Typical Nitrogen Content of Steel, Produced by Different Processes [13]

Steelmaking Process	% N
Bessemer	0.014
Thomas	0.012
Electric Arc	0.006
Basic Open Hearth	0.005
Acid Open Hearth	0.004
LD	0.004
Kaldo	0.003

Figure 1.1 – Location of the High Speed Steels in Ternary Atomic Plot (schematic) [1]

Figure 1.2 - Austenitizing Temperatures Versus Volume Percentage Carbides in Some High Speed Steels [12]

Figure 1.3 - Volume Fractions of Carbides in Various Annealed High Speed Steels [136]

a)

b)

Figure 1.4 - Phase Diagrams of Two High Speed Steels:

a) T1 Type High Speed Steel-Binary Section Through Quaternary Fe-W-Cr-C System at 18% W and 6% Cr [67]

b) M2 Type High Speed Steel-Section Through the Diagram for 6%W, 5%Mo, 4%Cr and 2%V [66]

Figure 1.5 - As-Cast Microstructures of High Speed Steels [83]:

- a) T1 High Speed Steel
- b) M2 High Speed Steel
- c) ASP60 High Speed Steel

Figure 1.6 – Particle Formation Stages During Atomisation [40]

Figure 1.7 - Vacuum Sintering Curves Of Some HSS

ASP60: 2.3 C- 4.0 Cr- 6.5 W- 6.5 V- 7.0 Mo- 10.5 Co [19]

M3/2: 1.1 C- 4.02 Cr- 6.05 W- 2.91 V- 5.80 Mo [48]

T42: 1.37 C- 4.42 Cr- 9.81 W- 2.74 V- 3.10 Mo- 9.26 Co [136]

T1: 0.99 C- 4.39 Cr- 17.68 W- 1.04 V- 0.51 Mo [93]

Figure 1.8 – Effect of Sintering Atmosphere on Density of T42 HSS [32]

Figure 1.9 - The subdivisions of pressureless sintering; the first major division is with respect to solid versus liquid phase processes [111].

Figure 1.10- Portion of Binary Phase Diagram Showing Alloy Composition and Various Calculation Parameters Associated with Heating a Powder to Temperature T Between the Liquidus and Solidus Curves [118].

Figure 1.11 – Supersolidus Liquid Phase Sintering (SLPS) Schematic Diagram. SLPS Involves the Formation of a Liquid Along the Grain Boundaries in a Prealloyed Powder Which Leads to Densification [111].

Figure 1.12(a) – Schematic Representation of a Sintering Curve for a High Speed Steel Powder

Figure 1.12 – Schematic Representation of HSS's Sintering Curves and Correlation Between Sintering Curves and Phase Diagram Regions [25]
 b) Schematic Microstructural Evolution Along Sintering Curve
 c) Partial Phase Diagram

Figure 1.13 – Pseudobinary Phase Diagram for M2 type Alloys Showing Effects that Variations in Carbon, Vanadium, Tungsten and Molybdenum Content Have on Size and Shape of $\gamma + M_6C + MC + L$ Region [53]

Figure 1.14 – Sintering Curves for Experimental M42-type High Speed Steel Showing Cobalt effect on Sintering Temperatures [83,114]

- ◆ Fe+13Mo+1.2C
- Fe+14Mo+4Cr+1.4C
- ▲ Fe+14Mo+8Co+4Cr+1.5C

Figure 1.15 – Influence of Annealing Temperature and Time on Hardness After Annealing and on Grain Size After Hardening in M2 HSS [13]
 — 1200°C Hardening Temperature
 ---- 1230°C Hardening Temperature

b)

Figure 1.16 - a) Schematic Tempering Curve for High Speed Steels Showing Component Factors [1]

b) Hardness Variation with Tempering Temperature for M2 and T15 High Speed Steels [136]

Figure 1.19 - The Variation of the Solubility of Nitrogen with Temperature in Iron Under a Pressure of 1 Atmosphere of Nitrogen [186]

2 - EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

2.1 - POWDER PRODUCTION

2.1.1 - ATOMISATION

The nominal compositions of the HSS powders used in this investigation are given in Table 2.1. Powders were prepared using virgin ferro-alloys. Atomisations were carried out using a 5 Kg capacity Davy McKee D-5 water atomiser, Figure 2.1. The water was deionised using a automatic two bed deioniser ELGAMAT DUO 2, with $2 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ capacity. The deioniser is set with two vinylester fibreglass pressure vessels containing their respective cation and anion exchange resins. Both resins are synthetic organic copolymers of styrene and divinylbenzene in the physical form of small spherical beads of about 0.5 mm average diameter. Prior to atomisation, the alloy was melted in an electric induction furnace lined with an alumina crucible. In order to minimise oxidation of the atomised powder, flowing argon was used over both the melt and inside the atomisation chamber, as shown in Figure 2.1. The order, in which constituents were added to the melt, was based on the standard free energies of formation of oxides [186,187,188,189]. Hence, before switching on the induction furnace, it was loaded with Fe-W ferro-alloy, graphite and a master alloy whose composition was chosen according to the final desired composition. Once the initial charge had been melted, the remaining elements and ferro-alloys were added, in the following order: Co, Fe-Mo, Fe-Cr, Fe-V and Si (deoxidiser). The melt was then poured into the atomiser tundish, and flowed through the calibrated nozzle into the atomising chamber. There, the liquid metal stream was atomised by four high pressure (200 bar) water jets. The geometry of the water jets is shown schematically in Figure 2.2. The atomisation parameters are given in Table 2.2. After being dewatered and filtered (to avoid losing the finer fractions of the powders), atomised powders were dried by placing them in a stainless

steel container inside a vacuum oven (vacuum $\approx 1 \times 10^{-5}$ Pa) at a temperature of 80°C, for ≈ 16 hours [19,83].

2.1.2 - ANNEALING

Prior to compaction, water atomised HSS powders need to be annealed, a) to soften the particles, thereby improving their compressibility and b) to reduce surface oxides. Before the powders were annealed, optimum annealing temperatures, and cooling rates were determined using dilatometry, Table 2.3. The dilatometric tests were performed in a LK-02 ADAMEL device having a maximum operating temperature of 1100°C. The dilatometric tests were conducted using 12 mm long and 2 x 2 mm² square cross section samples made from rods cast from the same melts used to prepare the atomised powders [19,83]. The specimens were heated under vacuum at 10°C/min up to 950°C (normally, the transformation temperatures on heating, A_{ci} and A_{cf} , for this type of alloys [19,83] are lower than 950°C), kept at this temperature for 15 min and cooled at 2°C/min to room temperature. These conditions were chosen to simulate the cycle in the annealing furnace. These tests permit the information about the transformation temperatures of each alloy during the heating up, A_{ci} and A_{cf} , and cooling down, based on the linear variation of the samples. So, A_{ci} is the starting austenite transformation temperature during the heating up and A_{cf} is the ending austenite transformation temperature. Both are determined on the dilatometric traces, where the straight line changes its slope, Figure 3.2 and 3.3. Annealing should be done at a temperature above A_{cf} , to guarantee that all the powder is in the austenitic phase prior to slow cooling to room temperature.

Powder annealing was carried out in a GCA SUPER VII vacuum furnace, Figure 2.3, ($P_{max} \approx 10^{-2}$ Pa) [19,73,83]. The powder was placed inside a heat resistant steel tray, the

depth of the powder bed being 10-15 mm. The annealing cycle consisted of heating at a rate of $10^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$, up to the chosen annealing temperature, found in all cases to be 950°C , hold at this temperature until the vacuum was better than 10^{-2} Pa. Experience at INETI had shown that one factor determining satisfactory processing of water atomised high speed steel powders is that the oxygen content of the annealed powders be reduced to ≈ 1000 p.p.m. [73]. In order to achieve this, it had been established that powders should be held at the austenitising temperature until the vacuum was better than $\approx 10^{-2}$ Pa. Due to the different as atomised oxygen contents, austenitising times varied for each composition. These times are given in Table 2.3. However further soaking will result in significant decarburisation due to the reaction [89]:

The annealing cycle was completed by controlled cooling from the austenitising temperature to 600°C , at a rate of 2°C/min , as determined by the dilatometric tests, in order to guarantee that all the austenite would be transformed to ferrite plus carbides. Below 600°C the furnace power was switched off, and the powder allowed to cool naturally down to room temperature inside the furnace. Manual separation of the annealed powders was then necessary because they fritted slightly during the annealing cycle. This was carried out using a steel-carving spatula prior to them being sieved.

2.1.3 - CHARACTERISATION OF THE POWDERS

Chemical Analysis

The analysis of carbon, sulphur, oxygen and nitrogen was carried out using LECO systems. Carbon and sulphur analysis were carried out using a LECO CS-46 carbon and sulphur 748-600 system, using a determinator model 770-200 and furnace model 768-100. The accuracy of this system is 1% and 3% of the present carbon and sulphur, respectively, with a sensitivity of 0.0001% for both elements. Oxygen and nitrogen analyses were carried out using a LECO system 782-400-300 device model TC-436. These analysis, i.e. O₂ and N₂, were made by IR absorption (O₂) and thermal conductivity (N₂). The accuracy of this system is 1% of the O₂ and N₂ present, with a sensitivity of 0.00001% for both gases. The calibration of C, S, O₂ and N₂ in these devices was performed using LECO standards. The analysis of the remaining elements was performed in the Department of Chemical Analysis of I.N.E.T.I. (D.C.E.A.I.). The silicon and phosphorus analyses were performed by (visible) molecular absorption spectrometry. All the other elements were analysed by atomic absorption spectrometry.

The oxidised surface of the as-atomised powders particles usually causes errors in the determination of the content of some elements during the chemical analysis. In fact, when as-atomised powders were used for chemical analysis, their high surface oxide content prevented accurate chemical analysis. This was because the surface layers act as a barrier preventing the dissolution of the metallic particles. Hence, all chemical analyses were performed using the as-annealed powders, and rods cast from the same melts used to prepare the powders. However, carbon and oxygen analysis were performed on both as-atomised and as-annealed powders

Particle Size and Morphology

The particle size distribution of a powder is one of its principal qualities. An accepted way to describe an atomised powder size distribution is to use the median particle size and standard deviation (σ) of the log-normal distribution which is generally a very good fit to the experimental data [86]. The mean particle size is the median (i.e. 50% finer than) and the standard deviation of the distribution is equal to:

$$\sigma = \frac{d_{84.1\%}}{d_{50\%}} = \frac{d_{50\%}}{d_{15.9\%}} \quad (2.1)$$

Powder particle morphology was evaluated by stereoscopic optical microscope observation of a sample of the whole powder before annealing. The fraction below 125 μm (the working fraction) was observed using SEM. Sieve analysis was used in order to determine the particle size distribution of the atomised powders. A set of calibrated sieves (DIN 4188), given in Table 2.4, was used for each powder, with a sample of the as-atomised powder which was obtained in accordance with the ASTM B 215(ISO 3954) standard [144]. The test powder samples, 100 g, as defined in the ASTM B 214 standard, were placed on the top sieve, and this one closed with a solid cover. The sieve assembly was then fastened in a mechanical sieve-shaking device (FRITSCH TYPE 03.002) and operated for 30 minutes. The sieved fractions were removed from the nest of sieves and weighed. Only the sub 125 μm fraction was used in the sintering experiments. The coarser fraction was discarded.

Flowing Rate and Apparent Density

These characteristics were determined using the as-annealed powders, and were determined with the HALL flowmeter funnel (ASTM B 213, ISO 4490). For the determination of the flowing rate of the as-annealed powders, a $50 \pm 0.1\text{g}$ test specimens

were used. The test specimens were carefully loaded into the flowmeter funnel while the discharge orifice was kept closed by placing a dry finger under it. A stopwatch was then started simultaneously with the removal of the finger from the discharge orifice and stopped at the instant the last particles of the powder left the funnel. The elapsed time in seconds was then recorded [144].

Concerning the apparent density, 35 cm³ of powder were used. The entire test specimen was carefully loaded into the flowmeter funnel and permitted to flow through the discharge orifice into the centre of the density cup. When the powder completely filled and overflowed the periphery of the density cup, the funnel was rotated approximately 90° in the horizontal plane so that the remaining powder fell away from the cup. Then, using a non-magnetic spatula the powder was levelled off flush with the top of the density cup, lightly tapped on the side to settle the powder to avoid spilling in transfer and weighing [144]. Apparent density was determined to the nearest 0.01 g/cm³.

For those powders which did not flow freely through Hall flowmeter funnel, apparent densities were determined using the Carney apparatus (ASTM B417, ISO 3923/1). This has a larger orifice, 5.08 mm in diameter, compared to the 2.54 mm diameter of the Hall apparatus.

Tap Density

In order to determine the tap density of the as-annealed powders, a 100±0.5g test specimen of each powder was placed in a graduated glass cylinder of 100 ml capacity (ASTM B527; ISO 3953) and tapped mechanically until no further decrease of the volume took place [144]. The volume of the powder in the cylinder was then read, and the tap density calculated as follows:

$$\rho_t = \frac{m}{v} \quad (2.2)$$

where ρ_t = tap density [g/cm^3] reported to the nearest $0.1 \text{g}/\text{cm}^3$; m = mass of powder [g]; v = volume of tapped powder [cm^3].

Compressibility

Compressibility or compactibility, is the capacity of a metal powder to be compacted uniaxially in a closed die. It could be expressed numerically as the pressure to reach a required density or, alternately, the density at a given pressure, with density expressed in g/cm^3 to the nearest $0.01 \text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ [144]. In order to assess compressibility annealed powders were uni-directionally compacted as preforms $22 \times 6 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$, in a semi-automatic RESULT HPA-15 15 ton capacity compacting press device, using a tungsten carbide die and punches. The range of compaction pressures was 600, 700 and 800 MPa. The green compacts were weighed to the nearest 0.01g and the dimensions were measured to the nearest 0.01 mm [144] using a Carl Zeiss optical measuring microscope.

After the compacting tests, a plot of the green density of the compacts versus the compacting pressure was traced. Samples for vacuum and nitrogen sintering were generally compacted to give green densities of about 70 % theoretical, using compacting pressures of 700 MPa.

Powder mixing

Blending of the annealed powders with graphite was carried out in a 2 Kg capacity Turbula type T2C mixer. Mixing conditions, based on previous experience at INETI [73], comprised 60 minutes mixing time at 42 rpm. The graphite powder was obtained from The British Drug Houses Ltd.

2.2 - POWDER PROCESSING

2.2.1 - VACUUM SINTERING

Vacuum sintering was performed using compacts prepared from the annealed P68 composition. In order to increase sinterability 0.1 and 0.2 % wt additions of graphite were made to the annealed powder. Vacuum sintering of P77 and P81 compositions were carried out without any graphite being added to the powders.

Green compacts (size 22 x 6 x 5 mm³) were sintered in a GCA SUPER VII pilot scale furnace, under vacuum (10⁻⁴ Pa) within a heat resistant steel box. This box was used in order to homogenise the temperature among the specimens, and its dimensions, 20 x 10 x 3 cm³, were chosen in order to fit within the hot zone of the furnace. The hot zone was calibrated using three Pt/ Pt-13%Rh thermocouples. The preforms were heated at a rate of 10°C/min., soaked for one hour at the sintering temperature and then furnace cooled. Furnace temperature was controlled using a shielded W-Re thermocouple linked to a Honeywell Digital Control Programmer DCP-7700 automatic controller. Sintering temperatures control was judged to be better than ± 2°C.

The Archimedes method was used to determine the density of the sintered samples. The accuracy of this method can be affected by ingress of water into slightly porous samples. In order to minimise the source of error specimens were coated with a cellulose lacquer. Density was calculated by the relationship:

$$d = \frac{W}{V} \quad (2.3)$$

where W is the mass of the specimen (g) and V is its volume (cm³), calculated as follows:

$$V = \frac{(W_{La} - W_{Lw}) - (W_L - W)}{1.3} \quad (2.4)$$

Where W_L is the mass of the specimen coated with lacquer; W_{La} is the mass of the specimen coated with lacquer and suspended in air by a cotton thread and W_{Lw} is the mass of the specimen coated with lacquer and suspended in water. The value 1.3 g/cm^3 is the density of the lacquer, determined previously by a densitometer. Densities were determined to the nearest 0.01 g/cm^3 .

2.2.2 - NITROGEN SINTERING

Nitrogen sintering was carried out in a tubular alumina furnace with the dimensions of $46 \text{ mm} \times 38 \text{ mm} \times 1000 \text{ mm}$ and maximum temperature of 1550°C , shown schematically in Figure 2.4. The temperature was controlled within $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ using a certified standard type R thermocouple (Pt / Pt-13%Rh) linked to an Eurotherm Controller type 818. The thermocouple hot junction was remade every 20 cycles. This was carried out in order to avoid any erroneous measurements due to mechanical failure or contamination of the thermocouple. The hot zone length was 5 cm long, Figure 2.4(c), and it was determined using a Pt / Pt-13%Rh thermocouple pushed through the furnace, maintained at working conditions. Temperatures were controlled to $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.

The atmosphere was composed of a mixture of $\text{N}_2/7\% \text{H}_2$ with an average dew point of about $-67^\circ/-68^\circ\text{C}$ corresponding to about 3-4 p.p.m. of H_2O . The dew point determinations were carried out with an automatic dew point meter (SHAW Electronic Hygrometer, type SADP). The composition of the gas mixture was determined in the Materials Department of I.N.E.T.I. using chromatography. During the sintering cycles the relative percentage of each gas was controlled by two Fisher and Porter flowmeters (FP-1/8-08-P-3/37 with a sapphire float for H_2 control, and FP-1/8-20-P-3/37 with a stainless steel float for N_2 control). The flowmeters were set to produce the desired $\text{N}_2+7\% \text{H}_2$. These settings were used for all the sintering cycles. The gases used were a C-45 grade nitrogen and a C-50 grade hydrogen both supplied by GASIN.

The sintering cycle was performed using a heating rate of 10°C/min. up to the sintering temperature, 1 hour soaking time at this temperature and natural furnace cooling. The samples were placed inside a heat resistant steel container on an alumina short fibre cloth (safil), Figure 2.4(d). Two dummy green samples were placed at both ends next to the other ones to be sintered, Figure 2.4(d). This was done to create a thermal inertia among the samples.

Samples were generally allowed to cool naturally in the furnace. However, a number of sintering trials was conducted in which samples were quenched from the sintering temperature. For these experiments, samples were attached to a platinum wire leading out of the furnace tube. Samples were rapidly withdrawn from the hot zone (≈ 2 -3 sec.) and quenched in oil. The densities of the specimens were determined by the Archimedes method, described in section 2.2.1.

Several graphite additions to the as-annealed powders were carried out, in order to have different carbon contents, that could enable a more accurate investigation on the sintering behaviour through out a broad range of compositions, as described in section 3.4.2.

2.2.3 - DIFFERENTIAL THERMAL ANALYSIS (D.T.A.)

Differential Thermal Analysis (D.T.A.) is used to investigate high temperature reactions of materials [189,190]. The resulting thermograms exhibit events with characteristic temperatures of a certain system. *Solidus* and *liquidus* temperatures of selected powders were determined using D.T.A.. In this technique a specimen of the material under test together with an inert reference material (alumina), which undergoes no reaction in the testing temperature range, are subjected to a thermal cycle at constant heating and cooling rates. The difference between the specimen's temperature rise and that of the reference material is plotted against temperature. When the specimen undergoes a transformation, this can be either an energy absorption, which promotes the decrease of the specimen temperature in relation with the reference material (endothermic peak), or an energy release (exothermic peak).

The tests were carried out in a Sétaram device model TGA/DTA 92 at the Centre des Materiaux of École des Mines de Paris. It was equipped with Pt-6Rh /Pt-30Rh or Pt/Pt 10Rh thermocouple pairs with alumina crucible which inner size was $\phi 3.5$ mm x 7 mm. The tiny size of the measuring cell imposed little amount of testing samples (≈ 0.3 g) which means a weak amplitude signal. Therefore, gains of about 10,000 were then applied. The samples, which had been compacted at a pressure of ≈ 1 MPa, using the "as-annealed" powders, were sized 3-4 mm in diameter and 6-8 mm high. Both heating and cooling rates were $10^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$, the same used in the sintering cycles, and the tests were performed in the temperature range 20-1350°C. Tests were performed in both argon (in order to have a protective atmosphere avoiding oxidation, similar to the vacuum sintering runs), and nitrogen.

2.2.4 - HOT ISOSTATIC PRESSING (HIP)

The HIP cycles were performed in a NF-National Forge Europe device, which maximum pressure is 200 MPa, and maximum temperature is 1500°C. The pressure gas used in this device is argon. The HIP cycle consisted of a heating ramp of 10°C min⁻¹, up to the desired temperature, soaking for 1 hour and cooled at a rate of 20°C min⁻¹. The HIP temperature was chosen accordingly to the onset temperature, T_{os} , of the rapid densifying zone of the nitrogen sintering curves (as only nitrogen sintered specimens were undersintered and HIP), in order to avoid any liquid formation which would lead to the formation of eutectic phases, which are known to degrade mechanical properties. Hence, for the P68 alloy T_{os} was 1100°C, and for the P77 and P81 alloys the desired temperature was 1050°C. From the sintering data presented in section 3.4.2 HIP temperatures were 1050°C, the HIP pressure being 150 MPa.

2.3 - HEAT TREATMENT

Heat treatment studies were performed both on vacuum and nitrogen-rich atmosphere sintered samples, 22 x 6 x 4 mm³. Heat treatment consists of pre heating in a salt bath (Degussa type GS450) for 30 min. at a temperature of 700°C. Samples were then transferred to a second salt bath (Degussa type GS750) set to the desired temperature. Samples were held at the austenitising temperature for 2 min then oil quenched to room temperature. The austenitising temperatures used were: 1050°, 1075°, 1100°, 1150°, 1175° and 1200°C. The bath temperature was controlled with a type S thermocouple (Pt/Pt 10%Rh) within $\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

The tempering of the quenched samples was carried out in a muffle type furnace. In order to prevent decarburisation samples were imbedded in a mixture of alumina/graphite powders. Samples were triple tempered in the temperature range 400°-600°C, with each temper lasting 1 hour. The temperature was controlled by a Cr-Ni type K thermocouple

placed among the samples. The temperature was controlled to $\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$. After each tempering treatment the samples were removed from the furnace and natural cooled in the air.

2.4 - CHARACTERISATION OF THE MICROSTRUCTURES

2.4.1 - OPTICAL MICROSCOPY

All the samples were mounted in a polymeric thermo-plastic resin and automatically ground on water cooled silicon carbide papers with gradually finer grit size, followed by polishing on clothes impregnated with 6 μm and 3 μm diamond pastes and finally manual polished on a cloth impregnated with a slurry of γ -alumina (0.05 μm) in water to reveal the carbides. All the samples were etched with 2 or 5 % nital to reveal austenite grain boundaries and examined using a Zeiss Axiomat optical microscope or a S.E.M.

2.4.2 - SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (S.E.M.)

Scanning electron microscopy was performed using a JEOL JSM 35CF (15 kV) equipped with an EDS spectrometer TRACOR model TN 2000/4000 with a TRACOR Si(Li) detector and a JEOL 6400 device, this one using a Energy Dispersive Spectrometry (EDS) equipment consisting of a Link Systems LKS detector interfaced to a Kevex Sigma analysis system. The samples were mounted and polished as described in section 2.4.1 and were graphite or gold sputter coated in order to prevent charging, in a JEOL-JEE-4X sputter coater. Gold coating was used when samples were mounted in a non-conductive resin. Fractography was carried out on sets of fractured specimens (placed side to side), which fracture surface was arranged upwards, in order to allow easier observations.

2.4.3 - ELECTRON PROBE MICRO ANALYSIS

The microprobe analyses were carried out using a Cameca SX50 EPMA device either at the University of Coimbra or at the Institut National Polytechnique de Grenoble. This device was used in order to obtain quantitative analysis of several phases of the microstructure of the samples, and to obtain x-ray maps with the elements distribution. The crystals used in the analysis of the specified elements were: PC2 (pseudo-crystal) for carbon, LiF for tungsten, iron, vanadium and cobalt, AlN for nitrogen and PET ($C_5H_{12}O_4$) for molybdenum. The samples were mounted in a polymeric thermo-plastic resin and automatically ground as reported in 2.4.1. No etching was required for the samples observed in the microprobe.

2.4.4 - QUANTITATIVE IMAGE ANALYSIS

Quantitative image analysis was performed on a image analysis system Tracor Northern TN-8500 model. The images could be taken from both optical or S.E.M. microscopes by an interface Super Scan Generator (SSG) system or by a Hires high resolution video camera. After being captured, the images were automatically converted into binary images with several grey contrast levels. Quantitative analysis was then performed when discrimination of phases of differing compositions was possible. Due to the low contrast level of the different phases present in the nitrogen sintered specimens, only some vacuum sintered specimens, where optimal conditions were observed, were analysed. The measurements were directly screened. Quantitative image analysis of nitrogen sintered specimens was then performed on both SEM screen or on micrographs taken by SEM, using grids placed either on the SEM screen or on the micrographs. At least 10 fields were counted for each specimen.

2.4.5 - X-RAY DIFFRACTION

Identification of phases present in both powders and sintered samples, was carried by x-ray diffraction. These studies were performed using a Rigaku-D/MAX IIC X-ray (45kV, 20mA) copper radiation ($K\alpha = 1.5406$) device was employed. The sintered samples were roughly polished with water cooled silicon carbide papers and previously cut in order to have similar dimensions ($12 \times 6 \times 4 \text{mm}^3$) so that the x-ray diffractograms could be compared. Powder samples were simply placed on a rectangular glass container, always having the same area $\approx 4 \text{cm}^2$. The scanning rate was $0.5^\circ/\text{min.}$, and tests were carried out using 2θ values ranging from 30° up to 130° in increments of 0.01° .

The identification of the different phases detected by x-ray diffraction was carried out by comparison between the respective reticular distances (d_{hkl}) present on the x-ray diffractograms and those of x-ray diffraction files [191], Table 2.5(a) and (b). As some of the phases present on the microstructure (particularly the carbides) were not stoichiometric compounds, but solid solutions of several constituents, measured d_{hkl} exhibited small differences compared to those given for the phase in the ASTM data files [191].

2.5 - MECHANICAL TESTS

2.5.1 - HARDNESS

The hardness tests were performed using an Otto-Wolpert-Werke apparatus (10-2500 N capacity) fitted with a Vickers square pyramidal diamond indentator. The load used for the hardness tests of all samples was 298 N (HV30). The HV values were determined as the mean of at least 10 individual measurements.

2.5.2 - MICROHARDNESS

The samples were mounted, polished and etched as reported in 2.4.1. The microhardness tests were performed in a ZWICK machine fitted with a Vickers square pyramidal diamond indentator, using a 0.5 N load. HV0.5 values were determined as the mean of 10 individual measurements.

2.5.3 - BEND STRENGTH

For the evaluation of the tensile rupture strength (TRS) of the sintered and heat treated specimens a three-point bending test was performed, using an INSTRON TTCM universal testing machine with 50 kN maximum capacity. The load was applied at a rate of 0.1 mm/min. The geometry of the test rig is shown in Figure 2.5, where h= specimen width, b= specimen height, l= span (16 mm) and F= load. The testing specimens had the dimensions 20x4x2 mm³ according to standards ASTM B 528-76 and ASTM B 399-81, and were longitudinally ground from oversized heat treated specimens (22x6x4 mm³) with their tensile faces metallographically polished (down to 3 μm diamond paste).

The bend strength, σ_F , was calculated using the following relationship:

$$\sigma_F = \frac{3Fl}{2bh^2} \quad (2.5)$$

Bend strength was calculated as the average of 10 samples for each condition.

Table 2.1 – Nominal Composition (wt%) of the Powders used in the present Investigation

	P68	P75	P72	P73	P74	P77	P81
C	2.4	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.8	2.5
V	8.0	6.0	8.0	10.0	12.0	8.0	6.0
W	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0
Mo	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Cr	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
Co	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0

Table 2.2 – Atomisation Parameters

Powder Code		P68	P75	P72	P73	P74	P77	P81
Tundish Hole (ϕ mm)		5						
Tap Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)		1740	1718	1770	1750	1740	1735	1720
Crucible Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)		900	992	1017	996	1012	930	970
Main Nozzles	Angle	50						
	Type	1504+stabilizer						
Secondary Nozzles	Angle	30						
	Type	1501.5						
Water Pressure (bar)		200						
Water Flow (litre/min.)	Total	35.4						
	Main Nozzles	26						
	Sec. Nozzles	9.4						

Table 2.3 – Annealing Parameters of the Powders used in the present work

Powder	Heating Rate [$^{\circ}$ C/min.]	Annealing Temperature [$^{\circ}$ C]	Soak Duration	Vacuum [Pa]	Cooling Rate [$^{\circ}$ C/min.]
P68	10	950	1h 30min	10^{-2}	2
P75	10	950	2h 25min	10^{-2}	2
P72	10	950	5h 30min	10^{-2}	2
P73	10	950	3h 30min	10^{-2}	2
P74	10	950	3h 45min	10^{-2}	2
P77	10	950	1h 30min	10^{-2}	2
P81	10	950	1h 30min	10^{-2}	2

Table 2.4 – Screen Sieve Set

Sieve Opening [μm]
800
250
200
125
90
63
45
36

Table 2.5 – (a) Identification Criteria for the Phase Peaks Present in the Experimental X-Ray Diffractograms as compared with the d_{hkl} Values Shown in the X-Ray Diffraction Files [191].

Phase	Crystal Structure	Cell Parameter [\AA]	d_{hkl} * [\AA]		
			d_{hkl}	d_{hkl} '	d_{hkl} ''
Ferrite (α)	b.c.c.	2.8664	2.0268 _x	1.1702 ₃₀	1.4332 ₂₀
Austenite (γ)	f.c.c.	3.60	2.08 _x	1.80 ₈₀	1.083 ₈₀
Fe ₃ W ₃ C- Fe ₄ W ₂ C- Fe ₃ Mo ₃ C (M ₆ C)	f.c.c.	11.04	2.12 _x	2.75 ₈₀	2.53 ₈₀
VC (MC)	f.c.c.	4.16	2.40 _x	2.07 _x	1.47 ₅₀
Fe ₃ C	orthorhombic	a=5.0915 b=6.7446 c=4.5276	2.068 _x	2.108 ₈₀	1.9775 ₆₅
(Cr,Fe) ₇ C ₃ (M ₇ C ₃)	hexagonal	a ₀ =13.98 c ₀ =4.523	2.04 _x	2.12 ₆₀	1.81 ₆₀
(Cr,Fe,W,Mo) ₂₃ C ₆ Fe ₂₁ (W,Mo) ₂ C ₆ (M ₂₃ C ₆)	cubic	**	2.044 _x	2.375 ₈₀	2.168 ₆₀

* - Index shows intensity value (x=100)

** - The Lattice Dimensions Depend on Alloy Content

a)

b)

Figure 2.1 - Water Atomisation Assembly

a)1-Atomiser 2-High Pressure Water Pump 3-Induction Furnace

b) Water Atomiser Schedule

Figure 2.2 - Water Jets Configuration
a) Tridimensional View
b) Top View

Figure 2.3 - Vacuum Sintering Furnace

a)

b)

Figure 2.4 – Atmosphere Sintering Assembly

- a) General View
- b) Schematic View

c)

d)

Figure 2.4 – Atmosphere Sintering Assembly

- c) Temperature Profile Along the Alumina Tube
- d) Diagram of Specimens Placement inside the Steel Container

a)

b)

Figure 2.5 – Bending Test Rig

- a) General view
- b) Schematic View

3 - RESULTS

3.1 - WATER ATOMISATION

The aim was to obtain high-vanadium high speed steels, based on the composition of standard T42 HSS. The P68 powder was intended to have vanadium and carbon contents of 8 wt% and 2.4 wt%, respectively. The series P72 - P75 was intended to have vanadium contents ranging from 6 to 12%, with carbon contents of $\approx 1\%$, with further alloys created by the addition of elemental carbon. Further powders having higher carbon contents were produced: P77 (2.7%C, 8% V) and P81 (2.6%C, 6% V). Chemical compositions of the powders in the “as-atomised” and annealed states are given in Table 3.1.

The parameters (conditions) used in the atomisation of the seven water atomised powders produced in this work are shown in Table 3.2. These parameters were selected as the result of previous experience at INETI [19]. The melt flow time varied according to the melt composition and temperature, which determined the viscosity of the liquid melt. In fact, for the powders having nominal 6 wt% V, P75 and P81, the last one, though had a lower temperature in the tundish (this was less hot), have a higher metal flow rate, 8.15 Kg min^{-1} , it having as well a higher carbon content, Table 3.1. For the powders with nominal vanadium content of 8 wt%, P68, P72 and P77, the one which had the highest metal flow rate was that with the highest carbon content, i.e. P77. Nevertheless, P68 though having a higher carbon content than P72, Table 3.1, did not have a higher metal flow rate, this being due to a lower tundish temperature in the P68 atomisation run, Table 3.2. The P73 and P74 powders needed a higher tap temperature to flow, even so, P74 alloy only flew for 50 seconds. Hence, regarding the metal flowrates of the seven powders, this increased concomitantly with increasing carbon content. Conversely, a higher melt viscosity was

found for an increasing vanadium content. The amount of powder obtained also varied with composition, it was found that higher vanadium and lower carbon contents favoured the formation of slag, which tended to obstruct the atomiser tundish nozzle. This was particularly noticeable in the case of P74. In fact, the P74 alloy though having a metal flowrate of 6.24 Kg min^{-1} only runned for 50 seconds, which resulted in the lowest powder production of all the runs, 5.2 Kg. The yield of each batch, i.e. the amount of powder finer than $125 \mu\text{m}$, is shown in Table 3.3 and Figure 3.1(h). Figure 3.1 (a) to (g) shows typical SEM micrographs of the seven powders ($<125 \mu\text{m}$ fraction). As it can be seen, all the powders exhibited an irregular particle shape, but particles size distribution were different for each batch, Table 3.3. The P68 powder was the one which has the lower percentage of particles finer than $125 \mu\text{m}$, and the inverse for coarser particles. P77 was the powder with the highest amount of finer particles ($<125\mu\text{m}$), having a very low percentage of particles coarser than $125 \mu\text{m}$ ($\approx 10 \%$). The amount of finer particles influence the yield of each atomisation run, P68 being the powder with the lowest yield (46 wt%), and P77 the powder with the highest one (89.2 wt%). Both powders had the same nominal vanadium content, i.e. 8 wt%, but P77 had a higher carbon content, Table 3.1. The remaining powders have yields in the range 60-70 wt%, and particle size distribution in between the referred to P68 and P77 alloys.

3.2 - ANNEALING OF THE ATOMISED POWDERS

The dried powders were sieved in order to separate the $<125\mu\text{m}$ fraction, which is the current particle size range for commercial water atomised powders. Dilatometric tests were carried out using “as cast” specimens obtained from the corresponding melt, in order

to determine the A_{ci} and A_{cf} transformation temperatures, and also the transformations on cooling. The resultant transformation temperatures are given in Table 3.4 and the dilatometric traces in Figure 3.2. The ferrite→austenite transformation was not observed for the P74 and P75 compositions, in the temperature range investigated (up to 950°C), and the powders remained ferritic. No direct relation between the transformation temperatures and the alloys composition was observed.

Figure 3.3 illustrates the cooling curves obtained for all compositions: the cooling rate of 2°C/min was slow enough to ensure complete austenite→ferrite + carbide transformation of P72, P73, P77 and P81, avoiding the formation of martensite or bainite (no B_s or M_s observed) which would affect the compressibility of the powders, while P74 and P75 powders exhibited no obvious phase transformations upon cooling.

The annealing cycle carried out in the vacuum furnace was similar to that used in the dilatometric tests, i.e. identical heating and cooling rates, except for the soaking time at 950°C, which was as long as necessary (up to 4 hours) to reduce the amount of oxides to an acceptable level, shown by the pressure drops in the furnace, as explained in Section 2.1.2.

3.3 - CHARACTERISATION OF THE POWDERS

3.3.1 - CHEMICAL COMPOSITION

The results of the analysis described in Section 2.1.3, are shown in Table 3.1. The oxygen contents of the P72, P73, P74 and P75 as-atomised powders were higher (≈ 6000 p.p.m.) than those usually found for water atomised high speed steel powders ($\approx 2000-3000$ p.p.m.) [19,20,69,73]. The necessary time to remove continuously the slag from the melt top before the atomisation, was enough to allow some carbon to evaporate. In fact, the P73 and P74, the nominal 10 and 12 wt% vanadium powders respectively, showed a decrease

upon atomisation of the vanadium content, and the four powders, P72, P73, P74 and P75, have a carbon content lower than the desired content of 1 wt%. The P68, P77 and P81 powders, since they were not so oxidised, elemental depletion did not take place, they had the desired target compositions. This can be attributed to the higher carbon content of these last alloys.

As expected, both oxygen and carbon contents decreased upon vacuum annealing. In general, an oxygen reduction of about 0.3 wt% was accompanied by a carbon reduction of 0.2 wt%, Table 3.1. After annealing, the oxygen content of the P72 through P75 powders was still high, ≈ 2000 -6000 p.p.m., but more prolonged annealing would have dropped the carbon content to levels that were not in consonance with the aims of this research. For the remaining powders (P68, P77 and P81) both carbon and oxygen “as-atomised” contents were in the normal range for these type of alloys. The actual compositions of all powders were very close to the nominal, except in those relating to the carbon content of the powders P72 through P75. In these powders the carbon content was lower than expected after annealing, due to the high content of vanadium oxides in the as atomised powders. Figure 3.4 shows the microstructure and EDS analysis of a P74 (12% V) powder particle, in both “as-atomised” and annealed conditions. The microstructural characteristics of the P72 (8% V) and P73 (10% V) alloys were similar to the ones shown in Figure 3.4. In this figure the dark lines are oxides: though it was not possible to analyse for oxygen, the high dark level of contrast are equivalent to a low average atomic number, indicating oxide inclusions. This microstructural feature was not seen after annealing, Figure 3.4 (b), though the oxygen content of the annealed P74 powder (as well as P72, P73 and P75) was still considered high, i.e. in excess of 2000 p.p.m., for this type of alloys, Table 3.1. The “as-annealed” powders show typical microstructures of fine carbides. These were identified by x-ray diffraction as MC and M_6C carbides dispersed in a ferritic matrix,

Figure 3.4 (b) and Figure 3.5 (b). Nevertheless, in the “as-annealed” P72-P75 powder series, the x-ray diffraction patterns did not show any MC carbides, Figure 3.5 (d), though they could be seen at the microstructure as shown in Figure 3.4 (b). This is probably because their volume fraction was below the limits of detection in x-ray diffractor. In the higher vanadium containing powders, P73 (10% V) and P74 (12% V), the final vanadium content was lower than intended due to the formation of the referred to above oxides in the powder particles, and at the melt surface during the atomisation. As it can be seen, the P72-P75 series of powders had abnormally high oxygen contents in the “as-atomised” condition, compared to values normally expected for these types of alloys. The higher the vanadium content of the powders the higher the oxygen present after atomisation. These highly oxidised powders necessitated longer annealing cycles, which resulted in powders having a lower carbon content than previously desired (about 1 wt% in the as-annealed condition). The presence of the oxides in the melt also made the atomisation runs difficult, because the melt was very viscous, making flow through the atomiser tundish nozzle difficult.

Figure 3.5 (a) and (b) shows the characteristic microstructure of the P68 powder particles, in both “as-atomised” and annealed conditions. The microstructure shown in this figure was also representative of the P75, P77 and P81 powders, in the same conditions. The “as-atomised” microstructure showed a dendritic structure, typical of “as-cast” materials. After annealing, the MC and M₆C carbides were found dispersed in a ferritic matrix. The x-ray diffraction patterns of all the powders used in the present research, both in the “as-atomised” and “as-annealed” condition, are shown in Figure 3.5 (c) and (d). It can be seen in Figure 3.5 (c) (powders in the “as-atomised” condition) that for the P68, P77 and P81 powders, the ones which have an higher carbon content, the austenite peak is stronger than the ferrite (martensite) one, austenite not being detected for the remaining

powders. In all powders MC was the only carbide detected. With regard to the annealed powders, Figure 3.5 (d), it can be seen that again there exists a difference between P68, P77, P81 compositions and the remaining powders, the first three ones being the only ones that showed MC carbide peaks besides M_6C , in the other compositions only M_6C was observed in x-ray diffraction patterns.

3.3.2 - PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

Besides sieve analysis (Table 3.3), the results of the determination of the relevant physical properties of the powders, are shown in Table 3.5. After observation of the powders in stereoscopic and SEM microscopes to check their particle morphology or shape, it was concluded that all the seven powders had irregular shaped particles, as expected for water atomised powders, Figure 3.1. For P68, the mean particle size was 140 μm , about 30% to 60% coarser than in the case of the other powders. Compacting at 700 MPa provided sufficient green density of the specimens (>60%), adequate for further processing by sintering [40]. Figure 3.6 shows the green density of all powders plotted versus the compacting pressure. All the powders showed an increase in density with increasing compacting pressure, P75 (6% V) was the powder with the highest green density at 700 MPa (the working compacting pressure selected on the basis of these curves) and P68 (8% V) the powder with the lowest density for the same compacting pressure.

3.4 - SINTERING BEHAVIOUR

3.4.1 - VACUUM SINTERING

3.4.1.1 - PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENTS WITH P68

Vacuum sintering of the P68 powder was performed both without and with graphite additions: 0.1 wt%-P68A, and 0.2 wt%-P68B. Green compacts were prepared using two pressures, 600 MPa and 800 MPa.

On a HSS's sintering curve three relevant temperatures can be identified as shown in Figure 3.7 [105]: T_{os} the temperature needed to initiate sintering, T_m as the minimum temperature to achieve full density and T_d the distortion temperature. An optimum sintering temperature (OST) can also be defined as a value about 5-10°C higher than T_m [136], where no (or only residual) porosity is observed and the microstructures do not exhibit coarse austenite grains or continuous grain boundaries carbide films, which would cause poor mechanical properties [73]. The sintering window is the temperature range on the sintering plateau at which the microstructures are considered still in condition to give the material good mechanical properties [48,114].

The variation in sintered density with both compaction pressure and sintering temperature for P68 and the two blends with added carbon, P68A and P68B, is shown in Figures 3.8 (a)- (c). For P68 the temperature for the onset of rapid densification, T_{os} see Figure 3.7, was found to be independent of compaction pressure. Samples compacted at 600 and 800 MPa started to undergo rapid densification at temperatures above 1220°C. Similarly, T_m was also independent of compaction pressure. In both cases the minimum temperature needed to attain maximum density was 1250°C. As can be seen from Figure 3.8 (a) samples could be sintered to densities of 8.1 g cm⁻³ over the temperature range 1250-1280°C. However, sintering at 1280°C resulted in sample distortion - rounding of edges.

The only influence of compaction pressure was at temperatures below 1250°C where the higher compaction pressure resulted in higher sintered densities. This effect, though, was less apparent as the temperature increased towards 1250°C.

The same effect of compaction pressure was observed with P68A and P68B samples, Figures 3.8(b) and (c). As can be seen the sintering behaviours of these two blends were similar to P68. The only differences observed were slight reductions in the values of T_{os} and T_m . The values for T_m for P68A and P68B were 1245 and 1240°C, respectively. T_{os} also showed similar small reductions compared to P68. As with P68 samples, P68A and P68B samples sintered to densities in excess of 8.1 g cm⁻³ with sample distortion occurring on sintering at 1270 and 1260°C, respectively.

Figures 3.9 and 3.10 show the “as sintered” microstructures and x-ray diffraction patterns of vacuum sintered P68 with no carbon addition. For the samples sintered up to 1250°C the microstructure of the P68 powder sintered in vacuum with no graphite addition was composed of globular shaped vanadium-rich MC carbides imbedded in a bainitic/martensitic matrix (600-700 HV0.05) as shown in Figure 3.9 (b). This bainitic/martensitic matrix is a transformation product of the austenite due to the fast cooling rate inside the vacuum furnace (>80°C/min.). A small volume fraction of M₆C carbide was also present in samples sintered at 1210°C, Figure 3.10 (a), its amount decreasing with increasing temperature. At and above 1260°C, an acicular shaped tungsten/molybdenum rich carbide can also be seen at the grain boundaries, Figure 3.11, but its volume fraction was not enough to be detected by x-ray diffraction as shown in Figure 3.10 (b). But its morphology and qualitative EDS analysis suggested that it was a M₂C-type carbide. The M₂C carbides were more pronounced at higher temperatures, Figure 3.9(d).

Figure 3.12 shows the microprobe micrograph and x-ray maps of carbon, vanadium, tungsten and chromium, of a sample sintered at 1260°C. The contents of carbon,

vanadium and tungsten are higher in the MC carbides and very weak or not detected in the matrix, unlike chromium that is evenly distributed all over the specimen.

Above 1280°C, incipient fusion caused the formation of eutectic carbides, affecting the shape of the specimen: a needle-type tungsten-molybdenum-rich carbide at the austenite grain boundaries, as shown in Figure 3.9 (d). The coarsening of the MC primary carbide and prior austenite grain size is also remarked, as shown in Table 3.6. The MC type carbide size range evolution with temperature is as follows: up to 1240°C the carbide size is 1-3 µm, at 1240°C their size is in the range 1-5 µm, at 1250°C is 1-8 µm, at 1260°C is 1-10 µm, at 1270°C is 1-15 µm and at 1280°C, the distortion temperature, is 1-20 µm. MC carbides precipitate both inside the grains (intragranular) and at the grain boundaries (intergranular), the latter ones being much larger, Figure 3.9(a) to (e).

Below T_{os} open porosity was observed with sharp shaped pores, Figure 3.9 (a). At T_m , closed porosity was observed, i.e. a few rounded pores, larger than those observed in the samples sintered at lower temperatures, Figure 3.9 (b). All samples sintered on the sintering plateau, contained small amounts of isolated residual porosity.

In spite of the sintering plateau starting at lower temperatures for the powders P68A and P68B, the sintering window has the same width as for the powder without graphite addition, i.e. 10°C. The microstructures of the vacuum sintered P68A and P68B powders are similar to those ones reported above, but shifted 10 and 20°C downwards respectively.

3.4.1.2 - VACUUM SINTERING OF P77 AND P81

Figure 3.13 shows the vacuum sintering curves for both P77 and P81 powders. Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15 show the microstructures of the vacuum sintered P77 and P81, respectively, at different sintering temperatures, T_{os} , T_m , OST and T_d . With regard to the microstructures, both P77 and P81 powders exhibited similar features. Following sintering

at 1130°C both alloys exhibited uniform distributions of small MC- and M_6C -type carbides, dispersed in the matrix, Figure 3.14 (a) and Figure 3.15 (a). Up to sintering temperatures of 1190°C the microstructure was composed of MC type carbides ranging 1 to 3 μm and open porosity (Figures 3.14 (b) and 3.15 (b)). At 1200°C, T_m temperature for both P77 and P81 powders, the MC carbides range 1 to 12 μm and only residual porosity is observed. The matrix microhardness is in the range 495-565 HV0.05 (P77) and 505-580 HV0.05 (P81). At sintering temperatures of 1190°C and above the formation of acicular eutectic M_2C carbides was observed, Figure 3.14 (b) and Figure 3.15 (b). The volume fraction, which was greater in the P81 samples, increased with increasing sintering temperatures, Figure 3.14(c) and (d) and Figure 3.15(c) and (d). This difference may be attributed to the higher carbon content of P81. The distortion temperature (T_d) is 1250°C for both alloys, with P81 distorting more than P77 specimens. This higher distortion in the P81 specimens corresponds in the microstructure to a continuous M_2C grain boundary eutectic carbide network, more extensive than in the P77 alloy. The MC carbides show a size range of 1 to 18 μm and the usual globular shape, and the matrix microhardness was 500/540 HV0.05 (P77) and 480/560 HV0.05 (P81).

3.4.2 - ATMOSPHERE SINTERING

3.4.2.1 - ATMOSPHERE SINTERING OF THE P68 POWDER

The sintering curve of P68 composition sintered in the $N_2+7\% H_2$ atmosphere is shown in Figure 3.16. The P68 specimens sintered in a $N_2+7\%H_2$ atmosphere showed quite different features in their microstructures compared to those sintered in vacuum. Figure 3.17 shows the general and detail views of the microstructures of the specimens sintered at

(a) and (b) 600°C (below A_{ci}), (c) and (d) 950°C (above A_{cf}), (e) and (f) 1120°C (T_{os}), (g) and (h) 1180°C (T_m), (i) and (j) 1200°C (OST) and (k) and (l) 1260°C (T_d).

No particle bonding was observed at the specimens sintered at 600°C, that was carried out in the ferritic field. Although the porosity evolution is similar to the vacuum sintered specimens, i.e. open porosity up to the middle of the rapid densifying zone ($\approx 1140^\circ\text{--}1150^\circ\text{C}$), closed porosity after this region, and only residual porosity after 1190°C, the carbide types present and their sizes were very different. The carbides present in these specimens were: MC/MX, M_6C and M_3C . The globular MC-type vanadium-rich carbides, are located mainly at the grain boundaries, though some were present within the grains, sized $<0.5\text{--}3\ \mu\text{m}$, present in the specimens sintered all over the sintering temperature range, Figure 3.17, and as determined by the microprobe analysis were the only phases that dissolve nitrogen being therefore MC/MX, Table 3.12. As these carbides present in the specimens sintered at very low temperatures, 600°, 800° and 950°C are so tiny, $<0.5\text{--}1\ \mu\text{m}$, no local quantitative microprobe analysis could be carried out. Nevertheless, regarding the nitrogen content of these specimens, Table 3.7, it can be seen that the specimens sintered at 600°C have the same nitrogen content as the as-annealed powder, and the ones sintered at 950°C have nitrogen content equivalent to the ones sintered at higher temperatures. Consequently, it can be said that, taking into account the nitrogen content of the specimens sintered at lower temperatures, i.e. 600° and 950°C, MC type carbides are converted into MX carbonitrides mainly after A_{cf} is crossed, i.e. the sintering is carried out in the austenitic field. A black spotted core was observed in great number of MX carbonitrides present in the specimens sintered at 950°C, Figure 3.17 (c) and (d). This feature was not observed in specimens sintered at 600°C, Figure 3.17 (a) and (b), and only very few of the MX carbonitrides present in the specimens sintered at 1120°C showed this feature, Figure 3.17 (f). The size of the MX carbonitrides increases concomitantly with sintering temperature,

this increasing in size being more evident when a critical temperature is crossed, i.e. before A_{cf} , 890°C, they were very tiny <0.5 μm , at T_{os} , 1120°C the carbonitrides are sized <0.5 μm , Figure 3.17 (e). Above this temperature their size increases up to 1-2 μm , and finally their coarser size, up to 3 μm , is attained at the distortion temperature T_d , 1260°C, Figure 3.17 (h). The M_6C tungsten-molybdenum-rich carbides, showed three different globular, rectangular and irregular shapes, Figure 3.17. In the specimens sintered between 600°C and 1120°C the globular M_6C carbides were located mainly at the grain boundaries having sizes <0.5 μm , Figure 3.17 (a). Both M_6C rectangular and irregular morphologies are present in specimens sintered between 1120°C and 1220°C. However in samples sintered above this temperature only irregular shaped M_6C carbides were present. These irregular shaped M_6C carbides were decorated inside with MX vanadium-rich carbonitrides, Figure 3.17 (d) and (h). An irregular shaped chromium-rich carbide was also observed in the grain boundaries, surrounding the MX, as shown in the microprobe x-ray map in Figure 3.18. This carbide was identified as M_3C by electron microprobe analysis, as shown in Table 3.12, and x-ray diffraction, Figure 3.19 and Table 2.5. Although being too small to be positively identified, qualitative EDS analysis showed that this M_3C carbide was also present in specimens sintered at 600°-950°C, Figure 3.20. At these temperatures this phase was similar in size to the MC-MX and M_6C carbides, about 1 μm and had a globular morphology, Figure 3.17 (a) to (d). It can be seen in the Figure 3.18 that in samples sintered at 1140°C chromium was uniformly dispersed all over the microstructure with a few higher concentration sites which suggests the precipitation of this M_3C carbide. In the samples sintered at 1200°C and above, the Cr-rich M_3C type carbide was present in significant amounts, Figures 3.17(g) to (l) and 3.18. In specimens sintered at the distortion temperature, 1260°C, the M_3C carbides tended to adopt a skeletal eutectic morphology, Figure 3.17 (l). At this same temperature, a small number of M_2C carbides were observed within the microstructures, Figure 3.17 (k).

In samples sintered at 950°C and above cooling down resulted in transformation of austenite to give a pearlitic type of transformation., Figure 3.17 (c)-(l), before that temperature the matrix was identified as being ferritic. The matrix microhardness of the specimens sintered at 1200°C was in the range 450-580 HV0.05.

As the nitrogen atmosphere sintered specimens showed different microstructure features when compared with the ones sintered in vacuum, a different criteria was necessary to define the optimal sintering temperature (OST). In fact, as the atmosphere sintered specimens show continuous M_6C and M_3C carbides films at the grain boundaries in the sintering plateau, the criteria used for the vacuum sintered samples was unsuitable. Instead, the OST was defined as a temperature 5-10°C above T_m , at which no (or very little) porosity was observed, upper limit being the maximum temperature at which no eutectic carbides were observed. Hence, the optimum sintering temperature for nitrogen sintered P68 was 1200°C, 60°C below the optimum one for vacuum sintered samples. The sintering window is, therefore, wider for the $N_2 + 7\% H_2$ atmosphere sintered specimens than in vacuum, i.e. 30°C instead of 10°C in vacuum.

The x-ray diffraction patterns of the specimens, sintered in the $N_2 + 7\% H_2$ atmosphere at 600°, 950°, 1120°C, 1200°C and 1250°C are shown in Figure 3.19. Besides the MC carbide peaks already found for the vacuum sintered specimens, M_6C carbide peaks were also observed. The peaks corresponding to M_3C carbides which are in the range 40°-50°, overlap the M_6C ones with the same values. Because of this overlapping, the most intense M_6C peak, which corresponds to $2\theta = 42^\circ$ is oversized compared to the relative intensity of this phase in the data file [191]. The diffraction patterns of all the present phases, were slightly leftwards shifted, but maintaining their relative positions. Figure 3.20

shows the SEM EDS qualitative analysis of the different phases present in P68 specimens sintered at different temperatures.

The oxygen and nitrogen contents of the as-sintered P68 powder specimens are shown in Table 3.7. The average nitrogen content for this alloy composition was 1.2 wt% and showed little variations with temperature along the sintering curve. However, specimens sintered in the ferritic field, at 600°C, had much lower nitrogen content ≈ 0.06 wt%, Table 3.1, i.e. similar to the as-annealed powder. The same happened with the oxygen content, which was about 0.09 wt% along all the sintering temperature range. As nitrogen was found only in the MX carbonitrides, and as the P68 nitrogen content was constant through the sintering temperature range, this suggested that the MX volume fraction was also constant for this alloy, though their size increases concomitantly with temperature. In fact, evaluation of the MX carbonitrides volume fraction showed that its value was 8.5% for specimens sintered at 1180°C and 8.8% for samples sintered at 1200°C.

The MC/MX type vanadium-rich carbides present in the specimens sintered at temperatures above 1180°C were sometimes cored, the average atomic number contrast varied from centre to periphery, e.g. Figure 3.17(k) and (l). For particles located within the prior austenite grains (i.e. not inside other carbides), they were surrounded by a white layer, as shown in Figures 3.17 (k) and (l) and 3.21 (a) for the specimen sintered at 1260°C, indicating that heavier elements such as tungsten or molybdenum, were present in these zones. In addition the average atomic number contrast of MC/MX carbides varied depending on their location within the microstructure. Dark MC/MX particles embedded in M_6C or M_3C carbides or at the prior austenite grain boundaries whereas ones located in the within the prior austenite grains were lighter, Figure 3.21 (b).

3.4.2.2-THE EFFECT OF TIME AND TEMPERATURE ON SINTERING OF P68

The variation in sintered density with both time and temperature for P68 specimens sintered and quenched is given in Table 3.8. These data are plotted in Figure 3.22, and the microstructural features are shown in Figure 3.23. As can be seen in Figure 3.22, an overall density increase, concomitant with sintering time was observed for all sintering temperatures but 1200° and 1240°C. At these two sintering temperatures, maximum density (8.2 g/ cm³) was already attained after 5 minutes. Irregular shaped porosity was observed in all the specimens sintered at 1240°C. The matrix of all the specimens was martensite, as a consequence of the quenching from the sintering temperature.

The microstructure of the specimens sintered at 1120°C, Figure 3.23 (a) 5 minutes, (b) 60 minutes and (c) 360 minutes, show porosity, as expected, globular vanadium-rich MC/MX (0.5-1 µm), globular chromium-rich M₃C sized 1-3 µm, being the coarsest carbide found in samples sintered for 5 minutes, globular M₆C carbides whose size was less than 1 µm for the specimens sintered for 5 minutes, its size increasing concomitantly with sintering time, reaching about 4 µm after 6 hours, its shape being irregular. In addition a few grain boundary rod shaped M₆C carbides were observed, especially in specimens sintered for 6 hours, Figure 3.23 (c). The M₃C carbides were located at the grain boundaries, whilst the MC/MX and M₆C carbides were located either inside the grains or at the grain boundaries. Also, some rows of vanadium-rich carbides/carbonitrides were observed at the prior powder particle boundaries, generally linked with what was on the basis of the contrast level to be an oxide, Figure 3.24. No carbide clustering was observed, even in the specimens sintered for 6 hours.

Specimens sintered at 1150°C, Figure 3.23 (d) 5 minutes, (e) 60 minutes and (f) 360 minutes, possessed microstructures composed of globular vanadium-rich MC/MX, globular, rod shaped and irregular M₆C. Small amounts of irregular chromium-rich M₃C

carbides were observed only in the specimens sintered for 5 minutes. The MC/MX particles were observed mainly at the grain boundaries, especially for sintering times above 5 minutes, after which they started to cluster. An evident coarsening of the M_6C carbides concomitantly with sintering time was observed, the globular shaped morphology being replaced by a rod shaped morphology, especially after 30 minutes sintering time. Round porosity was observed in all the specimens. Even for the longer sintering times, grain growth was not evident, being smaller than 10 μm .

In P68 specimens sintered at 1200°C, Figure 3.23 (g), (h) and (i), the microstructure was composed of vanadium-rich MC/MX particles, which were located mainly at the grain boundaries forming clusters (the clusters increasing their size with sintering time), individual particles sized 0.5 up to 3 μm their size increasing slightly with sintering time; a small amount of irregular chromium-rich M_3C present amongst the MC/MX at the grain boundaries in samples sintered for 5 minutes; M_6C which showed three morphologies: globular (higher amount for sintering times up to 30 minutes) and located mainly at the grain boundaries, rod shaped, located at the grain boundaries—very few were observed at 5 and 30 minutes sintering times, and irregular, sometimes decorated with MX and located at the grain boundaries as well. As a consequence of the quenching, the matrix was mainly martensite, typical acicular grains could be observed. Unlike the specimens sintered for 5 minutes, where high carbide precipitation was observed within the grains, the specimens sintered for 6 hours show very little intragranular precipitation. Very little porosity was observed, its size and volume fraction decreasing for longer sintering times. At this sintering temperature and for sintering times greater than 30 minutes, the grain growth was evident. Though the grain size was not homogeneous, the bigger ones could attain about 30 μm , Figure 3.23(g), (h) and (i).

Microstructures of the specimens sintered at 1240°C, are shown in Figure 3.23 (j) 5 minutes, (k) 60 minutes and (l) 360 minutes. At this temperature microstructures exhibited irregular porosity, typical of oversintered samples, very little intragranular carbide precipitation, MC/MX clusters at the grain boundaries, sometimes decorating the very few observed irregular M_6C carbides. The MC/MX carbides/carbonitrides size increased with sintering time from $<1 \mu\text{m}$ after 5 minutes sintering time to about $3 \mu\text{m}$ following sintering for 6 hours. For sintering times greater than 30 minutes, the MX clusters were about $10 \mu\text{m}$ across. The M_2C eutectic carbide was observed in all the specimens sintered at this temperature, some of them being decorated with MX carbonitrides. At this sintering temperature, sintering times greater than 5 minutes resulted in grain growth, though this was not homogeneous, the bigger ones attaining $\approx 40 \mu\text{m}$, Figure 3.23(j) to (l). No M_3C carbides were observed in these specimens sintered at 1240°C.

Nitrogen contents of samples sintered for different combinations of time and temperatures are given in Figure 3.25. As can be seen, apart from samples sintered at 1120°C, for the range of times and temperatures studied nitrogen contents were similar. However for the specimens sintered at 1120°C, nitrogen contents were higher. One explanation for this observation might be that as at 1120°C the sintered specimens show low density, i.e. high porosity, some gas may have trapped inside the pores, affecting the analysis results.

3.4.3 - THE DISCUSSION OF THE EFFECT OF VANADIUM AND CARBON CONTENTS ON ATMOSPHERE SINTERING BEHAVIOUR

The effect of different vanadium and carbon contents on atmosphere sintering behaviour was studied using the powders listed in Table 3.9. Different graphite amounts

were added in order to improve the sinterability of some powders, taking into account their actual carbon and also the oxygen contents, i.e. extra graphite was added in all cases according to the oxygen content of the “as-annealed” powders. The first graphite addition was made to the powders P72 to P75, up to an actual carbon content of 1.6 wt%. As this carbon content didn’t drop the T_m temperature to temperatures below 1180°C (that is the T_m temperature for P68 when sintered in a nitrogen-rich atmosphere), further carbon additions were tried. To determine the optimal carbon content for each powder, the Greetham expression [128] was used. This expression takes into account the tungsten equivalent (CWE) for the calculated carbon content (CCC), all in weight %, as follows:

$$\text{CWE} = \%W + 2 \times \%Mo + 6 \times \%V \quad (3.1)$$

$$\text{CCC} = (\text{CWE}/20) - 0.4 \quad (3.2)$$

So, fifteen different compositions were used in order to investigate the sintering behaviour, P68, the series P72 to P75 with several carbon contents, P77 and P81. All the compositions together with their optimum sintering temperatures (OST) or the temperatures, at which the alloys attained maximum density, are shown in Table 3.9.

The sintering curves, of powders with 6 wt% (P75, P81), 8 wt% (P68, P72, P77), 10 wt% (P73) and 12 wt% vanadium (P74) with different carbon contents sintered in the $N_2+7\%H_2$ atmosphere, are shown in Figure 3.26 and Figure 3.27. Figure 3.26 shows the effect of varying carbon (at constant vanadium content) on the sintering behaviour of the seven powders. In Figure 3.27 the effect of vanadium at constant carbon content is shown. As can be seen in Figure 3.26, for each alloy (or vanadium content) as the carbon content was increased the starting point of the sintering plateau (T_m) decreased though the attained densities are lower and the sintering plateau narrower. The lowest sintering temperatures were attained for the powders with lower vanadium contents, i.e. 6 and 8 wt%, especially

for compositions with carbon contents in excess of 2 wt%, Figure 3.26 (a) and (b). In fact T_m for P81 (6% V/ 2.6% C) was 1130°C, as well as for P77 (8% V/ 2.7% C). Figure 3.26 (a) shows the effect of increasing the carbon content of powders containing 6 wt% V. At a carbon content of 1.6% (P75-1.6% C) sintering above 1180°C resulted in densification with specimens sintered at 1260°C attaining densities of 8.13 g cm⁻³. Sintering at 1300°C resulted in specimen distortion. With increasing carbon content, sintering temperatures were reduced significantly. For example, P81-2.6% C specimens exhibited significant densification on sintering at temperatures above 1100°C, whereas sintering at 1130°C resulted in sintered densities of 8.2 g cm⁻³. In this case, sintering at higher temperatures did not result in specimen distortion until 1180°C. Similar trends were observed for the series of alloys containing 8 wt% V. Again, these alloys sintered to densities of 8-8.2 g cm⁻³ over a range of temperatures 1140°-1300°C. For P77-1.6% C, rapid densification was initiated on sintering at temperatures above 1200°C and the sintering plateau extended from 1260°C to 1320°C. Increasing the carbon content to 2.7% (P77-2.7%) reduced the temperature for initiating sintering to 1100°C, whilst the sintering plateau extended over the range 1130°-1180°C.

The alloys with 10 (P73) and 12 wt% of vanadium (P74) with 1.6% C content only started rapid densification at 1220°C and 1240°C, respectively. T_m for these two alloys was 1260°C for P73 (sintered density being 7.9 g cm⁻³), and 1300°C for P74 (sintered density being 8 g cm⁻³). The distortion temperature for these two compositions was 1320°C. When the carbon content was increased up to 2.4 wt%, the start of rapid densification decreased to 1120°C and 1140°C for P73 and P74, respectively. These powders did attain T_m at 1200°C, (P73) and 1230°C (P74), Figure 3.26 (c) and (d) and Figure 3.27 (c). Sintering at these last temperatures resulted in densities of 7.8 g cm⁻³ for both P73 and P74 alloys. Sintering of P73 (10% V) and P74 (12% V) containing 3.4 and 4 wt% C, respectively, was initiated at

1080°C. However these powders exhibited distortion before attaining total densification, at 1110°C and 1120°C for P74 and P73 respectively, Figure 3.26 (c) and (d), having attained sintered densities of 7.5 and 7.7 g cm⁻³. Thus there was a limit to the amount of carbon which could be added without degrading the sintering properties.

Considering the effect of vanadium content, for a given carbon content, it can be seen from Figure 3.27 that increases in vanadium content lead to increases in sintering temperatures.

The microstructures of the undersintered specimens showed levels of high porosity, as expected. Those sintered below T_{os} exhibited open porosity and prior powder particle boundaries could still be seen. Typical microstructures are shown in Figure 3.17 (e) for P68 alloy sintered at 1120°C. In these specimens sintered close to T_{os} the prior particle boundaries were decorated with oxides and MX rows, Figure 3.28 (e), this type of microstructural features having already been observed in the vacuum sintered specimens, Figure 3.9 (e). The carbides present at the undersintered specimens with C content in excess of 1.6 wt% were vanadium-rich MC/MX-type, chromium-rich M_3C and tungsten-molybdenum-rich M_6C -type, as shown in Figure 3.28. All these carbides were globular with sizes in the range 1-4 μm . In the case of higher carbon alloys (3.4 wt% C-P73 and 4 wt% C-P74) M_3C carbides were larger, as shown in Figure 3.28(c) and (i). In respect to the alloys with 1.6 wt% C, M_3C carbides were absent from all compositions, Figure 3.28(d) apart of P75 (1.6C-6V), Figure 3.28(b).

The specimens sintered at the T_{os} temperatures showed microstructures similar to the ones sintered at lower temperatures: irregular M_6C carbides located mainly at the grain boundaries, and globular MC/MX dispersed uniformly, though those located at the grain

boundaries were sometimes present as rows. Typical microstructures shown in Figure 3.17 (e) and (f) for the P68 composition.

Figure 3.29 (a), (b), (c) and (d) shows the microstructural evolution with carbon and vanadium contents, at the optimal sintering temperatures (OST), as defined previously for the $N_2+7\%H_2$ sintered specimens. The different alloys have been grouped taking into account their vanadium content. Hence, Figure 3.29 (a) shows the microstructures of the alloys with 6 wt% vanadium content with carbon content of 1.6, 2.0, 2.2 and 2.7 wt%. Figure 3.29 (b) shows the alloys with 8 wt% vanadium content and carbon content of 1.6, 2.0, 2.4 and 2.6 wt%. Figure 3.29 (c) shows the alloys with 10 wt% vanadium content and carbon content of 1.6, 2.4 and 3.4 wt%. Finally, Figure 3.29 (d) shows the alloys with 12 wt% vanadium content and carbon content of 1.6, 2.4 and 4 wt%.

Concerning the microstructural evolution of the sintered powders, it can be observed that the alloys with 1.6 wt% C content show grain boundary precipitation of irregular tungsten/molybdenum-rich M_6C carbides decorated with globular vanadium-rich MX carbonitrides (Table 3.12), sized 1-3 μm . Within the prior austenite grains little precipitation was observed. Intra granular phases were mainly MC/MX though the acicular shape of some carbides suggested that they were M_2C but they could not be analysed due to their small size. Since the OST's are higher for the alloys with lower carbon content (e.g. 1.6 wt%), the microstructures exhibited features found in oversintered structures, i.e. continuous irregular M_6C tungsten-rich carbide films at grain boundaries, Figure 3.29 (a1), (b1), (c1) and (d1). The MX carbonitrides precipitated mainly at grain boundaries and within the M_6C , their amount increasing with increasing vanadium content, see Table 3.11 and Figure 3.30.

For the alloys with carbon contents of 2 wt% and higher, in addition to MX and M_6C a chromium-rich carbide was also observed. This was identified by x-ray diffraction as M_3C , Table 2.5, a phase observed in P68, P77 and P81 samples sintered at temperatures in the range 600-950°C, Figure 3.17 (a) to (d). At higher sintering temperatures, i.e. above T_{os} , this carbide precipitated at the grain boundaries and was often decorated with MX carbonitrides. M_3C carbide was a rare feature in some of the sintered specimens with lower carbon content (1.6 wt%). The volume fraction and particle size of the M_3C carbide increased with increasing carbon content, especially for the alloys with vanadium content of 10 and 12 wt%, and 3.4 and 4 wt% carbon, where they were coarse, ($>10\mu m$). This feature is shown for the P74 alloy (12 wt% V/ 4 wt% C) sintered at 1100°C, Figure 3.31. This temperature was the one at which this composition attained its highest density, though there is still porosity, higher temperatures resulted in distortion. In the microprobe X-ray maps shown in Figure 3.31, the M_6C tungsten-rich carbides, MX vanadium-rich carbonitrides and M_3C -type chromium-rich carbide can be identified.

Microstructures of all the alloys containing 2 wt% carbon and higher, were contained M_3C , M_6C and MC/MX phases. An observation that can be seen in Figure 3.29, is that the MX S.E.M. contrast decreased clearer with increasing alloy carbon content, for the same nominal vanadium content. This can suggest that when carbon was increased, MX carbonitrides could contain less light elements (such as nitrogen) which are the ones with darker S.E.M. contrast. In fact, as it will be reported below, the nitrogen content of the alloys decreased with increasing carbon content, for the same vanadium content.

Figure 3.29(e) shows typical microstructures at T_d . MX carbonitrides were present in all microstructures general with a typical globular morphology, but in alloys with the lowest carbon content, i.e. P72-1.6%C and P74-1.6%C, MX became faceted, Figure 3.29(e2) and (e3). M_6C eutectic was also present in all microstructures, M_2C eutectic being

observed in the higher carbon containing alloys. Typical microstructures shown in Figure 3.29(e1) and (e4). Distortion temperatures for the alloys possessing 3.4 and 4 wt% C, i.e. P73 and P74, coincided with their T_m temperatures, shown in Figure 3.29(c3) and (d3), large amounts of M_3C carbides being observed. Microprobe x-ray maps are shown in Figure 3.31.

The nitrogen content evolution of these powder specimens with several carbon and vanadium contents is shown in Table 3.10. These analyses were carried out in specimens sintered at the optimum sintering temperature (OST). Figure 3.32 shows a three dimensional graph of the nitrogen-vanadium-carbon relation at the OST (shown in Table 3.10). As can be seen, a decrease of the nitrogen content was observed when carbon is increased. On the other hand, the nitrogen content increased with increasing vanadium content. The variation in volume fraction of the MX carbonitrides with the carbon and vanadium content of some alloys (those where it was possible to make the counting, due to sufficient different grey contrast level to allow discriminate the MX from the other phases in S.E.M. images, i.e. P75-6%V-1.6%C, P68-8%V-2.4%C, P74-12%V-1.6 and 2.4%C) is shown in Table 3.11 and in Figure 3.30. It can be seen that the MX carbonitrides volume fraction decreases with increasing carbon content, and increases with vanadium content.

Hence, plotting the observations made above, Figure 3.33, about the effect of the carbon content on T_{os} , T_m and T_d temperatures, keeping the vanadium content unchanged, a consistent decrease of these temperatures was observed when carbon is increased. Increasing the vanadium content (keeping carbon constant), the referred to temperatures do not decrease, and in the majority of the cases they even increase, as shown in Figure 3.34. The combined effect of vanadium and carbon content on these characteristic sintering temperatures is shown in Figure 3.35.

Contrarily to vacuum sintered specimens, which exhibited edge rounding when distorted, distortion of nitrogen sintered specimens was associated with surface blistering, possibly as a consequence of the excess amount of liquid and perhaps high rate of gas release. This is illustrated in Figure 3.36 (a) for the P72 alloy (8V/2.0C) sintered at 1270°C. Herringbone γ -M₆C eutectics was also surrounding pores caused by distortion, Figure 3.36 (b). Distortion was associated to the formation of several eutectic carbides. The low carbon (1.6 wt%) alloys showed solely γ -M₆C eutectics, Figure 3.29 (e2) and (e3), whilst needle-like γ -M₂C eutectic was observed at the alloys with higher carbon content Figure 3.29 (e1) and (e4). A γ -M₃C eutectic was also perceived in the alloys with carbon contents in excess 2 wt%, as shown for the P75 alloy in Figure 3.29(e1). In Figure 3.29(e1) the γ -M₂C eutectic can be seen decomposing into M₆C and MC/MX, though these last ones were not so evident.

3.5 - DIFFERENTIAL THERMAL ANALYSIS (D.T.A.)

The plots of the D.T.A. runs, on heating, of the “as-annealed” powders P68 (8V/2.2C), P74 (12V/4C), P77 (6V/2.7C) and P81 (8V/2.6C) are shown in Figure 3.37. Figure 3.37 (a) shows the plots of the runs carried out in an argon atmosphere, and Figure 3.37 (b) the ones performed under a nitrogen atmosphere.

For the DTA runs performed under argon, it can be seen that the $\alpha \rightarrow \gamma$ transformation took place in the temperature range 840°-890°C for all the tested powders but P74, this transformation being not observed. The determined *solidus* are 1138°C for P77, 1220°C for P68, 1140°C for P81 and 1110°C for P74. This last alloy showed liquation

of M_3C carbides at about 1140°C, this transformation was not observed for the other compositions.

Concerning the DTA runs performed under nitrogen atmosphere, it can be seen that for the P68, P77 and P81 powders, the $\alpha \rightarrow \gamma$ transformations take place in the same temperature range as for the argon runs, i.e. between 840° and 890°C. For P74, the $\alpha \rightarrow \gamma$ transformation was not observed once more. With regard to the *solidus* temperatures it can be seen that these are decreased for the cycles performed under nitrogen, when compared with the ones performed under argon. In fact the determined *solidus* were 1100°C for P77, 1130°C for P68, 1105°C for P81 and 1100°C for P74, this last one being similar to the one determined under argon. All the alloys except P68 showed liquation of M_3C carbides at about 1130°C for P77 and P81, and 1118°C for the P74 composition.

3.6 - HEAT TREATMENT

3.6.1 - HARDENING

Vacuum sintered P68 samples used in the heat treatments were sintered at 1260°C, whilst $N_2+7\%H_2$ atmosphere sintered samples were sintered at 1200°C, 1150°C and 1150°C for the P68, P77 and P81 compositions, respectively. All samples were sintered for 1 hour. The hardness values of P68 (both vacuum and atmosphere sintered), P77 and P81 (atmosphere sintered) in the as-quenched condition for different austenitising temperatures are listed in Tables 3.13 and 3.14 and plotted in Figures 3.38 and 3.39. For each powder, hardness decreased with increasing autenisation temperature. For example, for the vacuum sintered P68 alloy, the hardness dropped from 913 ± 14 down to 876 ± 10 when the quenching temperature was raised from 1100°C to 1200°C, respectively. For the nitrogen atmosphere

sintered alloys, similar trends were observed: for the P77 alloy, hardness dropped from 914 ± 32 down to 814 ± 36 when the quenching temperature was raised by only 25°C , from 1050°C to 1075°C . In the case of P81 alloy, the hardness reduction was smaller, decreasing from 800 ± 34 to 766 ± 44 for the same austenitising temperatures as P77. The nitrogen sintered P68 alloy that was quenched from 1100°C showed similar hardness values for both under-sintered at 1180°C and HIPped, and fully-sintered at 1200°C specimens, i.e. 763 ± 8 and 777 ± 8 , respectively.

After quenching, the microstructures of all the specimens had a martensitic matrix ($840\text{-}960\text{ HV }0.05$) in which the carbides were uniformly distributed. Figure 3.38 shows the as-quenched microstructures of vacuum sintered P68 specimens. The carbides observed in the as-quenched microstructure of vacuum sintered P68 were MC vanadium-rich carbides and small amounts of M_6C tungsten-molybdenum-rich carbide (in the specimens austenitised at both 1100° and 1150°C), as shown by the x-rays diffraction patterns in Figure 3.40. MC/MX, M_3C ($\approx 1\ \mu\text{m}$) and M_6C were all present in the as-quenched microstructures of the $\text{N}_2+7\%\text{H}_2$ atmosphere sintered specimens. As it can be seen in the microprobe x-ray maps, for $\text{N}_2+7\%\text{H}_2$ atmosphere sintered P68, Figure 3.41, the chromium-rich M_3C carbides almost dissolve completely during austenisation, its size being about $1\ \mu\text{m}$, and was distributed amongst the MX carbonitrides.

3.6.2 - TEMPERING

The secondary hardening response for each of the austenitising temperatures of the specimens sintered both in vacuum and nitrogen-rich atmosphere, was evaluated by hardness measurements. The tempering curves of these powders are shown in Figure 3.42 and Figure 3.43. As can be seen, in Figure 3.42 (a), the higher the austenitising temperature the higher the hardness of the triple tempered P68 vacuum sintered specimens, as expected [1,136]. The specimens quenched from the lower austenitising temperature (1100°C) showed no significant secondary hardening peak hardness.

Regarding the P68 specimens sintered in the $N_2+7\%H_2$ atmosphere, they showed a peak hardness value – 1040-1050 HV30 – about 7% higher than the vacuum sintered specimens at a tempering temperature of 525°C. The other two alloys sintered in the nitrogen atmosphere, P77 and P81, did not show such high hardness values. The peak hardness was 966 HV30 at 475°C for both austenitising temperatures of P77, and 927 and 950 HV30 for P81 specimens quenched from 1050° and 1075°C respectively, Figure 3.43.

The typical microstructures of the quenched and triple tempered vacuum and $N_2+7\%H_2$ atmosphere sintered specimens, are shown in Figure 3.44. Concerning the P68 alloy sintered in a $N_2+7\%H_2$ atmosphere, quenched from 1100°C and tempered at 550°C (3 x 1 hour), some chromium-rich carbide were observed, sized 1-4 μm (this feature being already observed in the “as-quenched” specimens, Figure 3.41), and the majority of the M_6C carbides were not decorated with MX carbonitrides (as they were in the as-sintered specimens), these last ones appearing scattered in the matrix and forming rows in the grain boundaries. This suggests that part of the M_6C carbides that enveloped them before the heat treatment, have dissolved during austenisation, Figure 3.44 (a). Typical quenched and triple tempered microstructures for the P77 and P81 compositions are shown in Figure 3.44 (b)

and (c) respectively. In these alloys some MX clusters can be seen at the grain boundaries, frequently linked by chromium-rich M_3C carbides.

3.7 - MECHANICAL TESTS

3.7.1 - THREE-POINT BENDING TESTS

Fracture strength, transverse rupture strength (TRS), was determined by three-point bending tests, using the procedures described in section 2.5.3. The values obtained for bend strength and hardness of fully hardened specimens sintered in both vacuum and atmosphere are shown in Tables 3.15 and 3.16.

The vacuum sintered P68 specimens showed a decrease in bend strength from 2297 ± 87 MPa to 2049 ± 78 MPa when the austenitising temperature was increased from 1100° to 1200°C , for a similar final hardness, Table 3.15. For the specimens quenched from 1150°C the highest average TRS value was attained, 2384 ± 118 , though this value showed wider scatter when compared with the remaining specimens shown in Table 3.15. The highest individual TRS value among all specimens was attained for a specimen quenched from 1150°C and was 2735 MPa, whilst the lowest was obtained for a specimen quenched from 1200°C and was 1768 MPa.

The failure initiating sites of the P68 vacuum sintered specimens were found to be pores, Figure 3.45, located at or beneath the tensile surface. Examination of tensile faces revealed cracked carbides (MC) located close ($< 50 \mu\text{m}$) to the fracture surface, Figure 3.45. Nevertheless, occasionally cracked carbides were found about 1 mm away from the fracture surface, these were located close to pores, Figure 3.45.

When sintered in nitrogen-rich atmosphere, the P68 alloy showed slightly lower bend strength, 2082 ± 114 MPa, for the same quenching temperature, 1100°C , and similar hardness levels, compared to the vacuum sintered alloy, Table 3.16. The highest individual TRS value for the P68 nitrogen sintered specimens was 2298 MPa and the lowest was 1818 MPa, both obtained for undersintered and HIPed specimens.

The P77 and P81 alloys showed lower bend strength, ≈ 1800 - 1900 MPa, when compared with the P68 alloy sintered either in vacuum or nitrogen. The highest TRS value among the P77 specimens was 2102 MPa and was obtained for a HIPed specimen quenched from 1075°C and tempered at 540°C , whilst the lowest was 1641 MPa for a specimen quenched from 1075°C and tempered at 475°C . Concerning to the P81 alloy specimens, the highest single TRS value was 2151 MPa, for a HIPed specimen quenched from 1075°C and tempered at 460°C , whilst the lowest was 1622 MPa for a HIPed sample quenched from 1075 and tempered at 530°C .

Failure initiation sites of atmosphere sintered specimens were found to be not only pores, as found for the vacuum sintered specimens, but also poor bonding particle boundaries, inclusions and surface collapse, as shown in Figure 3.46. This figure shows the typical failure initiation sites for all the specimens sintered in nitrogen-rich atmosphere. Figure 3.46 (a) shows the typical pore failure, the pores being located at the tensile face, while Figure 3.46 (b) shows a poor bonding particle boundaries, this zones showing Si-containing areas, as shown on the EDS analysis. The different inclusions identified as failure sources, contained Si (probably SiO_2) shown in Figure 3.46 (c) and Al, Si and Ca, which is shown in Figure 3.46 (d). Surface collapse containing no obvious flaw was also observed in some specimens, Figure 3.46 (e).

3.7.2 - HOT ISOSTATIC PRESSING

The bend strength was not sensitive to the HIP treatment, the non-HIPped specimens having bend strength very close to the HIPped ones, Table 3.16. Failure initiation sites observed in HIPped samples were identical to those observed for the non-HIPped specimens and shown in Figure 3.46.

TABLE 3.1 – Chemical Analysis (wt%) of the Powders, As-atomised and As-annealed

Element	P68		P75		P72		P73		P74		P77		P81	
	atom.	anneal.												
C	2.38	2.22	0.82	0.52	0.88	0.63	0.78	0.55	0.83	0.62	2.95	2.73	2.72	2.64
V	8.1		5.8		8.0		9.1		10.6		7.2		5.9	
W	9.1		8.9		9.1		9.7		9.1		9.2		8.8	
Mo	3.1		3.6		3.1		2.8		3.2		3.7		3.2	
Cr	4.0		3.3		3.6		3.3		3.5		4.4		3.8	
Co	9.4		9.1		7.0		8.5		8.3		9.2		9.5	
O	0.24	0.12	0.60	0.22	0.66	0.32	0.76	0.40	0.93	0.62	0.23	0.12	0.15	0.04
N	0.058	0.058	0.06	0.06	0.08	0.08	0.11	0.11	0.17	0.17	0.034	0.034	0.039	0.039

Table 3.2 – Atomisation Parameters

POWDER		P68	P75	P72	P73	P74	P77	P81
Temperature of Melt [°C] maximum	Furnace	1740	1718	1771	1750	1740	1735	1720
	Atomiser Tundish	1583	1645	1638	1633	1645	1632	1566
Metal Flow Time [sec]		100	110	90	109	50	78	66
Amount of melt in Furnace [kg]		14	10	11	10.5	10	12	10
Amount of Powder [kg]		8.05	7.84	8.21	9.78	5.20	11.4	8.96
Metal Flow [kg/min.]		4.83	4.28	5.47	5.22	6.24	8.7	8.15
Water/Metal flow (main nozzles)		5.38	6.07	4.75	4.98	4.17	2.99	3.19
Gas over the Melt (furnace)		argon						
Atmosphere inside the Atomiser		argon						
Settling Time [min.]		60	60	60	60	60	60	60
Filtration		yes						
Vacuum Drying at 80°C [hours]		28	24	24	24	24	24	24

Table 3.3 – Sieve Analysis of the As-atomised Powders

	P68	P75	P72	P73	P74	P77	P81
Particle Size Distribution [µm]	%						
+800	8.4	1.04	1.0	1.93	2.84	0.0	0.81
-800/+250	22.53	5.85	9.3	9.19	11.32	0.55	12.17
-250/+200	7.30	4.54	6.7	6.07	7.66	2.00	5.46
-200/+125	15.36	17.31	20.2	17.70	16.86	8.28	15.76
-125/+90	14.12	15.38	17.4	18.06	16.59	12.40	15.03
-90/+63	11.79	17.19	18.1	18.66	14.72	20.10	19.05
-63/+45	8.21	14.81	10.2	14.24	15.60	18.62	14.22
-45/+36	6.22	12.08	3.7	7.77	6.02	21.33	6.09
-36	6.07	11.8	13.4	6.38	8.39	16.72	11.41
Mean Particle Size [µm]	140	90	98	94	98	58	88
Standar Deviation	3	1.94	2.14	2.23	2.45	1.8	2.22
Yield (wt% <125µm fraction)	46.4	71.3	62.8	65.1	61.3	89.2	65.8
Particle Size Distribution of the <125 µm fraction [µm]	P68	P75	P72	P73	P74	P77	P81
	%						
-125/+90	30.42	21.57	27.7	27.74	27.06	13.9	22.84
-90/+63	25.41	24.11	28.82	28.66	24.01	22.53	28.95
-63/+45	17.70	20.77	16.24	21.87	25.45	20.87	21.61
-45/+36	13.38	16.94	5.89	11.94	9.82	23.91	9.26
-36	13.08	16.55	21.34	9.8	13.69	18.74	17.34

Table 3.4 – Dilatometric Tests Results (Heating Rate= 10°C.min⁻¹)

POWDER	P68	P75	P72	P73	P74	P77	P81
Ac _i [°C]	860	-	820	820	-	840	805
Ac _f [°C]	900	-	860	850	-	865	840

Table 3.5 – Physical Properties of the As-annealed Powders

POWDER	P68	P75	P72	P73	P74	P77	P81
Apparent density [g/cm ³]	1.17	1.58	1.57	1.52	1.44	2.10	2.47
Tap density [g/cm ³]	2.23	2.59	2.33	2.90	2.25	2.90	3.9
Flowing rate [s/50g]	61 ±1	none	none	none	none	none	none
Compressibility/density at 700MPa [g/cm ³]	5.58	6.15	6.01	5.79	5.74	5.72	5.73

**TABLE 3.6 – P68 Vacuum Sintered MC Carbide and Austenite Grain Size Ranges at Different Sintering Temperatures
Oxygen Content Shown for OST**

Sint. Temp. [°C]	MC [µm]	Grain [µm]	O [wt%]	N [wt%]
1210	1-2	<4	*	*
1240	1-4	4-20		
1250	1-8	5-35		
1260	1-10	10-50	0.035	0.04
1270	1-15	10-55	*	*
1280	1-20	20-60		

• - not analysed

TABLE 3.7 – Oxygen and Nitrogen Contents of P68 Specimens Sintered in a N₂ + H₂ Atmosphere at Different Temperatures

°C	O ₂ %	N ₂ %
600	*	0.06
950	*	1.26
1140	0.092	1.32
1160	0.099	1.25
1170	0.095	1.21
1180	0.094	1.15
1190	0.089	1.23
1200	0.090	1.20
1220	0.092	1.10
1240	0.072	1.25
1260	0.094	1.26

• - not analysed

**TABLE 3.8 – P68 Densities Upon Sintering at Different Times and Temperatures,
Followed by Oil Quenching
(nitrogen content analysed where indicated)**

Sintering Temp. [°C]	Time [min]	Density [g/cm³]	Wt% N
1120	5	6.06	1.44
	30	6.25	-
	60	6.24	1.4
	180	6.36	-
	360	6.37	1.86
1130	5	6.41	-
	30	6.48	-
	60	6.60	-
	180	6.69	-
	360	6.96	-
1140	5	6.60	-
	30	6.68	-
	60	6.78	-
	180	6.99	-
	360	6.81	-
1150	5	6.44	-
	30	6.62	-
	60	6.85	-
	180	6.93	-
	360	6.95	-
1180	5	7.45	-
	30	7.82	-
	60	7.90	-
	180	8.04	-
	360	8.06	-
1200	5	8.20	1.38
	30	8.21	-
	60	8.25	1.45
	180	8.21	-
	360	8.20	1.51
1240	5	8.23	1.39
	30	8.18	-
	60	8.19	1.48
	180	8.16	-
	360	8.12	1.54

TABLE 3.9 - Alloys used in atmosphere sintering trials (OST is shown)

V (wt%)	Carbon Content (wt%)							
	1.6	2.0	2.2	2.4	2.6	2.7	3.4	4.0
6	P75 1280°C	P75 1220°C	P75 1170°C	-	-	P77 1150°C	-	-
8	P72 1280°C	P72 1240°C	P72 1230°C	P68 1200°C	P81 1150°C	-	-	-
10	P73 1280°C	-	-	P73 1220°C	-	-	P73 1110°C*	-
12	P74 1300°C	-	-	P74 1250°C	-	-	-	P74 1100°C*

*- Total densification was not possible to be attained

TABLE 3.10 – Effect of Vanadium and Carbon on the Nitrogen Content of Specimens Sintered in a N₂ + H₂ Atmosphere at the OST

Alloy	C (wt%)	V (wt%)	N (wt%)	O (wt%)	OST [°C]
P75	1.6	6	1.12	0.077	1280
P72		8	1.54	0.100	1280
P73		10	1.95	0.125	1280
P74		12	2.42	0.157	1300
P75	2.0	6	1.06	0.098	1220
P72		8	1.47	0.146	1240
P68	2.4	8	1.20	0.090	1200
P73		10	1.70	0.190	1220
P74		12	2.09	0.230	1250
P81	2.6	8	0.76	0.029	1150
P77	2.7	6	0.92	0.137	1150
P73	3.4	10	1.7	0.222	1110
P74	4.0	12	1.9	0.310	1100

TABLE 3.11 – MX Volume Fraction, Carbon and Nitrogen Content of Specimens Sintered in N₂ + 7%H₂ Atmosphere

Alloy	OST [°C]	MX (Vol. Fraction)	C (wt%)	N (wt%)
6V (P75)	1280	9.5	1.6	1.12
12V (P74)	1300	13.8	1.6	2.42
8V (P68)	1200	8.8	2.4	1.2
12V (P74)	1250	12.8	2.4	2.09

TABLE 3.12 a) – Microprobe Analysis of the Different Phases Present in the Alloys which compositions are 1.6C-8V/12V and 2.4C-8V/12V Specimens Sintered at Both T_{os} and OST in a N_2+H_2 Atmosphere []**

Alloy	Sint. Temp. [°C]	phase	Element (At %)							
			C	N	V	Cr	Fe	Co	Mo	W
1.6C 8V	1280	V(CN)	9.74	36.5	47.6	4.31	0.8	0.12	0.46	0.45
		M ₆ C	12.6	0.98	3.63	4.90	38.7	5.44	10.6	23.2
		matrix dark	3.49	0.74	0.76	4.22	78.7	10.4	0.77	0.97
		matrix clear	2.81	0.79	1.22	4.73	78.1	1.00	0.99	1.32
1.6C 12V	1300	V(CN)	7.29	40.1	47.7	3.79	0.54	0.11	0.30	0.23
		M ₆ C	13.5	0.90	4.04	5.29	37.5	5.85	12.0	21.0
		matrix	1.39	0.79	1.93	4.35	78.1	11.2	1.00	1.21
		-								
2.4C 8V	1200	V(CN)	20.1	17.2	49	6.4	1.8	0.2	1.7	3.5
		M ₆ C	19.9	-	3.1	3.8	35.7	5.6	9.5	22.6
		matrix	9.1	-	0.7	3.5	74.8	10.2	0.7	1.1
		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1260	V(CN)	20.7	17.7	52.1	6.6	0.9	0.1	0.7	1.1
		M ₆ C	22.1	-	2.7	4.4	35.2	5.3	10.5	19.9
		M ₃ C	33.8	-	3.6	17.3	37.7	2.3	3.1	2.1
		matrix	5.2	-	1.25	3.3	78.1	10.4	0.8	1.0
2.4C 12V	1120	V(CN)*	10.9	29.3	21.0	2.95	32.3	2.84	0.30	0.38
		M ₆ C	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		M ₃ C	26.9	0.01	4.58	21.4	41.1	2.65	2.24	1.14
		matrix	10.1	0.43	3.80	16.9	56.7	8.60	2.28	1.23
	1250	V(CN)	13.2	32.6	47.1	4.22	1.38	0.16	0.63	0.67
		M ₆ C	13.6	0.24	4.73	4.67	38.5	6.07	10.3	22.0
		M ₃ C	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		matrix	4.81	0.46	1.31	4.29	76.8	10.8	0.73	0.80

*- Indicative Analysis due to phase dimensions

“-“ – Not analysed

[**] – Analysis carried out at INPG (France)

TABLE 3.12 b) – Microprobe Analysis of the Different Phases Present in the Alloys which compositions are 1.6C-8V/12V and 2.4C-8V/12V Specimens Sintered at Both T_{os} and OST in a N_2+H_2 Atmosphere []**

Alloy	Sint. Temp. [°C]	phase	Element (wt %)							
			C	N	V	Cr	Fe	Co	Mo	W
1.6C 8V	1280	V(CN)	3.4	14.8	70.2	6.5	1.3	0.2	1.3	2.4
		M ₆ C	1.8	0.2	2.2	3.0	25.9	3.8	12.1	50.9
		matrix dark	0.8	0.2	0.7	3.9	78.9	11.0	1.3	3.2
		matrix clear	0.7	0.2	1.2	4.8	85.4	1.2	1.9	4.7
1.6C 12V	1300	V(CN)	2.6	16.6	71.8	5.8	0.9	0.2	0.9	1.2
		M ₆ C	2.0	0.2	2.5	3.4	25.9	4.3	14.2	47.6
		matrix	0.3	0.2	1.7	4.0	76.7	11.6	1.7	3.9
		-								
2.4C 8V	1200	V(CN)	5.7	5.7	59.0	7.9	2.4	0.3	3.9	15.2
		M ₆ C	3.0	-	2.0	2.5	25.0	4.1	11.4	52.0
		matrix	2	-	0.7	3.4	77.7	11.2	1.2	3.8
		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1260	V(CN)	6.5	6.5	69.3	9.0	1.3	0.2	1.8	5.3
		M ₆ C	3.5	-	1.8	3.0	26.0	4.1	13.3	48.3
		M ₃ C	9.2	-	4.2	20.4	47.7	3.1	6.7	8.7
		matrix	1.1	-	1.1	3.1	78.9	11.1	1.4	3.3
2.4C 12V	1120	V(CN)*	3.4	10.7	27.9	4.0	47.1	4.4	0.8	1.8
		M ₆ C	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		M ₃ C	7.1	0	5.1	24.5	50.5	3.4	4.7	4.6
		matrix	2.3	0.1	3.6	16.5	59.6	9.5	4.1	4.2
	1250	V(CN)	4.5	13.0	68.5	6.3	2.2	0.3	1.7	3.5
		M ₆ C	2.0	0.0	2.9	3.0	26.3	4.4	12.1	49.4
		M ₃ C	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		matrix	1.0	0.1	1.2	4.1	78.1	11.6	1.3	2.7

*- Indicative Analysis due to phase dimensions

“-“ – Not analysed

[**] – Analysis carried out at INPG (France)

TABLE 3.13 – Hardness (HV30) of the Vacuum Sintered (1260°C) P68 Specimens Quenched from Different Austenitising Temperatures

As-sintered HV30	$\theta\gamma$ [°C]	1100	1150	1175	1200
635±10	HV30	913±14	904±13	881±10	876±10

TABLE 3.14 – Hardness (HV30) of Atmosphere Sintered Specimens Quenched from Different Austenitising Temperatures

POWDER	Sintering Temperature [°C]	As-sintered HV30	$\theta\gamma$ [°C]	HV30
P68	1180	541±17	1100	763±8
P68	1200	579±10	1100	777±8
P77	1150	575±12	1050	914±32
P77	1150		1075	814±36
P81	1150	563±5	1050	800±34
P81	1150		1075	766±44

TABLE 3.15 – Bend Strength, Hardness (HV30), Weibull modulus and Bend Strength Converted for American Standard ANSE/ASTM B528-76 of Hardened and Tempered Vacuum Sintered P68 Specimens

$\theta\gamma$ [°C]	Tempering [°C]	Bend Strength [MPa]	Hardness [HV30]	m	σ^s_R
1100	510	2297±87	871±3	17	1973
1150	550	2384±118	855±6	13	1954
1175	550	2080±54	878±6	26	1883
1200	550	2049±78	901±10	17	1760

TABLE 3.16 – Bend Strength and Hardened and Tempered Atmosphere Sintered Specimens

POWDER	θ_{γ} [°C]	Tempering [°C]	Bend Strength [MPa]	Hardness [HV30]
P68 (US+HIP)	1100	600	2082±114	885±4
P68 (FS)	1100	585	2031±81	931±3
P77	1050	520	1900±86	950±14
P77	1075	475	1795±50	997±11
P77 (HIP)	“	475	1874±55	990±14
P77	“	540	1904±66	966±9
P77 (HIP)	“	540	1915±58	917±15
P81	1075	460	1915±55	980±11
P81 (HIP)	“	460	1912±78	970±10
P81	“	530	1935±80	934±6
P81 (HIP)	“	530	1870±90	964±15

a) P68 powder

100µm

b) P72 powder

c) P73 powder

d) P74 powder

e) P75 powder

f) P77 powder

g) P81 powder

Figure 3.1 - Morphology of the powders used in this research (<125 µm fraction) (SEM micrographs)

Figure 3.1 h) - Yield (<125 μm Fraction) of the Atomisation Runs of the Powders Produced in the Present Research, as Function of Carbon and Vanadium Contents.

Figure 3.2 – Dilatometric Traces of the Alloys Used in the Present Research. Determination of A_{ci} . Heating Rate of $10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

Figure 3.3 – Dilatometric Traces at a Cooling Rate of $2^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ of the Alloys Used in the Present Research.

a1)

a2)

Figure 3.4 - Microstructure and EDS analysis of the P74 Powder Particles
a1) As-Atomised Particle
a2) Backscattered Electrons Image of the Same Particle

Figure 3.4 - Microstructure and EDS analysis of the P74 Powder Particles
 b1) As-Annealed Particle
 b2) Backscattered Electrons Image of the Same Particle

a)

b)

Figure 3.5 - Microstructure of the P68 Powder Particles:
a) As-Atomised
b) As-Annealed

Figure 3.5 c) - X-ray Diffraction Patterns of the As-Atomised Powders Used in the Present Research

Figure 3.5 d) - X-ray Diffraction Patterns of the As-Annealed Powders Used in the Present Research

Figure 3.6 - Green Density of the As-Annealed Powders When Compacted at 600, 700 and 800 MPa.

Figure 3.7 – Schematic Representation of a Sintering Curve for a High Speed Steel Powder

a)

b)

c)

Figure 3.8 – Vacuum Sintering Curves of the P68 Powder

- a) No Carbon Addition
- b) 0.1 wt% Carbon Addition
- c) 0.2 wt% Carbon Addition

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 3.9 - P68 Vacuum Sintered Microstructures (1 hour sintering time):

a)1210°C (T_{os}) b)1250°C (T_m) c)1260°C (OST) d)1280°C (T_d)

Figure 3.9 (cont.) - e) P68 Vacuum Sintered at 1210°C. Microstructure Particularity.

Figure 3.10 - X-rays Diffraction Patterns of the Vacuum Sintered P68 With No Carbon Addition:
a) 1210°C
b) 1260°C
c) 1280°C

Figure 3.11- γ - M_2C Eutectic Carbide on a P68 Specimen Sintered in Vacuum at 1260°C

a) P68 vacuum sintered at 1260°C (1 hour)

b) Tungsten X-ray pattern

c) Carbon X-ray pattern

d) Vanadium X-ray pattern

Figure 3.12- Micrograph and X-Ray Maps of Vacuum Sintered P68 (1260°C/1 hour) Obtained on a Microprobe. On The X-Ray Maps, Black Represents the Element Lack and Orange its Highest Concentration.

e)Chromium X-ray pattern

Figure 3.12 (cont.)- Micrograph and X-Ray Maps of Vacuum Sintered P68 (1260°C/1 hour) Obtained on a Microprobe. On The X-Ray Maps, Black Represents the Element Lack and Orange its Highest Concentration.

Figure 3.13 - Vacuum Sintering Curves of P77 and P81 Powders

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 3.14 - P77 Vacuum Sintered Microstructures (1 hour sintering time)
a) 1130°C, b) 1190°C, c) 1200°C and d) 1250°C

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 3.15 - P81 Vacuum Sintered Microstructures (1 hour sintering time)
a) 1130°C, b) 1190°C, c) 1200°C and d) 1250°C

Figure 3.16 - N₂+7% H₂ Atmosphere Sintering Curve of the P68 Powder

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 3.17- P68 $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere Sintered Microstructures
(1 hour sintering time)
(a) and (b) $600^\circ C$, (c) and (d) $950^\circ C$

e)

f)

g)

h)

Figure 3.17 - P68 $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere Sintered Microstructures
(1 hour sintering time)
(e) and (f) 1120°C, (g) and (h) 1180°C

i)

j)

k)

l)

Figure 3.17 - P68 $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere Sintered Microstructures
 (1 hour sintering time)
 (i) and (j) 1200°C; (k) and (l) 1260°C

a)

c)

d)

Figure 3.18 - Precipitation of a Cr-rich carbide linking MX carbonitrides in P68 Powder sintered in a $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere (1 hour)

a) P68 1140°C	b) P68 1200°C
c) P68 1140°C - Cr x-ray pattern	d) P68 1200°C - Cr x-ray pattern

Figure 3.19 - X-Rays Diffraction Patterns of P68 Sintered in a $N_2 + 7\% H_2$ Atmosphere:
 a) 600°C
 b) 950°C

Figure 3.19 - X-Rays Diffraction Patterns of P88 Sintered in a $N_2 + 7\% H_2$ Atmosphere:

- c) 1120°C
- d) 1200°C
- e) 1250°C

Figure 3.20 a) – SEM EDS Analysis of P68 Specimens Sintered in N₂+7%H₂ Atmosphere at 600°C

Figure 3.20 b) – SEM EDS Analysis of P68 Specimens Sintered in N₂+7%H₂ Atmosphere at 950°C

Figure 3.20 c) – SEM EDS Analysis of P68 Specimens Sintered in N₂+7%H₂ Atmosphere at 1120°C

Figure 3.20 d) – SEM EDS Analysis of P68 Specimens Sintered in N₂+7%H₂ Atmosphere at 1200°C

Figure 3.20 e) – SEM EDS Analysis of P68 Specimens Sintered in N₂+7%H₂ Atmosphere at 1240°C

a)

b)

Figure 3.21 - P68 Powder Sintered in $N_2+7\%H_2$, 1260°C. [micrographs made in INPG]

a) MC/MX and Pearlitic Matrix

b) MC/MX, M₆C, M₃C and Pearlitic Matrix

Figure 3.22 - Density Evolution with Sintering Time of P68 Specimens Sintered in a N₂+7%H₂ Atmosphere. Sintering Times were 5, 30, 60, 180, and 360 minutes. Specimens Have Been Oil Quenched After Sintering.

Figure 3.23 - Microstructures of the Sintered and Quenched P68 Alloy, Sintered at Different Temperatures and Times.

a) Sintering Temperature = 1120°C, 5 minutes.

b) Sintering Temperature = 1120°C, 60 minutes.

c) Sintering Temperature = 1120°C, 360 minutes.

d)

e)

f)

Figure 3.23 - Microstructures of the Sintered and Quenched P68 Alloy, Sintered at Different Temperatures and Times.

d) Sintering Temperature = 1150°C, 5 minutes.

e) Sintering Temperature = 1150°C, 60 minutes.

f) Sintering Temperature = 1150°C, 360 minutes.

g)

h)

i)

Figure 3.23 - Microstructures of the Sintered and Quenched P68 Alloy, Sintered at Different Temperatures and Times.

g) Sintering Temperature = 1200°C, 5 minutes.

h) Sintering Temperature = 1200°C, 60 minutes.

i) Sintering Temperature = 1200°C, 360 minutes.

j)

k)

l)

Figure 3.23 - Microstructures of the Sintered and Quenched P68 Alloy, Sintered at Different Temperatures and Times.

j) Sintering Temperature = 1240°C, 5 minutes.

k) Sintering Temperature = 1240°C, 60 minutes.

l) Sintering Temperature = 1240°C, 360 minutes.

Figure 3.24 - Microstructure and EDS Analysis of P68 Alloy $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere Sintered at 1120°C for 6 hours and Oil Quenched

Figure 3.25 - Nitrogen Content Evolution with Sintering Time of the $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere Sintered and Oil Quenched P68 Alloy.

Figure 3.26 - Carbon Effect on N₂+7%H₂ Atmosphere Sintering of Vanadium-Rich HSS
 a) 6 wt% V, b) 8 wt% V, c) 10 wt% V and d) 12 wt% V.

Figure 3.27 – Vanadium Effect on N₂+7% H₂ Atmosphere Sintering of Vanadium-Rich HSS: a) 1.6 wt% C; b) 2.0 wt% C and c) 2.4 wt% C

Figure 3.28 - Undersintered Specimens Sintered in $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere:

- a) P81 - 2.6C / 6V - Sintered at 1080°C
- b) P75 - 1.6C / 6V - Sintered at 1180°C
- c) P74 - 4C / 12V - Sintered at 1060°C
- d) P74 - 1.6C / 12V - Sintered at 1220°C

e)

Figure 3.28 - Undersintered Specimens Sintered in $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere:

e) P68 - 2.2C / 8V - Sintered at $1120^\circ C$, Showing an Oxide Row
Between Two Prior Particle Boundaries.

Figure 3.28 - Undersintered Specimens Sintered in $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere:

- f) P72 - 1.6C / 8V - Sintered at $1180^\circ C$
- g) P73 - 1.6C / 10V - Sintered at $1200^\circ C$
- h) P77 - 2.7C / 8V - Sintered at $1080^\circ C$
- i) P73 - 3.4C / 10V - Sintered at $1060^\circ C$

Figure 3.29 a) - Microstructures of the Alloys Sintered in a $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere (SEM):

- a1) 6V/1.6C - Sintering Temperature=1280°C (P75)
- a2) 6V/2.0C - Sintering Temperature =1220°C (P75)
- a3) 6V/2.2C - Sintering Temperature =1170°C (P75)
- a4) 6V/2.6C - Sintering Temperature =1150°C (P81)

Figure 3.29 b) - Microstructures of the Alloys Sintered in a $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere(SEM):

b1) 8V/1.6C - Sintering Temperature = 1280°C (P72)

b2) 8V/2.0C - Sintering Temperature = 1240°C (P72)

b3) 8V/2.4C - Sintering Temperature = 1200°C (P68)

b4) 8V/2.7C - Sintering Temperature = 1150°C (P77)

Figure 3.29 c)- Microstructures of the Alloys Sintered in a $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere (SEM):

c1) 10V/1.6C - Sintering Temperature = $1280^\circ C$ (P73)

c2) 10V/2.4C - Sintering Temperature = $1220^\circ C$ (P73)

c3) 10V/3.4C - Sintering Temperature = $1110^\circ C$ (P73)

Figure 3.29 d)- Microstructures of the Alloys Sintered in a $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere(SEM):

d1) 12V/1.6C - Sintering Temperature =1300°C (P74)

d2) 12V/2.4C - Sintering Temperature =1250°C (P74)

d3) 12V/ 4C - Sintering Temperature =1100°C (P74)

Figure 3.29 e) - Microstructures of the Alloys Sintered in a $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere(SEM):

e1) 6V/2.0C - Sintering Temperature =1240°C (P75)

e2) 8V/1.6C - Sintering Temperature =1320°C (P72)

e3) 12V/1.6C - Sintering Temperature =1320°C (P74)

e4) 12V/2.4C - Sintering Temperature =1270°C (P74)

Figure 3.30 - MX Volume Fraction, Carbon and Nitrogen Content of Specimens Sintered in $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere, at the OST (Referred to in Table 3.11).

Figure 3.31 - Microprobe Micrograph and X-Ray Maps of P74 (4%C/12% V) Sintered in $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere at $1100^\circ C$ - 1 hour.

Figure 3.32 - 3-D Plot of the Nitrogen Content at the OST of the Alloys with Different Vanadium and Carbon Contents, when Sintered in a 7% H₂+N₂ Atmosphere.

Figure 3.33-Carbon Effect on Tos, Tm and Td of N₂+7%H₂ Atmosphere Sintered Vanadium-Rich HSS with a) 6% V, b) 8% V, c) 10% V and d) 12% V.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 3.34 - Vanadium Effect on T_{os} , T_m and T_d for the Alloys with a) 1.6, b) 2.0 and c) 2.4 wt% Carbon Content, When Sintered in $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 3.35 - 3-D Plot of the Evolution of T_{os} , T_m and T_d with the Carbon and Vanadium Content of the Studied Alloys

Figure 3.36 - (a) Distortion (surface blisters) of P72 (2%C/8%V) Specimens When Sintered in a $\text{N}_2+7\% \text{H}_2$ Atmosphere at 1270°C - 1 hour
(b) Detail View Showing M_6C Eutectic Carbides

Figure 3.37 a) – DTA Traces On Heating of the As-annealed Powders Performed in Argon Atmosphere:
 P77 – 2.7C/ 7V; P68 – 2.2C/ 8V; P81- 2.6C/ 6V; and P74 – 4C/12V (wt%)

Figure 3.37 b) – DTA Traces On Heating of the As-annealed Powders Performed under Nitrogen Atmosphere:
P77 – 2.7C/ 7V; P68 – 2.2C/ 8V; P81- 2.6C/ 6V; and P74 – 4C/12V (wt%)

Figure 3.38 - HV30 and Microstructures of the As-Quenched Vacuum Sintered P68 Specimens

Figure 3.39 - As-Quenched Hardness of the $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere Sintered P68, P77 and P81 Specimens, at Different Austenitising Temperatures

Figure 3.40 - X-ray Diffraction Patterns of the As-Quenched Vacuum Sintered P68 Alloy

a) $\theta_\gamma=1200^\circ\text{C}$, b) $\theta_\gamma=1175^\circ\text{C}$, c) $\theta_\gamma=1150^\circ\text{C}$ and d) $\theta_\gamma=1100^\circ\text{C}$

a) Carbon

b) Chromium

c) Tungsten

d) Vanadium

e) Molybdenum

Figure 3.41 – Microprobe X-Ray Maps of “as-Quenched” Nitrogen Sintered P68 Alloy.

Sintering Temperature = 1200°C; $\theta\gamma = 1100^\circ\text{C}$

(Orange color is the highest element concentration and black is lack)

Figure 3.42 - Tempering Curves of the Sintered P68 Specimens:

a) Vacuum Sintered and Quenched from 1100°, 1150°, 1175° and 1200°C.

b) N₂+7% H₂ Atmosphere Under- and Fully-Sintered and Quenched from 1100°C

Figure 3.43 - Tempering Curves of the $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere Sintered and Quenched from 1050° and 1075°C:

- a) P77 Alloy
- b) P81 Alloy

Figure 3.44 - Typical Microstructures of the Quenched and Triple Tempered Specimens Sintered in Vacuum and $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmospheres:

- a) P68 Vacuum Sintered at $1260^\circ\text{C}-\theta\gamma=1150^\circ\text{C}/T(3 \times 1 \text{ hour})=550^\circ\text{C}$
- b) P68 $N_2+7\%H_2$ Sintered at $1200^\circ\text{C}-\theta\gamma=1100^\circ\text{C}/T(3 \times 1 \text{ hour})=550^\circ\text{C}$
- c) P77 $N_2+7\%H_2$ Sintered at $1150^\circ\text{C}-\theta\gamma=1050^\circ\text{C}/T(3 \times 1 \text{ hour})=520^\circ\text{C}$
- d) P81 $N_2+7\%H_2$ Sintered at $1150^\circ\text{C}-\theta\gamma=1050^\circ\text{C}/T(3 \times 1 \text{ hour})=460^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 3.45 - Failure Initiation Site of Vacuum Sintered P68 Alloy ($\theta\gamma = 1200^{\circ}\text{C}$): Pores.
a) Pore Beneath Surface.
b) Tensile Face Adjacent to Fracture Surface (FS).
c) Cracked MC Carbides on Tensile Face, About 1 mm Away from FS.

Figure 3.46 - Failure Initiation Sites of $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere Sintered Specimens
(P77 Sintered at $1150^\circ C+HIP+\theta\gamma=1075^\circ C-2min.+Tempering=540^\circ C$)
a) Pore
b1) Poor Bonding Boundaries
b2) EDS Analysis of the Dark Arrowed Area Shown in b1)

Figure 3.46 - Failure Initiation Sites of $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere Sintered Specimens
(P77 Sintered at $1150^\circ C+HIP+\theta\gamma=1075^\circ C-2min.+Tempering=540^\circ C$)
c1) Si Containing Inclusion
c2) EDS Analysis of the Inclusion Shown in c1)

Figure 3.46 - Failure Initiation Sites of $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere Sintered Specimens
(P77 Sintered at $1150^\circ C+HIP+\theta\gamma=1075^\circ C-2min.+Tempering=540^\circ C$)
d1) Al-Si-Ca Containing Inclusion
d2) EDS Analysis of the Inclusion Shown in d1)
e) Surface Failure Initiation Site Containing No Obvious Flaw

4 - DISCUSSION

The main objective of this research was to carry out a study of the differences in sintering behaviour of high vanadium containing water atomised high speed steel powders sintered in vacuum and in a nitrogen-hydrogen atmosphere. A key subsidiary aim was to investigate the effects variations in vanadium and carbon content had on powder sinterability in atmosphere sintering.

The seven powders produced in the course of this investigation all exhibited characteristics typical of water atomised powders. As shown in Figure 3.1, all batches comprised irregular shaped particles typical for water atomisation. However, the particle size distribution was different for each one. It is believed that this was due to the different chemical compositions, which led to distinct melt viscosities and different melt flow characteristics. Important factors determining powder size and shape are known to be superheat, melt viscosity and melt composition [74,77,80]. However, no obvious relationships between these factors and particle size distributions of the resultant powders were observed in this work, Table 3.2 and Table 3.3. The P68 powder showed the highest mean particle size-140 μm , Table 3.3, and the lowest apparent density-1.17 g/cm^3 , Table 3.5. It is believed that this was a consequence of the high viscosity of the melt, i.e. low metal flowrate of 4.83 kg min^{-1} , Table 3.2, observed during the atomisation run. This prevented effective atomisation of the liquid metal, producing a powder whose particle size distribution was composed mainly of coarse particles, resulting in poor packing characteristics. It is known that higher viscosities lead to increases in the surface tension of the liquid [74,80]. This, as in the case of P68, leads to a coarse particle size distribution and consequently a low apparent density [80,81]. Moreover, contrary to observations reported

by other authors [80,81], the increase of the metal flowrate observed for the other powders (P72 to P75, P77 and P81) did not lead to an increase of the median particle size. Instead, in the case of P77 and P81, Tables 3.2 and 3.3, higher metal flowrates were associated with finer powders. Melt (tap) temperatures were selected using prior experience at INETI making the assumption that liquidus would decrease with increases in carbon contents. However the actual liquidus temperature for each of the experimental alloys was unknown. Hence it is likely that the superheats were different for each composition, leading to variations in melt properties and particle size and shape [83].

The normal “as-atomised” oxygen contents of HSS type powders are in the range 0.1 to 0.3 wt% [69]. Whilst oxygen content of P68, P77 and P81 were of the order of 0.2 wt%, Table 3.1, those for the low carbon-high vanadium series of alloys, P72-P75, were much higher, ranging from 0.6 to 0.9 wt%, and directly increasing with vanadium content, Table 3.1. This was due to the continuous formation, during melting and pouring, of an oxidised slag that consumed some vanadium of the alloys, especially the two alloys with the highest vanadium content—P73 and P74. Whilst, the oxygen affinity of the group VA elements, i.e. V, Nb and Ta is well known [87,88], the relationship between vanadium and as atomised oxygen content was not a direct one, since for powders with similar vanadium contents oxygen content decreased with increasing carbon content of the melts, Table 3.1. In fact when the oxygen content of several different vanadium-containing alloys, produced in the same atomiser in I.N.E.T.I., is plotted against the V/C ratio, Figure 4.1, an approximately linear relationship can be observed, i.e. the oxygen content increasing with the V/C ratio.

Figure 3.4 (a) shows a typical microstructure of the “as-atomised” P74 (12 wt% V) and Figure 3.4 (b) its as-annealed microstructure. Figure 3.5 shows both “as-atomised” and as-annealed P68 microstructures. The main difference between the two typical

“as-atomised” microstructures, is that in the P74 alloy an iron-vanadium-rich oxide film was observed dispersed in the powder particles, similar features were seen in “as-atomised” P72 and P73. Normally oxides in water atomised powders are formed at particle surfaces as a consequence of contact with the atomising medium [69,89]. However, it is believed that the internal oxides are due to oxidation of the melt prior to the atomisation. The implication being that melting vanadium containing high speed steels which are deficient in carbon would result in extensive formation of vanadium oxides. This observation is consistent with thermodynamics since V_2O_3 is the oxide with the lowest free energy of the oxides which may form in these types of alloys [87], Figure 4.2. On the other hand it is well known the affinity for oxygen of the elements of group VA, where V belongs to [87,88], and that V is a strong carbide former [44]. Therefore, when C was present in considered small amounts (<1 wt%) and vanadium content was high, which was the case of the powder series P72-P75, there was not enough carbon to tie the vanadium as carbides, the remaining vanadium combined with oxygen increasing the powder oxygen content, Table 3.1.

Investigation of the “as-atomised” powders by x-ray diffraction showed that the high vanadium-high carbon series, P68, P77 and P81, possessed mixed austenite-ferrite matrixes, Figure 3.5 (c), whereas ferritic matrixes were observed for the high vanadium-low carbon series, P72-P75, Figure 3.5 (c). This can be explained on the basis of the relative ferrite and austenite forming tendencies of carbon (an austenite stabiliser [44]) and vanadium (a ferrite stabiliser [44]). Thus high V/C ratio (i.e. high vanadium-low carbon) would be expected to favour ferrite whereas low V/C favours austenite formation. This is consistent with observations with ternary Fe-V-C alloys [192] and M2 high speed steel [53,72]. Studies on the latter alloy in which the carbon content was kept constant at 0.8 wt%, i.e. comparable to the as atomised carbon contents of P72-P75, and vanadium

contents in the range 2- 5 wt%, showed that alloys with vanadium contents greater than 3 wt% solidified to give ferritic not austenitic matrices [53].

Apart from the P74 and P75 compositions, all the other alloys exhibited similar transformation characteristics in the dilatometric studies, Figures 3.2 and 3.3. A_{ci} and A_{cf} temperatures were comparable to those expected for these alloys [44,83]. Heating to 950°C resulted in complete transformation of ferrite to austenite which in turn fully transformed to ferrite plus secondary carbides on cooling, austenite not being observed in x-ray diffraction studies of annealed powders, Figure 3.5(d). However, the dilatometric traces for the P74 and P75 compositions were significantly different. These differences are difficult to explain without phase diagrams, which are unavailable for these alloys, but may be due to these alloys entering a $\alpha + \gamma + M_6C + MC$ phase field rather than $\gamma + M_6C + MC$ on heating to 950°C. The change in gradient observed on the dilatometric traces on cooling down is indicative of transformation of austenite to ferrite.

Two factors influence the compressibility of metallic powders: particle size and distribution and deformation (work hardening) characteristics of the material. In the case of P68, P77 and P81 powders, these were of similar composition, had being subjected to similar annealing treatment so it is reasonable to believe that microstructures and deformation characteristics would be comparable. Thus it is believed that the differences in compressibility, Figure 3.6 are due to slight differences in particle size distribution, Table 3.3, with the P68 powder being less efficient at packing than the P77 and P81 powders, Figure 3.6. More pronounced variations in compressibility were observed for P72-P75 series of powders. Although the particle size distributions for these powders were not identical, Table 3.3, it is believed that the variations in compressibility were compositional rather than being due to particle size differences since there was a direct correlation between increasing vanadium content and decreasing compressibility. SEM-EDS analysis

showed that irrespective of composition both MC and M_6C carbides were present in the annealed condition, Figures 3.4 and 3.5 (b). However, MC carbides were not detected by x-ray diffraction in the low carbon-high vanadium P72-P75 series, Figure 3.5 (d). This would indicate, not unexpectedly, a lower MC volume fraction. Thus it is postulated that variations in carbide volume fraction and distribution, which would affect deformation characteristics could account for the differences in compressibility.

The only free flowing powder was the P68 composition, Table 3.5. It is known [69,111] that two powder characteristics -particle size and shape- influence the interparticle forces. As all the powders have irregular shaped particles, it is the particle size that influences the powders flowing characteristics. As shown in Table 3.3, all other powders had lower mean particle sizes, and finer particle size distributions than the P68 powder. German reported [69,111] that finer mean particle size powders infer higher interparticle friction and therefore poorer flowing characteristics. It is believed that this would account for the poor flowability of the other powders.

The vacuum sintering curves of P68, P77 and P81 powders, Figure 3.8 and Figure 3.13, all exhibited the “S” shape sintering curve typical of sinterable water atomised HSS powders, Figure 1.7. Wright and co-workers [48,92,105] have shown that vacuum sintering of water atomised T1, M3/2 and M2 high speed steels is an example of supersolidus liquid phase sintering (SLPS). In particular, Wright [92] have shown that the T_{os} (see Figure 3.7) determined from sintering curves corresponds to the solidus temperatures determined by DTA. In fact, in P68, P77 and P81 vacuum sintered specimens, the observation of grain boundary M_2C eutectic carbides in specimens sintered above T_{os} , and the fact that volume fraction of the M_2C eutectic increased concomitantly with sintering temperature, e.g.

Figures 3.9, 3.14 and 3.15, is indicative of sintering in the presence of a liquid phase whose volume fraction increased with sintering temperature.

In terms of microstructure, the major difference noted for P68, P77 and P81 alloys compared to other water atomised HSS powders in general, and high vanadium containing ones in particular, processed by vacuum sintering was the presence of solely globular vanadium rich MC carbides (and some M_2C) in specimens sintered at temperatures above T_{os} - the temperature defining the onset of rapid densification, Figure 3.9, 3.14 and 3.15. In previous studies on T42 (3 wt% V) [32,54,95,136], M3/2 (3 wt% V) [48], T15 (5 wt% V) [8,32], ASP60 (6.5 wt% V) [19] and HITACHI (4.4 wt% V) [20], large angular M_6C primary carbides have always be observed in addition to MC. In the case of P68, P77 and P81, M_6C were only observed in the as-annealed powders, Figure 3.4 (b), Figure 3.5 (b) and (d), and in specimens sintered below T_{os} , Figure 3.9 (a), 3.14 (a) and 3.15 (a). M_6C carbides were observed in the P68, P77 and P81 specimens sintered at T_{os} , Figures 3.9, 3.14 and 3.15, however M_6C disappeared with increasing temperature as a consequence of dissolution, since it is known that M_6C carbides begin to dissolve at temperatures above 1150°C [12], so that samples sintered between T_m and T_d contained no M_6C . The presence of MC as the dominant carbide is simply due to the high vanadium content of the powder and as it is known that vanadium is a strong carbide former (1 wt% vanadium having the same effect as 4 wt% of tungsten [44]), MC vanadium-rich carbides form preferentially. In fact, Fredriksson et al [51] reported that, for a M2-type 1.2 wt% C alloy, above 1.9 wt% V, the amount of MC carbide was almost proportional to the vanadium content. So, this same tendency of the P68, P77 and P81 can be attributed to their high vanadium content, Table 3.1.

The distortion temperature, T_d , of P68, P77 and P81 alloys was associated with the formation of extensive pools of M_2C eutectic carbides, Figure 3.9 (d), Figure 3.14 (d) and

Figure 3.15 (d), especially for the P77 and P81 compositions. This distortion was associated with the formation of excess liquid phase. M_2C eutectic structures have been observed in many studies of oversintered vanadium containing high speed steels, for example M3/2 [48], ASP60 [19], HITACHI [20] and its needle shaped was found to be due to these alloys' high vanadium content [52]. In cast high speed steels M_2C carbide is a non-equilibrium phase, which decomposes into MC and M_6C carbides during subsequent reheating and hot working. Studies on unidirectional solidified M2-type compositions by Fredriksson et al [51] have identified the two main factors that influence the occurrence of M_2C eutectic carbides: high cooling rates and alloy content. Fredriksson et al [51] have shown that for a M2-type alloy with different carbon levels (0.90, 1.2 and 1.5 wt% C), a low vanadium content favoured the precipitation of M_6C herringbone eutectic carbides, whereas a high carbon content as well as a high vanadium content (>1.9 wt%) favoured the precipitation of MC and M_2C carbides, the same trends have been found by Gongqi et al [193] in tungsten based HSS's. Independently, Haberling et al [125], showed that high carbon contents in M2 also favoured M_2C formation. Similar remarks were made by Lichtenegger et al [52] for M2-type alloys, who reported that M_2C carbides can occur in HSS in three different morphologies: needle-like, lamellar and rod-like, the different morphologies being dependant on both alloy composition and cooling rate, the needle carbide being favoured by higher vanadium contents.

Sato et al [127] reported that for high vanadium HSS balanced compositions require the following relationship to be satisfied:

$$C(\%) = 0.19 + 0.017 \times W(\%) + 0.22 \times V(\%) \quad (4.1)$$

Table 4.1 compares the carbon contents for P68, P77 and P81 with those calculated from Equation 4.1. The equivalent carbon content calculation using the DIN 17 350 standard (1%W = 0.033%C; 1% Mo = 0.063%C; 1% V = 0.176%C and 1% Cr = 0.06%C) gives a necessary carbon content of 2.16 wt% for P68, 2.07 wt% for P77 and 1.76 wt% for P81, Table 4.1. This expression also shows that the actual carbon content of the P68 alloy can be considered as balanced, whilst P77 and P81 had excess carbon. Golczewski et al [55], on the basis of thermodynamic calculations with M2 HSS compositions, suggested that due to segregation factors, the melt which solidifies at last in the form of eutectic, is strongly enriched in carbon and in alloy elements which possess a segregation coefficient <1 , e.g. molybdenum and vanadium. High levels of these elements favour the crystallisation of M_2C at the expense of M_6C . The segregation coefficient of tungsten is >1 , and will therefore be low in the residual melt, which again favours the formation of M_2C . So the formation of M_2C -type eutectic is to be explained by enrichment of the liquid with carbon and alloying elements during sintering [55]. The higher amounts of needle-like M_2C eutectic carbide observed in the P77 and P81 compositions being attributed to the excess carbon content of these alloys. The high furnace cooling rate ($>80^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) of the vacuum sintering runs may also have favoured the formation of M_2C carbides, since previous studies on T15 [29], showed that fast cooling rates at $250^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ resulted in M_2C formation whereas when the same alloy was cooled slowly at 20°C h^{-1} from identical sintering temperatures, M_2C decomposed into MC and M_6C [29,54,194].

When powdered graphite was added to the P68 alloy, no deleterious effect on the microstructure was observed. The main effect was to lower the T_m and OST temperatures by 10° and 20°C for 0.1 wt% and 0.2 wt% graphite additions, respectively, Figure 3.8. The higher carbon content of the P77 and P81 compositions had more significant influence on sintering behaviour, the OST dropped from 1260°C for P68 to 1210°C for both

compositions. Similarly, reductions were observed for the T_{os} temperatures, which decreased from 1210°C for P68 to 1130°C for both P77 and P81, Figures 3.8(a) and 3.13. It is already well established [1,19,46,83,95,118,124,125], that carbon additions to HSS powders before sintering or to melts prior to atomisation [83], decreases the sintering temperature by decreasing the alloy solidus. Direct evidence for the effect of carbon content on reducing solidus temperatures was provided by the DTA studies, Figure 3.37. Solidus temperatures were 1220°, 1140° and 1140°C for P68, P77 and P81, respectively. As can be seen from Figure 4.3 these temperatures were comparable to the T_{os} temperatures. Thus confirming earlier observations of Wright [92], that sintering of these alloys occurs via a supersolidus liquid phase sintering mechanism, since densification only occurred on sintering above the solidus. An interesting feature of samples sintered just below or just above the T_{os} temperature was the presence of rows of MC carbides decorating oxides, for example Figure 3.9(a) and (e). Such features, which have similarities to “necklace” structures formed by the penetration and subsequent solidification of a wetting liquid observed by German [111] in Fe-7% Ti alloys, are believed to originate from the solidification of a vanadium rich liquid on vanadium rich oxide films not reduced by either the annealing treatments or during heating to the sintering temperature. Such features were not observed at higher sintering temperatures $\geq 1220^\circ\text{C}$, Figure 3.9(b) to (d), presumably due to high temperatures in combination with the vacuum level being more effective in reducing the oxides. Other microstructural evidence to support the presence of liquid at the sintering temperature was the formation of the acicular M_2C eutectic structures, e.g. Figure 3.9(d), a phase not observed in samples sintered below T_{os} . Furthermore, distortion temperatures were coincident with peak 3 of the DTA traces, Figure 4.3(a), a peak identified in parallel melting and solidification studies on the P68 composition by Lemoisson [195] as being due to the $L \rightarrow \gamma + MC$ eutectic reaction. However, distorted

samples did not exhibit skeletal MC eutectic structures, for reasons explained earlier, only increased amounts of non-equilibrium acicular M₂C eutectic compared with undistorted samples. Hence, as suggested by Wright [92], sintering curves for high speed powders can be correlated with transformation temperatures determined by DTA.

The equivalent carbon excess (the amount of carbon dissolved in the matrix) calculated (4.2) [127], also can give an idea about the alloys sintering behaviour:

$$\Delta C_{eq} = C - (0.19 + 0.017 W + 0.034 Mo + 0.22V) \quad (4.2)$$

The calculated ΔC_{eq} values for the majority of the alloys used in the present research (with several carbon contents) are shown in Figure 4.4 (a). In this Figure it can be seen that in fact, the P77 and P81 alloys have a carbon excess and that P68 has a slight carbon deficiency. Although the higher carbon levels of P77 and P81 lowered sintering temperatures significantly compared to P68, a commercially interesting observation, it resulted in the formation of large volume fractions of M₂C eutectics at all temperatures along the sintering plateau. The M₂C phase is considered an undesirable feature in HSS microstructures [1]. Although “in situ” decomposition of M₂C into MC and M₆C is possible by high temperature heat treatment [54], Maulik reported for T42 this reaction to be complete after heating for 1 hour at 1200°C, the acicular morphology would remain, very likely having a deleterious effect on properties. Thus, excess carbon level of 2.6 and 2.7 wt% have resulted in compositions unsuited for vacuum sintering to full density.

For a number of HSS powders, Wright et al [42,48,105,114] have correlated sintering curves and resultant microstructures with relevant phase diagrams. They have extended the generic model of SLPS of German, which states that sintering takes place on heating to a temperature intermediate between the liquidus and solidus [70,118,119]. In the case of HSS’s optimal sintering temperatures are located within the $\gamma + M_6C/ MC + liquid$

phase field. Moreover, Wright et al [48,105] have suggested that the gradient of the solidus line and the separation between solidus and the upper line of the γ + carbide(s) + liquid phase diagram region is of crucial importance. In the T1 system increases in carbon content were found to lead to a significant lowering of solidus temperatures, Figure 4.5, and due to widening of the $L + \gamma + M_6C/ MC$ phase field, a considerable increase in the width of the sintering window. They reported at 0.8 wt% C sintering windows of 10°C compared to one of 40°C at 1.4 wt% C. In an earlier paper Wright and Ogel [48] attributed the inferior sinterability of M2 to T1 to the compressed nature of the $L + \gamma + M_6C/ MC$ region in that system and the shallower solidus gradient shown in Figure 1.4, a feature confirmed by the solidification studies of Barkalow et al [53] and, more recently, in the calculated M2 phase diagram of Golczewski et al [55]. An interesting observation concerning the sintering characteristics of a number of high vanadium containing HSS's is, despite wide differences in alloy composition, is their similarity in sintering temperatures. For example optimum vacuum sintering temperatures for T42 (3.7 wt% V) [32], T15 (5 wt% V) [32], HITACHI (4.5 wt% V) [20] and ASP60 (6.5 wt% V) [19] are 1250°, 1260°, 1240° and 1235°C respectively. Sintering windows are $\approx 10^\circ\text{C}$, no better than for other high speed steels. These similarities are illustrated in Figures 4.6 and 4.7, in which, following the fashion of Wright et al [92], T_{os} , T_m and T_d temperatures, Table 4.2, are plotted for different C and V contents. As can be seen, for a given carbon content increases in vanadium contents above 2 wt% result in slight increases in T_{os} , and hence, given the established correlation between DTA and sintering curves, in solidus temperatures. Similar trends also occur for T_m and T_d . Conversely for a given vanadium content, T_{os} , and hence solidus temperatures, T_m and T_d show a decrease with increasing carbon content. Moreover apart from T1, P77 and P81 compositions, the temperatures separating T_{os} , T_m and T_d are largely independent of composition. Given the correlations established between sintering curves and appropriate

phase diagrams for a number of high speed steels it would seem reasonable to infer from Figures 4.6 and 4.7 that in high speed steels containing 2-8 wt% V and up to 2.3 wt% C that the $L + \gamma + M_6C/ MC$ phase field is similar in form to that shown in Figure 1.4 for M2, i.e. a narrow $L + \gamma + M_6C/ MC$ phase field with a shallow decrease in solidus with increasing carbon content. Evidence to support this view is provided by the pseudo-binary phase diagrams calculated by Ansara [83] for the Fe - 12W - 4 Cr - C - V system at 5, 10 and 15 wt%, Figure 4.8. These show $L + \gamma + M_6C/ MC$ phase fields similar in form to that observed in the M2 system. The commercial implications of this will now be discussed.

In 1970's and 1980's a number of companies attempted, with varying degrees of success, to commercialise the cold compaction-vacuum sintering of prealloyed water atomised HSS's powders [81,196]. However, as pointed out by Brewin [196] the narrow sintering windows, at best 10°C, combined with small temperature variations within sintering furnaces, made it difficult to control dimensional tolerances, preventing net shape processing. More recently, by using phase diagrams calculated from thermodynamic data, Fe-Cr-Mo-(Co)-C alloys have been identified which possess sintering windows of 20-30°C with mechanical and cutting properties comparable to some grades of HSS's [42,114]. However, all these sinterable compositions contain no vanadium and owe their enhanced sinterability to an expansion in the temperature interval separating the solidus from the upper boundary of the $L + \gamma + M_6C$ phase field. From the evidence presented above it can be postulated that, given the effect of vanadium contents of 2 wt% and above is to compress not expand the width of the $L + \gamma + M_6C/ MC$ phase field over a wide range of alloy compositions, it unlikely that vanadium containing compositions could be developed which possess comparable sintering windows. The variation in T_{os} , T_m and T_d for alloys containing 2.6-2.7 wt% C appears to contradict the above argument since there is an apparent expansion in temperature interval, Figure 3.13. However, these were unbalanced

compositions with excess carbon which promoted the formation of M_2C eutectics, Figures 3.14 and 3.15. Accordingly these were considered to be unsinterable compositions for cold compaction-vacuum sintering processes. Although previous work has suggested that M_2C eutectic formation could be avoided by slow cooling from sintering temperature [51]. This would be unacceptable industrially since in order to minimise cycle times, fast cooling which favours M_2C formation are preferred.

The studies of Urcola and co-workers [26-32,34] have suggested a possible alternative approach to enhancing the sinterability of vanadium containing high speed steels. Sintering alloys such as T42 and T15 in a $H_2-N_2-CH_4$ atmosphere resulted in both a lowering of sintering temperature and a claimed widening of sintering windows compared to vacuum sintering [32]. The main aim of this thesis was to expand on the work of Urcola et al by studying the effects of sintering alloys containing vanadium in a nitrogen rich atmosphere on microstructure and sinterability levels much higher than those investigated previously. The results of this study will now be discussed.

The first significant observation of sintering the P68, P77 and P81 experimental alloys in the nitrogen-rich atmosphere, was the decrease in the sintering temperatures, compared with the same alloys sintered in vacuum, i.e. the temperature to achieve maximum density was some $60^\circ C$ lower than when the specimens were sintered in the nitrogen-based atmosphere. In fact, though the nitrogen sintering curves show the same evolution as in vacuum, the reference temperatures as shown in Figure 3.7– T_{os} , T_m and T_d – were lower, T_m temperatures for P68, P77 and P81 were 1180° , 1130° and $1130^\circ C$ respectively. This is in agreement with previously observed effects of sintering for T15 (1.64 C, 4.7 V) [27,29], T1 (0.96 C, 1.09 V) [29] and T42 (1.45 C, 2.94 V) [26,29] powders when sintered in a $N_2-H_2-CH_4$ atmosphere compared to vacuum. The sintering

temperatures of P68, P77 and P81 were dropped $\approx 60^{\circ}\text{C}$ when these alloys were sintered in the nitrogen atmosphere, i.e. a larger decrease compared to the drop of about 20°C observed for T42 HSS by Palma et al [26], and about 40°C for T15 HSS processed by Jauregi et al [27] under similar conditions. Thus there is apparently a direct correlation in the reduction sintering temperature and vanadium content. The reason for this will be discussed later. However, the lowering of sintering temperatures to, in the case of P77 and P81, 1150°C is of commercial significance, since this could enable full density processing using continuous mesh belt sintering furnaces - the preferred choice of the PM industry since this has the lowest operating costs of any type of sintering furnace [69,91]. So, it can be said that an important decrease in sintering temperatures can be observed when high vanadium containing HSS, i.e. $> 2 \text{ wt\%}$, are processed via nitrogen atmosphere sintering.

Significant differences were observed between the microstructures of vacuum sintered P68, P77 and P81 and the same compositions sintered in the nitrogen rich atmospheres. Firstly MC carbides present on the vacuum sintered material were replaced by nitrogen containing MX carbonitrides, Table 3.12. The MX particles were much smaller than the MC carbides in fully dense vacuum sintered alloys, Figures 3.17, 3.28 and 3.29. Secondly, fully dense atmosphere sintered alloys contained a significant volume fraction of M_6C carbide, a phase absent from the vacuum sintered steels. These two observations are consistent with those of Palma et al [26] on T42 and Jauregi et al [27] on T15 who also reported that sintering in a nitrogen rich atmosphere resulted in the formation of smaller MX and an increase in M_6C volume fraction [26,27]. The third significant difference was the formation of Fe-Cr rich M_3C carbides in the atmosphere sintered alloys whose carbon content was at least 2.0 wt%. This phase was absent from vacuum sintered alloys containing similar carbon levels. A much lower volume fraction Fe-Cr rich phase have been observed in T42 HSS [29] sintered in a nitrogen rich atmosphere.

Nitrogen content was observed to increase when the powders were sintered in the nitrogen-rich atmosphere, Table 3.10, compared with nitrogen content of as-annealed powders, Table 3.1, and in the case of P68, with vacuum sintered, Table 3.6. In fact, P68 powder had a nitrogen content of 0.04 wt% when sintered in vacuum at the OST, that was 1260°C, Table 3.6, and when it was sintered in N₂+7%H₂ atmosphere the respective nitrogen content was increased up to 1.2 wt% for the specimens sintered at the OST, 1200°C, Table 3.10, the as-annealed content being 0.058 wt%, Table 3.1.

DTA traces of P68, P77, P81 and P74 (4 wt% C) carried out in nitrogen atmosphere, Figure 3.37(b), showed solidus temperatures lower than the ones found for DTA runs performed in argon, Figure 3.37(a). The solidus temperature for the P68 composition was decreased by about 80°C, whilst the ones for P77 and P81 were reduced by about 40°C. In addition, all these alloys but P68 showed, in nitrogen, a feature that was not observed in the runs performed in argon, Figure 4.3(d), shown schematically in Figure 4.3(c) as peak 2a. This feature, can be ascribed to formation of a γ -M₃C eutectic, whose consequence for sinterability will be discussed later. This transformation was most pronounced in the P74 composition, Figure 3.37 and, unlike the other compositions studied by DTA, was observed for runs carried out in both argon and nitrogen. As it was shown previously for vacuum sintering of P68, P77 and P81, correlation between DTA and nitrogen sintering curves can also be done. In fact, the nitrogen sintering curves of P68, P77 and P81, showed that the rapid densification zone only occurred once the solidus temperatures, determined by DTA, had been exceeded, Figure 4.3(d). This can mean, as already observed for the vacuum sintering of these alloys, that a minimum amount of liquid is necessary to promote densification, i.e. nitrogen sintering of high vanadium containing alloys can also be explained by invoking a SLPS mechanism. This evidence is reinforced from the results of the study of the effects of varying time and temperature on the atmosphere sintering of P68,

Figure 3.22 and Table 3.8, which showed that no total densification was possible when the sintering trials were carried out at temperatures up to 1150°C ($\approx T_{os}$) even for 360 minutes sintering times. This once more enhances the fact that a minimum amount of liquid is necessary to sinter these alloys to maximum density. On the other hand the pronounced $M_3C + \gamma \rightarrow L$ reaction in the P74-4%C composition was associated with a lack of sinterability in the nitrogen atmosphere, since compacts prepared from this alloy distorted before attaining full density, Figure 3.26, and resultant microstructures contained a high volume fraction of large M_3C carbides, Figure 3.29(d3).

Microstructural developments occurring during sintering in the nitrogen rich atmospheres were studied in detail using the P68 composition without added carbon. The “as-annealed” microstructure of this powder, in common with all the compositions used in this investigation, consisted of small vanadium-rich MC and tungsten-molybdenum-iron rich M_6C carbides dispersed in a ferritic matrix, Figures 3.4 and 3.5(b). Nitriding of steels is normally carried in mixtures of NH_3 , N_2 and H_2 at temperatures in the range 400°-600°C [1,13,152,153,197,198] with atomic nitrogen, derived from the reactive species [13,152] forming Fe_4N . At these temperatures pure nitrogen is considered to be unreactive with nitriding steels due to the low level of dissociation [152,156]. In a recent study by Correia et al [197] M2 powders nitrided in NH_3 at 500°-600°C were reported to contain up to 5 wt% N with the nitrogen forming Fe_3N rather than Fe_4N normally found in nitrided steels. In the present investigation there was no evidence from x-ray diffraction studies of P68, P77 and P81 samples sintered at 600°C of nitride formation. Instead x-ray diffraction and SEM studies indicated the presence of Cr-rich M_3C . It is well known that in order for nitrides to form in flowing $NH_3 + N_2/ H_2$ mixtures at 400°-600°C the dissociation of NH_3 has to be controlled [13,198]. If dissociation is too low nitrides will not form, Figure 4.9 [199].

However the formation of M_3C at 600°C , a phase not present in the annealed powders, implies that the $N_2 + 7\% H_2$ atmosphere has sufficient activity to react with the P68 (and P77, P81) compositions. The formation of M_3C is indicative that the matrix is being enriched in carbon. Now nitrogen is soluble in MC but not in M_6C [199,36]. Thus it would appear that the source of this carbon is the result of the *in situ* transformation of MC to MX. However, due to the small size of the vanadium rich particles at these temperatures, it was not possible to confirm this by microanalysis.

The nitrogen diffusion rate is higher in ferrite ($D_0 = 0.0047 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) than in austenite ($D_0 = 0.0034 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) [200], though nitrogen solubility being higher in the γ -phase [31], Figure 1.19. This high solubility is due to the nitrogen atomic radius (0.75\AA), being smaller than the other interstitial species, the carbon (0.91\AA), and to the different lattice parameters the α -phase being smaller ($Fe_\alpha\text{-b.c.c.} = 2.86$ and $Fe_\gamma\text{-f.c.c.} = 3.6$ [201]). On the other hand, it is known [87,88,200] that grain boundaries represent regions of lattice mismatch and disorder which cause enhanced diffusion. It was observed [88] as an approximate rule, that the activation energy for grain boundary diffusion is approximately half of that for lattice diffusion. Then, owing to the lower activation energy, the relative importance of grain boundary diffusion increases with decreasing temperature, the diffusing species, in this case nitrogen, moving rapidly along the grain boundaries whilst it simultaneously diffuses into the grains from the grain boundary by lattice or volume diffusion [87,88,200]. Hence, at these temperatures ($<A_{ci}$) it is postulated that the nitrogen atoms start to replace the carbon ones in the MC carbides f.c.c.-lattice forming MX carbonitrides, the carbon being rejected to the matrix, and becoming available to form additional carbides. This explains why the specimens sintered at 600°C , though having a low nitrogen content of 0.06 wt%, already contain chromium-rich carbides. This preferential dissolution/ substitution can be explained by the higher affinity of the nitrogen atoms for the MC carbides [173]. The

formation of vanadium nitride through the reaction of nitrogen with vanadium carbide and release of carbon, as shown in Equation (4.3), is thermodynamically possible. In fact, from Kubaschewsky's thermochemical data [202] Gibbs free energies were calculated for temperatures of 900°(627°C), 1100°(827°C), 1200°(927°C), 1400°(1127°C) and 1500°K (1227°C).

Therefore: $\Delta\mu_o$ = formation energies of the products - formation energies of the reactants
which gives:

$$900^\circ\text{K} \Rightarrow \Delta\mu_o = [-268.2 + 0.88 (-10.4)] - [-140.1 + \frac{1}{2} (-184.3)] = \mathbf{-45.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}}$$

$$1100^\circ\text{K} \Rightarrow \Delta\mu_o = [-287 + 0.88 (-15.3)] - [-155.2 + \frac{1}{2} (-230.1)] = \mathbf{-30.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}}$$

$$1200^\circ\text{K} \Rightarrow \Delta\mu_o = [-297.1 + 0.88 (-18.0)] - [-163.4 + \frac{1}{2} (-253.5)] = \mathbf{-22.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}}$$

$$1400^\circ\text{K} \Rightarrow \Delta\mu_o = [-318.8 + 0.88 (-24.1)] - [-181.2 + \frac{1}{2} (-301)] = \mathbf{-8.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}}$$

$$1500^\circ\text{K} \Rightarrow \Delta\mu_o = [-330.3 + 0.88 (-27.4)] - [-190.7 + \frac{1}{2} (-325.1)] = \mathbf{-1.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}}$$

Hence, the reaction products (vanadium nitride and free carbon) are therefore more stable than vanadium carbide and nitrogen in the range of sintering temperatures.

On the other hand, the f.c.c. nitrides are isomorphous with the carbides (f.c.c. MC) and they are mutually soluble [173]. Since the alloy nitrides are more stable than their respective carbides, it would be expected that most of the nitrogen in the steel will combine with the alloying elements and some of the carbon to form the alloy carbonitride M(CN) [173].

The solution of the nitrogen atoms in the MC carbides, as confirmed by microprobe analysis, Table 3.12, transforms MC into MX and releases carbon to the matrix. The presence of a higher carbon concentration in the matrix causes a decrease in the alloy solidus. It is this transformation of MC to MX which is responsible for the lowering of sintering temperatures when vanadium rich high speed steels are sintered in a N₂-H₂ atmosphere compared to vacuum sintering. As such this is in agreement with Urcola and co-workers who also attributed the reduction in sintering temperatures of T42 and T15 alloys to the transformation of MC to MX and consequence release of carbon to the matrix. However Urcola and co-workers have never stated in any of their papers [26-35] at what temperatures this reaction was initiated. The evidence of the present research is that it can occur early in the sintering cycle. In fact, nitrogen content of alloys sintered at 950°C, 1.26 wt %, was similar to the nitrogen content of the samples sintered at higher temperatures, Table 3.7. Dilatometric studies showed that A_{cf} temperature for P68 was 900°C, Table 3.4. Hence, at 950°C the matrix would be austenitic. According to the data of Feichtinger [123] the solubility of nitrogen in austenite at one atmosphere pressure is only 0.03 %. This would suggest that the transformation of MC to MX is complete by 950°C. At temperatures below A_{ci}, the rejected carbon only has one carbide forming element available in the matrix in enough amount to react with, chromium, as the other carbide formers such as tungsten, molybdenum and vanadium are combined in the M₆C and MC carbides. Hence, the rejected carbon and the available chromium form globular M₃C carbides, Figure 3.17(a) to (d), as identified by x-ray diffraction, Figure 3.19(a) and (b). This carbide was not observed in any of the vacuum sintered specimens. Sintering P68 at temperatures about 1120°C, T_{os} temperature, resulted in minimal microstructure coarsening. However, after sintering for 6 hours at 1120°C coarsening and the development of rod like M₆C carbides was observed, Figure 3.23(c). Identical microstructural development has been observed by Lemoisson

[195] at some stage in the supersolidus liquid phase sintering of T1 high speed steels. Lemoisson attributed this to the presence of a grain boundary liquid phase which facilitated mass transport and hence growth rates. The same principle is probably operating in P68 since the T_{os} temperature was comparable to the solidus. Comparison of the microstructures of atmosphere sintered P68 samples furnace cooled from the sintering temperature with those sintered in under identical conditions then quenched, showed that morphologies of the grain boundary M_6C and MX particles were identical, Figure 3.17(a) to (l) and 3.23(a) to (l). In a study of the sintering of a high carbon T1 (1.4%C), Lemoisson [195] observed a cooling rate effect on the morphology of grain boundary MC carbides. In fully sintered samples quenched from the optimal sintering temperature, 1250°C, the M_6C and iron-chromium $M_{23}C_6$ carbides exhibited identical morphologies to those reported by Wright et al [105] for samples of the same powder furnace cooled from comparable sintering temperature, angular and film like, respectively. The MC carbides though possessed skeletal morphologies in quenched samples [195] and the more usual globular morphology in furnace cooled samples [105]. The implication of this is that the MC carbides found in this alloy are product of solidification of some of the liquid present at the sintering temperature by a $L \rightarrow \gamma + MC$ eutectic reaction, with the remaining liquid solidifying to give the $M_{23}C_6$ films. Thus, the first reaction that gives rise to the MC eutectic carbides in as cast as well as in T1 of standard composition (0.8%C) high speed steels containing vanadium contents greater the 1% of T1 [14]. The above observations though would suggest that the morphology of the product of the $L \rightarrow MC + \gamma$ reaction is influenced by cooling rate. In the present study the MX particles coarsened both with increases in sintering temperature and time. This would indicate that the MX particles are present at the sintering temperature and are not formed by solidification of liquid on cooling. This is consistent with the known higher stability of V(CN) compared to VC in steels [173]. On

crossing the solidus the globular M_3C carbides present at lower temperatures are replaced by M_3C films. The size and volume fraction of the M_3C pools increased with temperature. Thus sintering is initiated by the formation of a liquid containing Cr-Fe-V-Mo-W since all these elements are present in the M_3C carbide, Figure 3.20. The grain boundary M_6C films are produced as a result of solidification of some of the liquid probably via a eutectic $L \rightarrow \gamma + M_6C$ reaction. Increases in sintering time, Figure 3.23, and temperature, Figure 3.17, resulted in the concentration and clustering of MX at the grain boundaries, whilst the prior austenite grains become denuded in M_6C and MX phases. It is believed that the MX particles which become trapped in the liquid, grow via mass transport through the liquid at the expense of the intragranular MX carbonitrides which dissolve. Certainly the cored microstructures of the grain boundary MX particles observed in back scattered electron images is indicative of compositional differences, i.e. a reduction in average atomic number contrast, from centre to periphery, Figure 3.17(l). At the same time the grain boundary M_6C also coarsen by precipitation from the liquid, as they grow they envelope MX particles and become more irregular, Figure 3.17(g) to (l). In the earlier studies of Urcola and co-workers dealing with sintering of high speed steels in $N_2-H_2-CH_4$ atmosphere they have stated that the MX particles seen in their alloys were due to the *in situ* transformation of MC into MX. At the same time they report [26,27,29] an increase in vanadium content for MC in vacuum sintered materials of about 40 wt% to about 70 wt% (excluding N and C) for MX particles in atmosphere sintered alloys. It is difficult to see how *in situ* transformation involving inward diffusion of N and rejection of C could lead to a rise in vanadium content. Whereas, as proposed above, the development of MX particles through mass transport via the liquid would lead to compositional changes.

The sintering mechanism for nitrogen sintering of P68 suggested in the present investigation is schematically shown in Figure 4.10. In summary, the initiation of the

supersolidus liquid phase sintering of the P68 composition is a two stage process. The first being the transformation of MC to MX in the solid state. Carbon is rejected into the matrix which then combines with Cr and Fe to form globular M_3C . The liquation of these M_3C carbides on crossing the solidus enables the formation of a Cr rich liquid which initiates the densification of the material. As the material densifies intragranular MX dissolve whilst grain boundary MX grow. One of the key observations in the study of the effects varying vanadium and carbon contents was the change in volume fraction of irregular grain boundary M_3C with composition. This phase was absent in the 8,10 and 12 wt% V alloys containing 1.6 wt% C, Figures 3.29(b1), (c1), (d1) and (e2). Whereas in the other alloys increasing carbon content increased the volume fraction of M_3C carbide, e.g. Figures 3.28(c), (h) and (i) and 3.29(a4), (b4), (c2), (c3) and (d3).

The earlier work of Wright et al [105], dealing with variations in sintering characteristics of T1 alloys (Fe-18W-4Cr-1V-C) containing nominal carbon contents in the range 0.6-1.6 wt% is of particular relevance for this discussion and will be reviewed in detail. In their work they reported a decrease in the DTA determined solidus temperature from 1330°C at 0.6 wt% C to 1166°C at 1.4 wt% C and 1156°C at 1.6 wt% C. These are comparable to T_{os} temperatures, as defined in Figure 3.7, determined from sintered curves for the same alloys, Figure 4.5. Furthermore in alloys containing up to 1.2 wt% C the onset of sintering was associated with the appearance of M_6C films at prior austenite grain boundaries. The amount of grain boundary films increased as the sintering temperature was raised and sample distortion coincided with the appearance of herringbone M_6C eutectic structures within the microstructure. This was identical to the sintering behaviour of P72, P73 and P74 alloys containing 1.6 wt% C since on crossing T_{os} , i.e. the solidus, M_6C grain boundary films formed and distortion was associated with the appearance of M_6C eutectic carbides, Figure 3.29(e2) and (e3). In the higher carbon alloys, the commencement of rapid

densification coincided with the formation of grain boundary films of a Fe-Cr rich phase instead of M_6C . Also in these higher carbon alloys, sample distortion coincided with the appearance of skeletal structures of the Fe-Cr rich phase. Again similar behaviour to that observed in alloys containing 2.0 wt% and higher amounts of carbon. The 1.6 wt% C alloy they studied contained large globular M_3C particles at temperatures below T_{os} . On crossing the solidus these particles liquated and the volume fraction of liquid formed was large enough to cause sample distortion before full density was attained. Again the behaviour of the P73 (3.4 wt% C) and P74 (4 wt% C) alloys exhibited similar behaviour. Wright et al correlated the sintering behaviour of this group of alloys with the pseudobinary section at 18 wt% W and 4 wt% Cr through the Fe-Cr-W-C system, Figure 4.11. Lower sintering temperatures were associated with the decrease in solidus with increasing carbon content. In particular, they attributed the formation of the Fe-Cr rich carbide to heating and cooling of samples through the invariant $\gamma + L + M_6C + M_3C$ region of Figure 4.11. Similarly, sintering of the lower carbon containing alloys was considered to have taken place in the $L + \gamma + M_6C$ phase field with the M_6C grain boundary films arising due to solidification of liquid by the $L \rightarrow \gamma + M_6C$ eutectic reaction. A more recent calculated pseudobinary section through the Fe- W- Cr- V- C system at 18 W- 4 Cr- 1 V (wt%) also predicts the existence of invariant $L + \gamma + M_6C + M_7C_3$ and $L + \gamma + M_6C + M_{23}C_6$ phase fields at carbon contents greater than 1.4 - 1.5 wt% [195]. In further work on these same alloys Lemoisson identified the Fe-Cr rich phase as $M_{23}C_6$ [195]. This would suggest a closer correlation with the calculated phase diagram of Figure 4.12 which predicts $M_{23}C_6$, than the much older diagram of Figure 4.11.

The difference between the present study and that of Wright et al is the presence of nitrogen. As shown in Table 3.10 and Figure 3.32 the alloy nitrogen content was influenced by both the vanadium and carbon contents. The effects of this on microstructure will be

discussed later but as can be seen from Figure 3.33 variations in alloy content had a significant effect on T_{os} temperature. This data is replotted in Figure 4.13 to include the effect of nitrogen. Since it is known from DTA studies, Figure 3.37 that T_{os} is the solidus temperature, Figure 4.13 is showing the variation in solidus temperatures at different compositions through the Fe/ 9W/ 3Mo/ 9Co/ 6-12V/ 1.6-4C/ 0.8-2.4N system with each curve representing a pseudobinary section in which the point TE (see Figure 4.11), which defines the start of the invariant phase field present in all high speed steels systems [114], Figure 1.4, at about 1150°C is shifted to higher total C+ N contents with increasing vanadium content. This observation is consistent with trends observed with phase diagrams calculated for high speed steel type compositions containing 5-15 wt% V [83], Figure 4.8. As can be seen, due to the ferrite stabilising properties of vanadium, increasing the vanadium content shifts the γ phase fields to the right and, though not shown on the diagram, the invariant field as well.

As different carbon contents for the same vanadium content alloys were used in the present investigation, the effect of both elements on the sintering temperatures, is shown in Figures 3.33 and 3.34. As it can be seen all the three temperatures – T_{os} , T_m and T_d – follow the same trend, i.e. a decreasing with the increased carbon content, which corresponds to a solidus decreasing, and consequently to a lower sintering temperature, and increasing with vanadium (for same alloys carbon contents). As it can be seen in Figure 3.33 (c) and (d), for the 10 and 12 wt% vanadium content alloys respectively, when the carbon content was over 3 %, the three temperatures became very close to one another compressing the sintering plateau. This was due to the high vanadium + carbon + nitrogen content of these alloys. In fact, it is known [1,44] that vanadium is a ferrite stabiliser, capturing carbon to form carbides, impoverishing the matrix in that element, the matrix becoming ferritic. However, independently of the vanadium content, it can be observed in Figure 3.33 and Figure 3.35

that when carbon content was increased the sintering temperatures get closer of the 1100°C temperature. This can suggest that a compositional limit was reached, it existing an invariable region at about the referred to temperature. On the other hand, the decreasing interval between T_{os} and T_d temperatures when both carbon and vanadium contents were increased, suggests a constriction of the $\gamma + \text{liquid} + \text{carbides/carbonitride}$ region. The vanadium effect on the sintering temperatures of the same alloys is shown in Figure 3.34. In this figure it can be seen that for a constant carbon content, sintering temperatures were found to increase concomitantly with vanadium alloy content.

The microstructural evolution observed during atmosphere sintering will now be discussed within the content of a pseudobinary phase diagram representation of the alloy system, shown schematically in Figure 4.14. In terms of observed sintered microstructures of the alloys used in the present work, they can be collated into 3 generic groups, as shown in Figure 4.15. A first group having 1.6 wt% C which showed MX carbonitrides and M_6C carbides, e.g. Figures 3.29(a1), (b1), (c1) and (d1). A second group having carbon contents in the range 2-2.7 wt% which showed MX, M_6C and M_3C when sintered and furnace cooled, whilst when P68 (2.4 wt% C) was sintered and quenched M_3C carbides were absent of the microstructure, Figure 3.23. This M_3C carbide volume fraction was found to increase concomitantly with alloy C content, Figures 3.17(j), 3.29(a4) and 3.29(b4). The last group having 3.4 and 4 wt% C showed MX, M_6C and large amounts of M_3C carbides, these alloys attained distortion before full density, Figure 3.29(c3) and (d3).

Group I alloys, did show no M_3C carbides, except the 6 wt% V alloy, P75, where in some specimens this carbide was observed, Figure 3.28(b). This was attributed to the lower V content of this alloy, when compared to the other alloys of this very group, P72 (8% V), P73 (10% V) and P74 (12% V). The high sintering temperatures of these alloys were due to

their high solidus, this being a consequence of the low carbon content, Figure 4.15. Densification was promoted by a W-Mo rich liquid, Figure 3.29(a1) originating from the liquation of the M_6C carbides.

Group II alloys showed globular M_3C carbides at low temperatures, 600°-950°C, which are believed to favour the first liquid that formed, promoting densification. Skeletal grain boundaries M_3C carbides volume fraction were found to increase with carbon content, the sintering temperature decreasing with increasing carbon. Therefore, it is believed that in this group II, densification was promoted by the presence of a Cr rich liquid at the grain boundaries. Fast cooled P68 alloy specimens sintered above 1200°C did not show any M_3C carbides. The M_3C carbide was also absent in the P68 specimens sintered for sintering times in excess of 5 minutes for sintering temperatures below 1200°C. This suggested that this composition was placed left of point TE, and when rapid cooled the solidification of the liquid occurred via a $L \rightarrow M_6C + MX + \gamma$ reaction, though slow cooling was carried out through a $L \rightarrow M_6C + MX + M_3C + \gamma$ reaction, right of point TE, due to compositional effects in the solidification front [203,204,205,206]. An explanation for this is now presented. Hence, P68 composition is probably placed left of TE, but close to it and as solidification of the liquid takes place, the already formed MX which grow in the liquid, impoverished it in V. As V is an α -stabiliser, hence, with V impoverishing of the liquid, point TE moves left. On the other hand C content of the liquid was increased due to dissolution of *in situ* formed MX carbonitrides and M_6C carbides. This fact moves P68 composition to the right. Therefore, the combined effect of these two facts, and because P68 composition would be about left of point TE, promotes the formation of M_3C carbides on slow furnace cooled specimens.

Finally, in group III, the presence of large amounts of M_3C carbides present already in undersintered specimens, Figure 3.28(I), impeded densification of these alloys. In fact, on

crossing the solidus, M_3C carbides liquated, promoting the apparition of excessive liquid which caused specimens distortion. Hence, M_3C carbide seemed to be the responsible for sintering behaviour of these alloys. Its lack impeding sintering of low carbon alloys, group I, its presence within a certain range (not quantitatively determined) promoted sintering to full density of alloys of group II, and excessive amounts of it, impeded the sintering of group III alloys.

The variation in T_{os} , T_m and T_d temperatures of the alloys used in present study with V and C content, Figures 3.33, 3.34 and 3.35 and, taking into account the C + 12/14 N content of the same alloys, Figure 4.13 showed for the same V content a decreasing of these temperatures with increasing carbon. Figure 4.16 shows the sintering data for M2 (0.9-1.1C/ 2V) [27], T15 (1.6-1.8C/ 5V) [27] and T42 (1.4-1.6C/ 3V and 2.2-2.8C/ 7V) [32,36] alloys sintered in 90%N₂-9%H₂-1%CH₄ atmospheres. As can be seen the trends are identical to Figure 4.13. As to their microstructures, similar aspects were observed in these alloys compared to those of the present research. In fact, densification of M2 alloy (2V,0.9-1.1C) [27] was carried out after the appearance of M_6C grain boundary films, which suggests a W-Mo rich liquid, comparable to the alloys of group I, whilst in higher carbon alloys such as T15 (1.6-1.8C/ 5V) [27] and T42 (1.4-1.6C/ 3V and 2.2-2.8C/ 7V) [32,36] the observation of a Cr rich carbide at the grain boundaries, suggests sintering behaviour comparable to that of alloys of group II.

Among all the different compositions used in the present investigation, Table 3.9, the minimum OST temperature was obtained for the P77 and P81 alloys, it being 1150°C. Lower sintering temperatures are claimed to be achieved by Albornoz [36] and Tallachia et al [35] using similar T42-type composition powders (2.71C, 4.38Cr, 9.2Co, 7.2V, 3.7Mo,

9.2W). Nevertheless, these authors used finer particle powder fractions in their sintering experiments. Hence, powders with sizes below 25 μm , 50 μm and 75 μm reached full density at 1135°, 1140° and 1145°C, the temperature reduction is probably due to a consequence of greater capillary forces due to the powder fraction used [112] and not due to any composition effect.

The MX carbonitrides found in the specimens of the present research, have similar content of metallic elements, to the ones reported by other authors [27,28,29,36], working in similar sintering atmospheres and using T-type HSS's, Table 4.3. As reported earlier, these were the only nitrogen containing phases, Table 3.12. For the same alloy carbon content, when vanadium was raised, the MX carbonitrides showed higher nitrogen content, Table 3.12. On the other hand, for the same vanadium content of the alloys when the alloy carbon was raised, nitrogen content was found to decrease in the carbonitrides. As it can be observed in Figure 3.32 and Table 3.10, nitrogen content of the alloys sintered at the respective OST in $\text{N}_2+7\%\text{H}_2$ atmosphere was found to vary accordingly to alloy composition. The elements which were found to influence nitrogen content of the alloys were vanadium and carbon. Hence, as seen in Figure 3.32, for the same vanadium content, nitrogen was found to decrease with increasing carbon content of the alloys. At constant carbon content, nitrogen content of the alloys was found to increase concomitantly with vanadium content.

The observed fact that the nitrogen content of the alloys decreased with increasing carbon content can be explained by the following balance:

i.e. if the carbon dissolved into the matrix was already high, the necessary rejection of carbon from the MC carbides to the matrix to form carbonitrides became more difficult,

which causes a lower nitrogen content of the alloy. On the other hand, it is known that carbon decreases the solubility of nitrogen in iron, as shown in Figure 4.17 [123].

All the MX carbonitrides showed the same globular morphology both in this research and other authors' works. The main difference was the clustering observed for the ones of the present research, as a consequence of both the slow heating and cooling rates and amount of liquid present, as discussed previously. However, for the specimens sintered up to distortion, especially for alloys containing 1.6 wt% V, some MX were found to become faceted, their cross section being rectangular, as shown in Figure 3.29 (e2) and (e3). As reported in the "Results" section, where it was possible, the MX volume fraction was determined, Figure 3.30. The MX volume fraction was found to decrease, for the same vanadium content, with increasing carbon content. For the same carbon content, MX volume fraction was found to decrease with decreasing vanadium content. This observation, once more, enhances the fact that increasing the carbon content of the alloy, and subsequently of the matrix due to carbide dissolution, less carbonitrides can be formed and lower the nitrogen content of the alloy.

Comparing these microstructural features with the ones reported by Palma et al [26,29], Jauregi et al [27], Urrutibeaskoa et al [28,31,32], Talacchia et al [30,33,34,35], Zelada [106] and Albornoz [36], some differences were observed. In fact, in the present research the irregular shaped M_6C carbides, present in the majority of the sintered specimens, formed a more or less continuous network at the grain boundaries, sometimes along with the chromium-rich M_3C carbides, both being decorated with MX carbonitrides, Figure 3.29. In Urcola's and co-workers papers [26-36], this feature was not reported, though the MX were mainly located at the grain boundaries [29,32,36,37], the chromium-rich carbides being reported as M_7C_3 [36] (occurring when low cooling rates were used) and the M_6C carbides were not decorated with MX, this occurring only when

eutectic carbides were present [36]. Besides any variance in composition, among the powders used in the present investigation and those used at CEIT, this difference can be attributed to the different heating and cooling rates used in the investigations. In fact, Urcola and co-workers used heating rates in the range $50^{\circ}\text{C}-240^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ to the sintering temperature with samples being quenched from the sintering temperature at a rate of $\approx 250^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ [26], while in the present research for comparison with the vacuum sintered material, the heating rate was $10^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$, with 1 hour soaking at sintering temperature and furnace cooled, the average cooling rate being $<30^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$. In a different project at INETI [207] using the same P77 and P81 alloys, when the heating rate was increased up to $30^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ and shorter sintering times (30 min.) were used the M_3C deleterious carbide networks were minimised. Hence, the M_3C carbide networks were due to the presence of an excess amount of liquid at the grain boundaries, which was promoted by the long heating, cooling and sintering times.

The discussion will now turn to a consideration of the bend strength determined in 3-point loading of P68, P77 and P81 samples processed under optimal conditions. Weibull statistics is often used to analyse the strength data of HSS's, as they are brittle or quasi brittle materials [208,209]. Since it gives a measure of the data scattering and consequently the material reliability, Weibull modulus "m" is of special relevance for engineering applications. Fully hardened HSS's show typical Weibull modulus as follows: T15: 6-16 [96], ASP60: 12-13 [19] and M2: 12 [210].

Though influencing the bending strength of the specimens, heat treatment temperatures were found not having any direct relation with the Weibull modulus, Figure 4.18. As seen in Figure 4.18, practically all the specimens sets showed higher Weibull

modulus than the other HSS's reported in the literature referred to above, the alloy which shows the highest values of m being the P77, Figure 4.18(c).

Weibull analysis assumes failure for a single population of flaws. Whilst in the vacuum sintered failures were predominantly initiated by pores, Figure 3.45(a), a wider range of failure initiation defects were observed in atmosphere sintered samples, pores, Si inclusions originating from the crucible of the melting furnace and oxide inclusions at prior particle boundaries due to the N_2 -7% H_2 atmosphere being less effective at reducing oxides at the lower sintering temperatures compared to vacuum. Weibull analysis thus is probably not strictly valid since this can decrease the Weibull modulus [97]

Taking into account the microstructures obtained in the nitrogen sintering trials, i.e. continuous carbides at grain boundaries, it was anticipated that bend strength values of these specimens would be lower than the ones for the vacuum sintered specimens. In fact, though having coarser MC carbides ($\approx 10\mu m$), vacuum sintered samples did not show continuous grain boundary carbide films which normally weaken sintered high speed steels [19,73]. The bend strength values obtained for the experimental alloys sintered in vacuum in the present research, Table 4.4, agree well with previous reported results for similar alloys (T42-type) [9,211] and even for other HSS types [8,9,10,19,20,42], Table 4.5. Nevertheless, the reported results obtained in 4-point bending tests [9,211] are quite lower than the ones of the present research, which were obtained in a 3-point bending test rig. This can be attributed to the volume of material that is loaded to the maximum stress in 4-point bending test than 3-point bending. Hence, the probability of finding a microstructure defect is higher in 4-point compared to 3-point loading.

With regard to the nitrogen sintered alloys, the bend strength results of the present research's specimens are higher than the reported ones, obtained for similar alloys sintered in similar conditions [35]. In fact, Tallacchia et al [35] reported fracture strength values of

0.5 up to 1 GPa for a T42-type (7.2 V, 2.2 C wt%) HSS with hardness ranging 825-930 HV, and 1.1 up to 1.5 GPa for another T42-type (7.2 V, 2.7 C wt%) with hardness ranging 820-950 HV. These authors only reported a fracture strength value of 2 GPa for a HIPped set of the 7.2 V, 2.7 C wt% alloy which had a hardness value of 870 HV. However, due to differences in sample size, 6 mm width and 20 mm length in Tallacchia et al [35,36] compared to 2 mm width and 16 mm length in the present work a direct comparison was not possible. Furthermore since Talacchia et al did not determine Weibull moduli it is not possible to use the equations developed by Wronski [97] to correct for different sample size and test geometry.

A number of authors [25,212,213,214] have reported that fracture in a number of cast and wrought and powder metallurgy high speed steels involves a process of subcritical crack growth. In this mechanism a crack nucleus is formed by cracking at or just below the tensile surface of a microstructural feature such as large carbide or inclusion. Cracks then grow subcritically in the matrix, eventually reaching a critical size, producing catastrophic failure. Examination of the tensile surfaces of failed P68, P77 and P81 samples did not reveal any evidence of subcritical crack growth. Cracks observed adjacent to the fracture face, Figure 3.45(b) and (c), were considered to caused by the release of energy on failure rather than being the cause of failure.

Many authors [215,216] have analysed fracture of high speed steels using linear elastic fracture mechanic models, assuming elliptical or semi-elliptical flaws, Figure 4.19, using Irwin's equations for semi elliptical surface flaws:

$$a_{sc} = \frac{K_{IC}^2}{\pi\sigma^2} \left[\frac{\phi^2 - 0.212(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_y})^2}{12} \right] \quad (4.4)$$

where:

$$\phi = \int_0^{\pi/2} \left[\sin^2 \theta + (\frac{a_{sc}}{c})^2 \cos^2 \theta \right]^{1/2} d\theta \quad (4.5)$$

a_{sc} = critical crack depth, w = surface depth width, σ = applied stress and ϕ = elliptical integral. Values of ϕ depend upon the ratio of a/c . These are given for different a/c ratios in Table 4.6. Irwin [97] also gives for embedded elliptical flaws the following expression for the critical crack depth

$$a_{ic} = \frac{K_{IC}^2}{\pi\sigma^2} \left[\phi - 0.176 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_y} \right)^2 \right] \quad (4.6)$$

These equations were used to estimate theoretical flaw sizes. Yield stresses were estimated from Vickers hardness values assuming $\sigma_y = 1/3$ HV. K_{IC} values taken from the data of Talacchia [36] for nitrogen sintered alloys similar in composition and microstructure to P68. The results of this analysis are presented in Table 4.6, along with the ranges for observed flaw sizes. As can be seen these theoretical flaws were comparable or smaller than observed ones. Hence, this could explain the absence of evidence for subcritical crack growth since pores and cracks formed in carbide clusters or oxide layers are likely to be of critical dimensions.

This work has shown that nitrogen sintering of HSS containing vanadium in the range 10-12 wt% contents, were difficult or impossible to sinter to full density, powders possessing 6-8 wt% V showed good sintering characteristics, their sintering temperatures being compatible with industrial atmosphere furnaces, which are normally limited to 1150°C maximum sintering temperature. The fine microstructure comprising of fine MX carbonitrides (up to 4-5 μm max.) instead of coarser MC carbides (≈ 10 μm) may provide these materials with improvements in cutting performance, as it is known that coarse carbides are harmful to cutting performance [7,59]. Industrial trials, using alloys similar to the ones used in the present investigation, have been recently carried out under the framework of a CRAFT program [217] in the wood cutting industry, cutting tests revealing

additional benefits in tool life and surface finishing [97]. On the other hand, as shown in the present study, higher vanadium-low carbon containing powders (10-12 wt% V-1.6 wt%C) contained higher volume fractions of fine MX carbonitrides, Figure 3.30, this being a very attractive characteristic of these powders since in general finer microstructures lead to higher strength [19,73]. Thus there is a possibility of using such powders to produce very fine microstructure materials: as it was observed that undersintered low carbon-high vanadium powders possess very fine MX carbonitrides dispersed in the matrix and/or grain boundaries, Figure 3.38(d), their size being <1-2 μm , M_6C carbides being similar in size. Hence, undersintering these materials to 95% densification followed by containerless HIPping to fully density, could produce very fine microstructure materials which could possess improved mechanical and cutting characteristics.

Table 4.1 - Actual, Sato's Equation (4.1) [127] and DIN 17 350 Standard Calculated Carbon Contents of P68, P77 and P81 Powders

Alloy	Actual C(wt%)	Equation 4.1	DIN 17 350
P68	2.2	2.13	2.16
P77	2.7	1.9	2.07
P81	2.6	1.6	1.76

Table 4.2 - T_{os}, T_m, OST and T_d Temperatures of Several HSS

Alloy	T _{os}	T _m	T _d	OST	Sint. Window	Carbon (wt%)	Vanadium (wt%)	Ref.
ASP60	1210	1230	1260	1235	20	2.3	6.5	19
HITACHI	1180	1230	1250	1240	<10	2.0	4.4	20
T42	1220	1240	1270	1245	≈30	1.4	2.7	136
T42	1200	1230	1270	1240	≈20	1.5	3	95
T42	1175	1215	1250 (?)	1235	?	1.4	3	32
T15	?	?	>1280	1270	<10	1.6	4.75	8
T15	1210	1250	1280(?)	1270	?	1.55	4.7	32
M3/2	1220	1240	1270	1250	≈10	1.1	3	48
M2	1230	1255	1290	1255	<5	0.9	2	48
T1	1290	1310	1330	1320	≈5	0.8	1	105
T1	1290	1310	1335	1315	<20	1	1	185
T1	1180	1220	1300	1240	70	1.4	1	105
T1	1140	1170	1250	1180	≈60	1.7	1	105
P68	1215	1250	1280	1260	10	2.2	8	
P81	1130	1190	1250	1200	<40	2.6	6	
P77	1130	1190	1250	1200	<40	2.7	7	

Table 4.3 - Chemical Composition of Carbides and Carbonitrides of Several Alloys Sintered in Nitrogen-Based Atmosphere (wt%)

MX Carbonitrides

Alloy	Sint.Temp °C	Fe	W	Cr	Mo	V	Co	Ref.
T1	1330	1.6	18.2	5.8	3.8	70.5	-	29
T42	1185	7	9	5.7	5	72	1	29
T42mod	1150	7.9	9.7	2.9	3.7	74.2	1.63	36
T15	1225	6.2	6.2	4.4	1.3	72.0	0.1	27/29
M2		11.5	3.1	5.4	2.7	77.3	-	27
ASP30	1230	7.6	10.1	4.6	7.4	68.3	1.9	31

M₆C Carbides

Alloy	Sint.Temp °C	Fe	W	Cr	Mo	V	Co	Ref.
T1	1330	25.5	68	2.3	2.4	1.6	-	29
T42	1185	26.5	49	2.3	16.2	1.7	4.4	29
T42mod	1150	22.1	57.7	2.4	12	1.5	4.2	36
T15	1225	26.4	62.5	2.2	5.8	1.9	1.3	27/29
M2		31.6	42.9	2.6	21.4	1.6	-	27
ASP30	1230	27.1	46.8	2.5	18.3	1.7	3.7	31

Fe-Cr Carbide

Alloy	Sint.Temp °C	Fe	W	Cr	Mo	V	Morphology	Ref.
T42 mod	1225 #	70.4	7.0	13.6	8.4	-	perlitic/M ₇ C ₃	36
T42 mod	1225 #	51.77	14.4	15.84	5.5	3.77	perlitic/M ₇ C ₃	36
T10.92C	1290*	53.4	12.6	26.1	2.1	5.8	skeletal	105
T11.78C	1140*	59.0	11.5	22.3	1.0	6.2	globular	105
T11.78C	1200*	58.2	13.2	13.2	1.2	5.6	skeletal	105

- Sintered in Nitrogen-based atmosphere

* - Sintered in Vacuum

Table 4.4 - Bend Strength -Assuming Linear Elastic Behaviour and Converted for American Standard ANSE/ASTM B528-76 - and Weibull Modulus Obtained in the Present Investigation

Alloy		$\theta\gamma$ (°C)	Tempering (°C)	Bend Strength (MPa) ☆	Bend Strength (MPa) ☑	Weibull Modulus m
P68	VS	1100	510	2297±87	1973	17
		1150	550	2384±118	1954	13
		1175		2080±54	1883	26
		1200		2049±78	1760	17
	N ₂ + H ₂ (US+HIP)	1100	600	2082±114	1706	13
	N ₂ + H ₂ (FS)		585	2031±81	1759	18
P77	N ₂ + H ₂	1075	475	1795±50	1618	25
	N ₂ + H ₂ + HIP			1874±55	1690	25
	N ₂ + H ₂		540	1904±66	1661	19
	N ₂ + H ₂ + HIP			1915±58	1740	27
P81	N ₂ + H ₂	1075	460	1915±55	1711	23
	N ₂ + H ₂ + HIP			1912±78	1626	16
	N ₂ + H ₂		530	1935±80	1662	17
	N ₂ + H ₂ + HIP			1870±90	1554	14

☆ - Bend Strength Values Calculated Assuming Linear Elastic Behaviour

☑ - Bend Strength Values Converted to American Standard ANSE/ASTM B 528-76

VS - Vacuum Sintered

N₂+H₂ - Nitrogen Sintered

Table 4.5 - Bend Strength Values of Several HSS

HSS	TRS (GPa)	Processing	Reference
T1	3.7	VS+HIP	103
T1	2.1 / 1.9* 1.7 / 1.6* 1.3 / 1.3*	CWL CWT VS	9
T1	2.7 2.2	VS+HIP HIP	42
T1	1.5	VS	10
T15	1.6-2.2	VS	8
T15	1.7-3.4	VS	96
T15	1.2-2.7	VS	7
T42	2.2 / 1.9* 2.0 / 1.6* 2.4 / 1.2*	CWL CWT VS	9
T42	2.8*-3.5* 2.1*-2.4* 1.8*	CWL CWT VS	211
T42(mod.)	0.5-2	N ₂	35
T42(mod.)	0.16-2.6	N ₂	
ASP23	4	HIP	18
ASP23	>5	HIP	6
ASP60	2	VS	19
ASP60	1.9*-2.99*	VS	25
HITACHI	1.5-1.8	VS	20

VS-Vacuum Sintered; CW-Cast and Wrought; N₂-Atmosphere Sintered; HIP-Hot Isostatic Pressing; L-Longitudinal; T-Transversal; * - 4-point Bending Test

Table 4.6 - Theoretical Critical Surface (a_{sc}) and Internal (a_{ic}) Flaw Sizes for Nitrogen Sintered Powders

MATERIAL	HV30	σ_y^*	σ_F	K_{IC}^{**}	a_{sc}			a_{ic}			observed flaw size μm
					a/c			a/c			
					0.2	0.6	1	0.2	0.6	1	
					ϕ			ϕ			
GNm^{-2}	GNm^{-2}	$MNm^{-3/2}$	1.05	1.28	1.57	1.05	1.28	1.57			
P68	885	3.0	2.1	15	13	16	20	16	20	24	10-30
P68	931	3.1	2.0	14	12	15	19	15	18	23	10-30
P77	950	3.2	1.9	15	16	20	25	20	24	30	10-20
P77	997	3.3	1.8	14	16	20	24	19	24	29	10-20
P77	990	3.3	1.9	14	15	18	22	18	22	27	10-20
P77	966	3.2	1.9	15	16	20	25	20	24	30	10-20
P77	917	3.1	1.9	14	14	17	21	17	21	26	10-20
P81	980	3.3	1.9	14	14	17	21	17	21	26	10-30
P81	970	3.2	1.9	14	14	17	21	17	21	26	10-30
P81	934	3.1	1.9	13	12	14	18	14	17	22	10-20
P81	964	3.2	1.9	15	17	21	26	20	25	31	10-20

σ_y^* - Estimated as being 1/3 HV

K_{IC}^{**} - Estimated Value from [36] Data

Figure 4.1 - V/C Ratio Effect on Oxygen Content of Water Atomised Powders

Figure 4.2 - The Standard Free Energies Diagram of Formation of Oxides [64]

Figure 4.3(a) – Schematic Correlation Between DTA Traces and Sintering Curves

Figure 4.3(b) – Correlation Between DTA Traces and Sintering Curves of Vacuum Sintered (b1) P68, (b2) P77 and (b3) P81 Alloys

Figure 4.3(c) - Schematic Correlation Between DTA and Sintering Curves, Both Carried Out in Nitrogen Atmosphere

(d1)

(d2)

(d3)

(d4)

Figure 4.3(d) – Correlation Between DTA Traces and Sintering Curves for Alloys Sintered in $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere

a)

b)

Figure 4.4— Calculated Excess Carbon Equivalent of the Alloys Used in the Present Research

a) Calculation Taking into Account C, W, Mo, and V

b) Calculation Taking into Account C, W, Mo, V and N

Figure 4.5 – Comparison of T_{os} , T_m and T_d with *liquidus* and *solidus* temperatures determined by DTA for T1-type alloys, by Wright et al [105]

Figure 4.6 – Carbon Effect on T_{0s} , T_m and T_d of Vanadium Containing HSS

Figure 4.7 – Vanadium Effect on Tos, Tm and Td on Vanadium Containing HSS

- a) T1 [105], T42 [136], T15 [32]
- b) HITACHI [20], ASP60 [19], P68
- c) P81, P77

Figure 4.8 - Vanadium Content Influence on Phase Diagrams of the C-Cr-Fe-V-W System Calculated by Computer [83].

(a) 5 wt% V Content

Figure 4.8 - Vanadium Content Influence on Phase Diagrams of the C-Cr-Fe-V-W System Calculated by Computer [83].

(b) 10 wt% V Content

Figure 4.8 - Vanadium Content Influence on Phase Diagrams of the C-Cr-Fe-V-W System Calculated by Computer [83].

(c) 15 wt% V Content

Figure 4.9 – The Lehrer Diagram for the Equilibration of Iron with Ammonia-hydrogen Mixtures Showing Critical Ammonia Concentrations for the Formation of Iron Nitrides [199]

Up to A_{ci}

- Nitrogen starts to diffuse through grain boundaries. Nitrogen content is similar to the as-annealed powders.
- Nitrogen starts to be picked up by MC carbides and the *in situ* transformation into MX carbonitrides is initiated. Carbon is rejected to the matrix.
- The first carbon released forms globular M_3C chromium-rich cementite at the grain boundaries. Limited sintering is carried out through solid state sintering mechanisms.

Beyond A_{cf}

- Nitrogen content is similar to the specimens sintered at OST. MC/MX formed by *in situ* transformation start to dissolve due to their small size. MX formation at grain boundaries.

After T_{os}

- Dissolution/liquation of globular M_3C carbides. Formation of liquid at the grain boundaries. Densification through SLPS mechanisms. MX formed *in situ* continue to dissolve. The liquid drags MX's present at grain boundaries, which forms MX clusters. MX carbonitrides grow in the liquid.

At T_d

- M_6C liquate and liquid solidifies on cooling as M_6C and M_3C eutectic carbides. MX's which were transported by the liquid decorate both M_6C and M_3C . Some M_2C eutectic carbides are also observed.

Figure 4.10 – Schematic Representation of the Nitrogen Sintering Mechanism of High Vanadium-High Carbon HSS's Made Taking into Account the Observations of P68 $N_2+7\%H_2$ Atmosphere Sintered Specimens.

Figure 4.11 - Pseudobinary Section Through Fe-W-Cr-C System at 18% W-4% Cr [105]

Figure 4.12 – Calculated Phase Diagram for C-4Cr-18W-1V-Fe bal. [195]

Figure 4.13 – Carbon plus Nitrogen Effect on the T_{0s} Temperatures of the Experimental Alloys Used in the Present Investigation, for Several Vanadium Contents.

Figure 4.14 – Schematic Partial Phase Diagrams of:

- T1 HSS – in solid black
- High Vanadium HSS – dotted (model)

Figure 4.15 – Schematic Representation in the Pseudobinary Phase Diagram of the Several Compositons Used in the present Study

Figure 4.16 – Carbon plus Nitrogen Content Effect on the Tos, Tm and Td Temperatures of V-rich Alloys sintered in 90%N₂+9H₂+CH₄ Atmosphere
M2 [27], T15 [27], T42-3V [32], T42-7V [36]

Figure 4.17 - Influence of Some Elements on the Nitrogen Solubility in Iron Melts at 1600°C with Respect to their Position in the Periodic System. Influence is Plotted as Height of the Blocks [123]

Figure 4.18 - Weibull Plots (Weibull modulus being shown in box) of:

(a) P68 Vacuum Sintered Specimens

(b) P68 N₂+7% H₂ Sintered Specimens

(c) P77 N₂+7% H₂ Sintered Specimens

(d) P81 N₂+7% H₂ Sintered Specimens

Temperatures of Heat Treatments Shown on Plots Legends.

Figure 4.19 – Models of Flaws:
a) Semi-Elliptical Surface Flaw
b) Elliptical Embedded Flaw

5 - CONCLUSIONS

- High vanadium containing powders, whose vanadium and carbon contents were 10 and 12 wt% and 0.8 wt%, respectively, were difficult to atomise, due to the high melts viscosities resulting from oxidation in the furnace crucible prior to atomisation. These powders possessed oxygen contents in excess of 7000 p.p.m. Oxygen content was found to increase with increasing V/C ratio. However these high oxygen contents could be reduced by vacuum annealing for 3 to 5 hours at 950°C. After annealing oxygen contents were 3000-6000 ppm.
- Atomisation yields (amount of <125µm powder fraction) varied from 46 to 90 %. Mean particle sizes ranged 58-140 µm, which are normal for these types of water atomised alloys.
- Compressibility of as-annealed powders was found to vary with composition. In fact, the powder which showed higher green density (6.1 g cm⁻³) at the pressure used in this research, 700 MPa, was the P75, the composition with lowest vanadium (6wt%) and carbon (0.5wt%). This effect was believed to be caused by different carbide volume fractions. The green density was found to decrease with increasing vanadium content.
- The P68 composition could be vacuum sintered to full densities of 8.15 g cm⁻³ at 1260°C, possessing acceptable microstructure comprising of vanadium rich MC carbides 1-20 µm in diameter embedded in a bainitic/martensitic matrix which possessed a prior austenite grain size of <4-60 µm. The Sintering window was found to be about 10°C. Variations in compacting pressure were found not to influence density of

the specimens sintered on the sintering plateau. On the other hand carbon additions of 0.1 and 0.2 wt% decreased optimal sintering temperatures to 1250° and 1240°C, respectively, though no broadening of the sintering window had been observed.

Higher carbon containing P77 and P81 alloys were found not to be vacuum sinterable due to the formation of deleterious to mechanical properties grain boundary M_2C eutectic carbides. These carbides were present in specimens undersintered at 1190°C (8 g/cm³).

- Following sintering in a $N_2+7\%H_2$ atmosphere, the microstructure of the P68 composition comprised vanadium rich MX carbonitrides located mainly at grain boundaries with diameters in the range 1-3 μ m, grain boundary tungsten-molybdenum rich M_6C and chromium rich M_3C carbides. Full density in this case was 8.1 g cm⁻³ attained at 1200°C, which represents a 60°C decrease compared with the optimal sintering temperature obtained for vacuum sintering. Sintering in the $N_2+7\%H_2$ atmosphere enlarged the window to about 30°C.
- Sintering the experimental alloys of this research in $N_2+7\%H_2$ resulted in nitrogen contents of 0.9-2.4 wt%, this content being dependent on vanadium and carbon contents of the alloys. For the same carbon content, nitrogen was found to increase concomitantly with vanadium. On the other hand, for the same vanadium content nitrogen was found to decrease with increasing carbon. MX carbonitrides volume fraction was found to be dependent on composition: for the same carbon content the higher the vanadium the higher the MX volume fraction.

- Vanadium and carbon contents were found to influence sintering temperatures. Therefore, for the same vanadium content, the higher the carbon content the lower the sintering temperature. On the other hand for the same carbon content, the higher the vanadium content the higher the sintering temperature. However above a carbon content of 2.4 wt%, sintering temperatures could not be decreased due to the constriction of the $\gamma+L+\text{carbides}$ region, higher carbon contents resulted in distorted samples by sintering these compositions at 1100°C through the $\gamma+L+M_6C+MX+M_3C$ region, this region being present in all high speed steels. This is therefore a compositional barrier for design high speed steel alloys.
- In low carbon and high vanadium compositions distortion was associated with the formation of eutectic M_6C carbides, whilst for higher carbon compositions distortion was correlated with the formation of skeletal grain boundary M_3C carbides. The presence of large volume fractions of the deleterious to mechanical properties grain boundary M_3C skeletal carbide was attributed to sintering involving heating and cooling through an invariant $\gamma+L+M_6C+MX+M_3C$ phase region. All the compositions which fell within in this region were unsinterable. On the other hand, the sinterability of the alloys whose sintering comprised heating into and cooling from $\gamma+L+M_6C+MX$ phase region decreased with decreasing carbon content. The resultant increase in solidus temperatures raised sintering temperatures whilst the decrease in separation of the phase boundaries defining this region decreased sintering windows.
- A comprehensive nitrogen sintering mechanism was developed for the P68 alloy (and similars). Hence, at temperatures up to A_{ci} nitrogen diffused in volume and through grain boundaries and is absorbed by the MC carbides which are therefore transformed *in*

situ into MX carbonitrides. Carbon is then rejected to the matrix. The first carbon released forms globular M_3C chromium rich cementite at the grain boundaries. Specimens sintered at temperatures of 600°C, i.e. below austenite transformation temperatures, showed a nitrogen content similar to as-annealed powders, 0.6 wt%. Sintering in the austenitic field, 800°-950°C, produced nitrogen contents compared to those for specimens sintered along the sintering plateau, i.e. about 1.2 wt%. Limited sintering was carried out through solid state sintering mechanisms. Beyond A_{cf} the *in situ* carbonitrides start to dissolve due to their small size, and MX were precipitated at grain boundaries. Carbon released to the matrix decreased solidus, and consequently sintering temperatures. When the solidus was crossed dissolution/liquation of globular M_3C carbides occurred, forming grain boundary liquid. Densification is then carried out through supersolidus liquid phase sintering mechanisms promoted by this iron-chromium rich liquid. MX formed *in situ* continue to dissolve. Grain boundary MX were dragged by the liquid forming clusters at grain boundary triple points. Contact with liquid result in MX particle coarsening with increasing time and/or increasing temperature. When distortion temperature was attained M_6C carbides liquated and liquid solidified on cooling as M_6C and M_3C eutectic carbides. MX particles which had been transported by the liquid decorated both M_6C and M_3C . Some M_2C eutectic carbides were also observed.

- In spite of the presence of M_3C and M_6C carbides networks at the grain boundaries, the resulting bending strength was similar or higher, 1.8-2.4 GPa, to equivalent alloys, i.e. T42-type alloys sintered in nitrogen-rich atmosphere which showed bending strength of 0.2-2.6 GPa.

6 - SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER WORK

As a consequence of the conclusions of the present research it can be reported that, as a first approach, the atomisation conditions of the compositions referred to in the previous section should be optimised, in order to produce powders with better characteristics, e.g. ligamental rather than irregular shapes. This can increase the powder flowability, by reduction of the interparticle friction, and increase the powder apparent density, which facilitate the automatic processing of the powders. Optimisation of the “as-atomised” carbon content should be done, as the high vanadium compositions (>8 wt% V) were difficult to atomise.

One alloy with no chromium could show the effect of this element in the sintering temperatures, specially in the T_{os} temperature. This way it could be remarked if the free carbon, released at low temperatures ($<T_{os}$) to the matrix due to the MX formation, it having no free carbide forming elements could drop or not the *solidus*, as like it was observed in the present research, this free carbon is tied in the formed chromium-rich M_3C carbides.

Sintering cycles studies varying both time and temperatures of other alloys rather than P68 could be done in order to optimise the sintering cycles and microstructures, particular regard could be the high vanadium/high carbon alloys.

STEM work on the precipitates could be done, in order to allow their explicit identification, especially the ones which precipitate at temperatures below A_{cf} in nitrogen rich atmosphere sintering. Microprobe nitrogen analysis of the M_2C carbides could be carried out.

The sintering of the specimens would be done using faster heating and cooling rates and shorter sintering times, in order to optimise the microstructures to allow better mechanical properties, such as bending strength.

Undersinter to about 92-95 % density, to produce fine microstructure and closed porosity, and further HIPping, to close remaining closed porosity, of high vanadium (10-12 wt%V) low carbon (1.6 wt%C) compositions would be of particular interest, as these compositions showed both higher nitrogen content and MX volume fraction. The high volume fraction of fine MX carbonitrides would favour grindability of these materials. Wear, grindability, fatigue and mechanical properties such as toughness are some areas of interest in the development of these materials to be compared with other high vanadium materials available in the market such as ASP60 or T15. TiN coating and cutting tests of the coated materials would be of particular interest as well.

An investigation of the heat treatment conditions can be done, in order to find out if and which conditions would allow a complete dissolution of the chromium-rich M_3C carbide, found at the slow cooled specimens.

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